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The Journal of Bio based Marketing (JBM) provides a forum for academics, researchers, entrepreneurs, young experts, professionals, educators to analyze global aspects of bio-based marketing as a theoretical idea and real business model in value chain of bio-based products. Covering all aspects of knowledge regulation and order including organizational issues, technology support, knowledge representation, transfer of knowledge and knowledge valorization. JBM focus on the following topics:

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ANALYSIS OF TRENDS IN PRODUCTION, CONSUMPTION AND TRADE IN THE AFRICAN ONIONS MARKET

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ABSTRACT

Onions are a crucial agricultural commodity in Africa contributing significantly to both domestic consumption and international trade. It requires attention due to the African Continental Free Trade Agreement that encourages regional integration on the continent. The onion industry dynamics in Africa is a complex interplay of factors such as climatic conditions, farming practices, pricing and consumer dynamics and market access that shapes production volumes, quality, trade and ultimately the livelihoods of millions engaged in onion farming and trade. The study for the first time investigates trends in onion production, consumption and trade among the five regions in Africa, comprising North Africa, West Africa, Central Africa, East Africa and Southern Africa. By so doing, provides insights on the performance of the onion sector from the lens of production, consumption and trade. Data for the study was drawn from the database of the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations and cover 1961-2022 (62 years), broken down into three periods to ease comparison (1961 - 1980), (1981 - 2000) and (2001 - 2022). The specific objectives of the study were to: 1. analyze the growth rates in onion production, consumption and trade across different regions of Africa. 2. estimate the doubling time in onion production, consumption and trade across different regions of Africa. 3. evaluate the contribution of area and yield to the growth of onion production across different regions in Africa. The findings from the study show that yield has not kept up with expansion in areas across Africa, despite both increased growth in consumption and trade. The study recommends investment in modern high yielding production technology and training across Africa, especially in West Africa in order to increase growth in onions yield.

KEYWORDS: Growth rate, doubling time, decomposition analysis, East Africa, West Africa, Middle Africa, North Africa, Southern Africa

ABSTRAKT

Zwiebeln sind ein wichtiges landwirtschaftliches Erzeugnis in Afrika, das sowohl für den Inlandsverbrauch als auch für den internationalen Handel von großer Bedeutung ist. Das afrikanische kontinentale Freihandelsabkommen, das die regionale Integration auf dem Kontinent fördert, erfordert besondere Aufmerksamkeit. Die Dynamik der Zwiebelindustrie in Afrika ist ein komplexes Zusammenspiel von Faktoren wie klimatische Bedingungen, Anbaupraktiken, Preisgestaltung, Verbraucherdynamik und Marktzugang, die Produktionsmengen, Qualität, Handel und letztlich die Lebensgrundlage von Millionen von Menschen, die im Zwiebelanbau und -handel tätig sind, beeinflussen. In der Studie werden zum ersten

Mal die Trends bei der Zwiebelproduktion, dem Verbrauch und dem Handel in den fünf Regionen Afrikas untersucht, die Nordafrika, Westafrika, Zentralafrika, Ostafrika und das südliche Afrika umfassen.

STICHWORTE: Wachstumsrate, Verdopplungszeit, Dekompositionsanalyse, Ostafrika, Westafrika, Mittleres Afrika, Nordafrika, Südliches Afrika.

RÉSUMÉ

Les oignons sont un produit agricole essentiel en Afrique, qui contribue de manière significative à la fois à la consommation intérieure et au commerce international. L'accord de libre-échange continental africain, qui encourage l'intégration régionale sur le continent, mérite que l'on s'y attarde. La dynamique de l'industrie de l'oignon en Afrique est une interaction complexe de facteurs tels que les conditions climatiques, les pratiques agricoles, la dynamique des prix et des consommateurs et l'accès au marché qui façonne les volumes de production, la qualité, le commerce et, en fin de compte, les moyens de subsistance de millions de personnes engagées dans la culture et le commerce de l'oignon. L'étude examine pour la première fois les tendances de la production, de la consommation et du commerce d'oignons dans les cinq régions d'Afrique, à savoir l'Afrique du Nord, l'Afrique de l'Ouest, l'Afrique centrale, l'Afrique de l'Est et l'Afrique australe.

MOTS-CLÉS: taux de croissance, temps de doublement, analyse de décomposition, Afrique de l'Est, Afrique de l'Ouest, Afrique centrale, Afrique du Nord, Afrique australe.

INTRODUCTION

Onions play a vital role on the African continent by contributing immensely in production, consumption and international trade (Zegeye, et al., 2024). The Onion vegetable belongs to the genus *allium* which is closely related to other vegetables such as garlic, shallots, and leeks (Braun, 2022). On average, a person consumes roughly 10 kilogram of onions per year and can be eaten raw, cooked, pickled, or powdered (Cattivelli, et al., 2021). Onions contain compounds that help protect the heart, reduce the risk of certain cancers and ease the process of the body to make insulin (Galavi, Hosseinzadeh, & Razavi, 2021).

Furthermore, Onions provide a veritable source of quercetin, and scientists have linked onions to many possible health benefits, for instance, the antioxidant properties in onions help prevent cell damage in the body by fighting inflammation and boosting the immune system. Onions are also a good source of vitamins and minerals as well as adding flavour to boost any breakfast, lunch, or dinner dish (Nemeth, Takacsova, & Piskula, 2003; Tawfeeq, Shallal, Abdulwahid, & Aldahham, 2023).

The cultivation of onions is widespread throughout Africa, with farmers producing the crop across diverse agroecological zones and climatic conditions (Emmanuel, Sulaiman, & Abu, 2024). The geographic distribution of onion production is influenced by soil fertility, water availability, temperature and market demand, leading to disparities in production levels and quality standards across different regions (Ochar & Kim, 2023). Despite facing numerous challenges, such as limited access to inputs, inadequate infrastructure, pests, diseases, and climate variability (Atairet & Umoh, 2022; Atairet, Umoh, & Atairet, 2024). Onion production remains a vital source of income and livelihood for millions of smallholder farmers across Africa (Zegeye et al., 2024). The resilience and adaptability of farmers play a critical role in mitigating these challenges and ensuring a steady supply of onions to meet both domestic and international demand (Jung, et al., 2024)

Egypt, Algeria, Sudan, and Nigeria lead onion production in Africa, making use of both irrigated and rain-fed agricultural systems to optimize output (Africa view facts, 2024). These nations meet substantial domestic demand while also contributing to regional onion trade, which bolsters economic ties within the African continent.

Accordingly, one of Africa's most significant policy decisions is the establishment of the Africa Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCFTA) in 2018. AfCFTA aims to create a single market for goods and services across the continent, promoting economic integration and growth. A primary challenge for agriculture under the AfCFTA is the existence of trade barriers (Simola, et al, 2022). These barriers can take the form of tariffs, quotas, and non-tariff measures that restrict the flow of agricultural products between member states (Nugroho, et al., 2024). In addition, infrastructure plays a crucial role in the agricultural sector, affecting everything from production to distribution (Abiri, Rizan, et al, 2023). Many African countries suffer from inadequate transportation networks, poor storage facilities, and limited access to markets (Khan, Nouman, Negrut, Abban, Cismas, & Siddiqi, 2024).

Agriculture in Africa is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, which can exacerbate existing challenges such as droughts, floods and pests (Onyeaka, et al., 2024). The Africa Continental Free Trade Agreement holds great potential for transforming the agricultural landscape across the continent. However, addressing the various challenges faced by the agricultural sector is crucial for its success. Therefore, understanding the underlying trends in onion production, consumption, and trade in Africa is essential for informing evidence-based policy decisions and interventions aimed at addressing the growth performance of this important crop.

Accordingly, this study explores the trends in regional onion production, consumption and trade in Africa by investigating production, consumption and trade growth rates, doubling time and sources of production growth and drawing policy implications based on the findings that can guide policymakers, researchers, development practitioners and other stakeholders in designing effective interventions and strategies to promote sustainable onion production, improve market opportunities and enhance livelihoods for smallholder farmers across Africa.

This study is essential due to its significant contributions to the continent's agricultural economy, food security and trade competitiveness and holds significant importance for various stakeholders. The trend analysis provides insights into improving agricultural productivity, enhancing food security, and promoting trade competitiveness across the continent.

Research Objective: The study therefore has the following specific objectives:

1. analyze the growth rates in onion production, consumption and trade across the five regions of Africa, i.e. West Africa, East Africa, Central Africa, Southern Africa, and North Africa from 1961-2022.
2. estimate the doubling time in onion production, consumption and trade across the five regions of Africa, i.e. West Africa, East Africa, Central Africa, Southern Africa, and North Africa from 1961-2022.
3. evaluate the contribution of the area and yield to the growth of onion production across the five regions of Africa, i.e. West Africa, East Africa, Central Africa, Southern Africa, and North Africa from 1961-2022.

Research methodology: The Study area is Africa, which comprises 54 countries (worldometers.info, 2024). Africa is the second largest continent in the world by land mass covering an area of approximately 30 million square kilometres, with an estimated population of 1.5 billion

(Rosenberg, 2024), and is roughly divided equally between males and females (countrymeters.info, 2024). According to the African Union (2024), Africa is made up of five regions, namely: West Africa, East Africa, North Africa, Central Africa and Southern Africa and each region is associated with an economic bloc. According to Gardiner & Smedley (2024), Agriculture is by far the single most important economic activity in Africa, employing a large number of the working population.

Data Source: Secondary data obtained from the Food and Agriculture Organization statistical database (FAOSTAT) was used in the study. Data used include area (ha), yield (kg/ha), production (tonnes), consumption (tonnes), export (tonnes), import (tonnes), export value (\$) and import value (\$) of onion for each region and Africa and cover 62 years from 1961-2022. The data is further broken into three periods, namely: 1961-1980, 1981-2000 and 2001- 2022, to ease comparison.

Modelling Growth Rates: The log-linear model is generally used to estimate growth rates, the regressand takes the logarithm form and the regressor is a time variable which can take values from one to infinity (Akpaeti, et al., 2013; Akpaeti, Basse, & Okon, 2014b; Sharma et al., 2017; Akpaeti, et al., 2018a; Godara & Krishan 2020).

The log-linear model generally takes the mathematical form:

$$\ln y_{t(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8)} = b_0 + b_1 t + e_t \quad (1)$$

Where $\ln Y_{t1}$ = Natural logarithm of Onion production measured in tonnes

Where $\ln Y_{t2}$ = Natural logarithm of Onion yield measured in kg per hectare

Where $\ln Y_{t3}$ = Natural logarithm of Onion area harvested measured in hectare

Where $\ln Y_{t4}$ = Natural logarithm of Onion export measured in tonnes

Where $\ln Y_{t5}$ = Natural logarithm of Onion export value measured in \$

Where $\ln Y_{t6}$ = Natural logarithm of Onion import measured in tonnes

Where $\ln Y_{t7}$ = Natural logarithm of Onion import value measured in \$

Where $\ln Y_{t8}$ = Natural logarithm of Onion consumption measured in tonnes

b_0 = estimated constant regression line

b_1 = estimated growth coefficient

t = linear time trend for each period

e_t = error term

Compound Growth Rate: Compound growth rate is a nonlinear measure, in other words, the effect of compounding takes into account variability or volatility that has occurred over time (Jagannath et al., 2013; (Akpaeti, et al., 2014a; Akpaeti, et al., 2018b; Akpaeti, et al., 2019; Antia-Obong & Otung, 2019)., the compound growth rate is expressed as follows:

$$CGR = (\text{antilog } b_1 - 1) * 100 \quad (2)$$

Otherwise expressed as:

$$CGR = (e^{b_1} - 1) * 100 \quad (3)$$

Where;

CGR = Compound Growth rate of coconut.

b_1 = estimated growth coefficient or slope.

e = Euler's exponential constant, given a value of 2.71828

Doubling Time. To estimate doubling time, the rule of 72 (Moneychimp, 2019; Antia-Obong et al. 2019) is applied and is used for annual periodic compounded data using a constant of 8 per cent at a periodically determined compounded rate derived as follows:

$$2P = P(1 + r)^Y \quad (4)$$

$$Y = \ln(2) / \ln(1 + r/100) \quad (5)$$

To approximate to obtain a fraction,

$$Y = K/r \quad (6)$$

Where K is a number that enables approximation of a good fit for r,

$$\ln(2)/\ln(1 + r/100) = K/r \quad (7)$$

$$\ln(2)/\ln(1+0.08) = K/0.08 \quad (8)$$

$$K = [\ln(2)/\ln(1.08)] * 0.08 \quad (9)$$

$$K = 0.721 \quad (10)$$

$$K = 0.721 * 100 \quad (11)$$

$$Y = 72/r \quad (12)$$

Where;

Y = Time to double growth

r = Compound growth rate as in equation (3)

Contribution of Area and Yield to the Growth of Onion Production across Different Regions in Africa. Decomposition analysis is used to capture the contribution of area and yield to onion production growth, which measures the relative contribution of area and yield to the total change in production (Antia-Obong, Eno, & Obot, 2024; Ikuemonisan et al., 2020; Antia-Obong & Bhattarai, 2012). The equation is expressed thus;

$$P = \frac{(A_{by} * \Delta Y)}{\Delta P} * 100 + \frac{(Y_{by} * \Delta A)}{\Delta P} * 100 + \frac{(\Delta A * \Delta Y)}{\Delta P} * 100 \quad (13)$$

(yield effect) (area effect) (Interaction effect)

Where;

P = Production growth

ΔP (Change in Production) = (P_{cy} – P_{by})

ΔY (Change in yield) = (Y_{cy} - Y_{by})

ΔA (Change in area) = A_{cy} – A_{by}

A_{by}, Y_{by} and P_{by} are the base year for area, yield and production of onions.

A_{cy}, Y_{cy} and P_{cy} are the current years for area, yield and production of onions.

Accordingly, the area effect, yield effect and interaction effect share percentage contribution towards production growth with each source contributing different percentage levels to production growth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ANALYZE THE GROWTH RATES IN ONION PRODUCTION, CONSUMPTION AND TRADE ACROSS THE DIFFERENT REGIONS OF AFRICA. Table 1 presents the growth rates in area, yield and production of onions for Africa and captures the five African regions. All five regions including Africa experienced significant positive growth rates at the 1% level for the four periods concerning area except for West Africa which experienced growth in area at the 5% level of significance. The results mean that the area under onion cultivation had been increasing across Africa and the regions. Similar studies on

growth rates such as (Antia-Obong, et al., 2024; Akpan, et al., 2025) also found that area of coconut and oil palm fruit experienced increased growth.

For yield, East Africa and Middle Africa experienced significant positive growth at the 1% level during the second, third and pooled periods. However, Middle Africa experienced significant negative growth in yield at the 1% level during the first period; while North Africa on the other hand experienced significant negative growth in yield at the 5% level during the second period. Southern Africa experienced significant positive growth in yield across all the periods except the second period.

The growth rate in yield for the first period in West Africa was positive and significant at the 10% level; on the contrary, yield in the second and pooled periods experienced significant negative growth at the 1% level. Africa reveals a dismal yield growth rate with the only significant positive growth occurring during the third period; while the other periods experienced negative growth. An interesting finding is that growth rates in onion production experienced significant positive growth at the 1% level across all periods.

Table 2 classifies growth rates in the regions into low, medium and high corresponding to <2%, 2% to 3% and >3% respectively. Accordingly, in the first period, high and medium growth rates in the area occurred in all the regions with East Africa, Middle Africa, West Africa and Africa experiencing high growth rates. Furthermore, all regions experienced low growth in yield; while high and medium growth also occurred in all regions concerning production with East Africa, Middle Africa, Southern Africa and West Africa experiencing high growth.

Table 1: Compound growth rate for area, yield and production of onion (%)

Regions	Period I (1961-1980)			Period II (1981-2000)			Period III (2001-2022)			Pooled period (1961-2022)		
	A	Y	P	A	Y	P	A	Y	P	A	Y	P
EA	5.23* **	-0.4	4.81* **	4.5** *	1.11* **	5.65* **	3.87* **	2.22* **	6.18* **	4.29* **	1.31* **	5.65* **
MA	12.41 ***	- 4.5** *	7.47* **	1.41* **	2.12* **	3.56* **	5.87* **	1.21* *	7.14* **	4.29* **	1.11* **	5.34* **
NA	2.84* **	-0.6	2.22* **	3.36* **	-0.4**	2.84* **	3.87* **	1.61* **	5.44* **	3.46* **	0.9** *	4.5** *
SA	2.53* **	1.61* **	4.29* **	4.71* **	0.2	4.92* **	3.46* **	1.01* **	4.39* **	3.15* **	1.11* **	4.29* **
WA	4.71* **	0.9*	5.65* **	31.65 ***	- 13.32 ***	14.11 ***	1.71* *	4.29* **	6.08* **	12.19 ***	- 3.44* **	8.33* **
AF	4.08* **	-1.09	2.94* **	10.63 ***	- 4.97* **	5.13* **	2.63* **	2.94* **	5.65* **	5.76* **	- 0.6** *	5.13* **

*** indicates a 1% level of significance, ** indicates a 5% level of significance, * indicates a 10% level of significance

EA= East Africa, MA= Middle Africa, NA= North Africa, SA= Southern Africa, WA= West Africa, AF= Africa

A= area, Y= yield and P= Production

During the second period, only Middle Africa experienced low growth while the other regions all experienced high growth rates concerning the area. The reverse occurred for yield, in this case; Middle Africa experienced medium growth; while the other regions all experienced low growth rates. Furthermore, a high growth rate was experienced in all the regions except for North Africa which experienced medium growth in production.

The third period witnessed a high growth rate in the area in East Africa, Middle Africa, North Africa and Southern Africa; while low and medium growth rates in the area were experienced in West Africa and Africa respectively.

Yield on the other hand witnessed low and medium growth rates across the regions; on the contrary, production experienced high growth rates across all regions.

Table 2: Classification of regions based on growth rates of Onions

Periods	Elements	Low (<2%)	Medium (2% to 3%)	High (>3%)
Period I (1961-1980) 20 years	Area		NA, SA	EA, MA, WA, AF
	Yield	EA, MA, NA, SA, WA, AF		
	Production		NA, AF	EA, MA, SA, WA
Period II (1981-2000) 20 years	Area	MA		EA, NA, SA, WA, AF
	Yield	EA, NA, SA, WA, AF	MA	
	Production		NA	EA, MA, SA, WA, AF
Period III (2001-2022) 22 years	Area	WA	AF	EA, MA, NA, SA
	Yield	MA, NA, SA	EA, WA, AF	
	Production			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA, AF
Pooled (1961-2022) 62 years	Area			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF
	Yield	EA, MA, NA, SA, WA, AF		
	Production			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF

EA= East Africa, MA= Middle Africa, NA= North Africa, SA= Southern Africa, WA= West Africa, AF= Africa

The pooled period provided an interesting finding, because area and production in all the regions experienced a high growth rate; while yield on the other hand experienced a low growth rate in all the regions. On the other hand, growth rates occurred at the extremes i.e. either low growth rate or high growth rate.

Table 3 presents the growth rates in onion consumption, the most striking finding was that all regions in the four periods witnessed positive and significant growth rates at the 1% level. This finding is consistent with Yeshiwas, Alemayehu, & Adgo (2023) wherein onion was acknowledged as increasingly being consumed in Africa.

Table 3: Compound growth rate for domestic consumption of onions (%)

Regions	Period I (1961-1980)	Period II (1981-2000)	Period III (2001-2022)	Pooled period (1961-2022)
	Consumption	Consumption	Consumption	Consumption
EA	4.08***	5.55***	6.93***	5.55***
MA	5.34***	4.71***	9.75***	6.29***
NA	3.25***	2.22***	6.18***	4.81***
SA	5.13***	5.02***	3.67***	4.29***
WA	1.92***	3.98***	6.18***	4.07***
AF	3.05***	3.46***	6.18***	4.6***

***indicate 1% level of significance

EA= East Africa, MA= Middle Africa, NA= North Africa, SA= Southern Africa, WA= West Africa, AF= Africa

Table 4 shows the classification of growth rate in onion consumption, during the first period, only West Africa witnessed low consumption growth; while the other regions experienced high consumption growth rates.

In the second period, only North Africa witnessed medium consumption growth, while the other regions experienced high consumption growth.

The third and pooled periods all experienced high consumption growth which further confirms that onion consumption increased across Africa.

Table 4: Classification of regions based on consumption growth rates of Onions

Periods	Element	Low (<2%)	Medium (2% to 3%)	High (>3%)
Period I (1961-1980) 20 years	Consumption	WA		EA, MA, NA, SA, AF
Period II (1981-2000) 20 years	Consumption		NA	EA, MA, SA, WA, AF
Period III (2001-2022) 22 years	Consumption			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF
Pooled (1961-2022) 62 years	Consumption			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF

EA= East Africa, MA= Middle Africa, NA= North Africa, SA= Southern Africa, WA= West Africa, AF= Africa

Table 5 shows the growth rate in the export and import of onions, while export and import generally experienced significant negative growth at the 1% level during the first period the remaining periods experienced significant positive growth at the 1% level. This negative trade growth rate implies that onion exports and imports mostly declined during the first period, while the positive trade growth rate suggests that onion exports and imports increased after the first period.

Table 5: Compound growth rate for export and import quantities of onions (%)

Region s	Period I (1961-1980)		Period II (1981-2000)		Period III (2001-2022)		Pooled period (1961-2022)	
	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import	Export	Import
EA	-10.95***	-8.7***	7.04***	9.42***	10.08***	14.45***	5.76***	6.18***
MA	6.29	-2.54***	6.5	3.25**	31.39***	7.68***	4.19***	5.44***
NA	-7.6***	-24.87***	13.66***	11.4	5.34***	18.18***	3.25***	3.05
SA	-2.57*	29.05***	7.68***	18.18***	10.41***	5.02***	4.5***	14.68** *
WA	6.18**	2.33***	6.61*	4.81***	3.56***	7.79***	7.47***	6.72***
AF	-6.67***	-1.88***	11.18***	5.65***	5.87***	8.98***	3.67***	6.18***

EA= East Africa, MA= Middle Africa, NA= North Africa, SA= Southern Africa, WA= West Africa, AF= Africa
*** indicates a 1% level of significance, ** indicates a 5% level of significance, * indicates a 10% level of significance

Table 6 shows the classification of growth rates into low, medium and high. The most obvious finding to emerge from the classification is that export and import for the second, third and pooled periods all experienced high growth rates.

Table 6: Classification of regions based on growth rate of export and import quantities of Onions

Periods	Elements	Low (<2%)	Medium (2% to 3%)	High (>3%)
Period I (1961-1980) 20 years	Export quantity	EA, NA, SA, AF		MA, WA
	Import quantity	EA, MA, NA, AF	WA	SA
Period II (1981-2000) 20 years	Export quantity			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF
	Import quantity			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF
Period III (2001-2022) 22 years	Export quantity			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF
	Import quantity			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF
Pooled (1961-2022) 62 years	Export quantity			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF
	Import quantity			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF

EA= East Africa, MA= Middle Africa, NA= North Africa, SA= Southern Africa, WA= West Africa, AF= Africa

Table 7 shows the growth rate in the value of exports and imports measured in United States dollars. What can be seen is that import value in the first period was the only period with a significant negative growth rate at the 1% level for North Africa. In other words, the value of imports and exports was generally positive and significant at the 1% level during the other periods.

Table 7: Compound growth rate for export and import value of Onions (%)

Region	Period I (1961-1980)		Period II (1981-2000)		Period III (2001-2022)		Pooled period (1961-2022)	
	Export (\$)	Import (\$)	Export (\$)	Import (\$)	Export (\$)	Import (\$)	Export (\$)	Import (\$)
EA	-2.27	-0.99	5.65***	8.11***	9.97***	14.22***	6.5***	7.68***
MA	7.25	5.34***	0.9	1.21	34.31***	8.55***	5.13***	6.93***
NA	0	-	6.18***	10.08	13.31***	19.96***	5.13***	4.39***
SA	5.13***	16.05*** 29.3***	7.14***	17.7***	11.85***	6.93***	6.29***	15.37** *
WA	19.72***	8.33***	8.98*	4.08***	4.19**	10.08***	9.42***	7.47***
AF	1.41	5.13***	7.9***	4.29***	11.07***	10.63***	5.65***	7.25***

*** indicates a 1% level of significance, ** indicates a 5% level of significance, * indicates a 10% level of significance

EA= East Africa, MA= Middle Africa, NA= North Africa, SA= Southern Africa, WA= West Africa, AF= Africa

Table 8 shows that the export and import value of onions tilted towards a pattern of high growth rate during the third and pooled periods. Accordingly, the low growth rates witnessed in export and import value for East Africa, North Africa and Africa during the first period and Middle Africa during the second period transitioned to high growth rates during the third period. In other words, the value of onion trade increased over time implying that the international price of onions has over time experienced high growth which suggests that onion supply has not met with rising demand in Africa.

Table 8: Classification of regions based on the value of growth rate of export and import of Onions

Periods	Elements	Low (<2%)	Medium (2% to 3%)	High (>3%)
Period I (1961-1980) 20 years	Export value	EA, NA, AF		MA, SA, WA
	Import value	EA, NA		MA, SA, WA, AF
Period II (1981-2000) 20 years	Export value	MA		EA, NA, SA, WA, AF
	Import value	MA		EA, NA, SA, WA, AF
Period III (2001-2022) 22 years	Export value			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF
	Import value			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF
Pooled (1961-2022) 62 years	Export value			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF
	Import value			EA, MA, NA, SA, WA,AF

EA= East Africa, MA= Middle Africa, NA= North Africa, SA= Southern Africa, WA= West Africa, AF= Africa
Estimate the doubling time in onion production, consumption and trade across different regions of Africa. Table 9 shows the doubling time in years for area, yield, production, consumption, export, import, export value and import value of onions in Africa.

Table 9: Doubling time in years for Area, yield, production, consumption, export quantity, import quantity,

Pooled period (1961-2022)								
Regions	Area	Yield	Production	Consumption	Export	Import	Export Value	Import Value
EA	17	55	13	13	13	12	11	9
MA	17	65	13	11	17	13	14	10
NA	21	80	16	15	22	24	14	16
SA	23	65	17	17	16	5	11	5
WA	6	-21	9	18	10	11	8	10
AF	13	-120	14	16	20	12	13	10

export value and import value of Onions in Africa

EA= East Africa, MA= Middle Africa, NA= North Africa, SA= Southern Africa, WA= West Africa, AF= Africa

The results show that for the area, Southern Africa experienced the highest doubling time of 23 years, while West Africa witnessed the lowest with 6 years. This means that it will take 23 years for the area harvested under Southern Africa to double in size from the current size; while it will take just 6 years for the area to double in West Africa from the current size.

Concerning yield, the finding shows that it will take 21 years for onion yield to fall to half its current level. The opposite of doubling time is half-life and is referred to as negative doubling, which implies that West Africa had the shortest doubling time, furthermore, it will take Africa 120 years for onion yield to fall to half its current level. This finding is disturbing because the implication is that it will take 240 years for onion yield to double from current levels and it shows that onion yield in Africa is lacking in modern yield technology that can rapidly increase yields and shorten its doubling time.

For production, West Africa experienced the lowest doubling time of 9 years while Middle Africa witnessed the least doubling time of 11 years to consumption. Furthermore, North Africa experienced the highest doubling time for export and import as well as export and import values.

Evaluate the contribution of area and yield to the growth of onion production across different regions in Africa. Table 10 shows the sources of production growth, a cursory look reveals that area effect was the main

source of production growth across all periods. This means that expansion in area under onion cultivation was the main reason behind onion production across the regions in Africa. Akpan, Udoh, & Edet (2025) also found that area expansion was the main source of production growth for oil palm fruit in Nigeria. Furthermore, West Africa had the shortest doubling time of 10 years for export and export value, while Southern Africa experienced the shortest doubling time of 5 years for import and import value.

Table 10: Contribution of area and yield to Onion Production growth across Africa

Region	Period I				Period II				Period III				Pooled period			
	(1961-1980)				(1981-2000)				(2001-2022)				(1961-2022)			
	YE%	AE%	IE%	Total %	YE%	AE%	IE%	Total %	YE%	AE%	IE%	Total %	YE%	AE%	IE%	Total %
EA	13.31	72.41	14.28	100	12.62	71.77	15.62	100	17.59	56.14	26.27	100	4.74	41.56	53.81	100
MA	-16.17	191.1	-74.94	100	60.6	21.85	17.55	100	4.89	85.19	9.92	100	0.32	91.07	8.6	100
NA	27.07	62.08	10.86	100	-12.69	126.48	-13.79	100	19.99	51.43	28.58	100	7.1	51.2	41.7	100
SA	30.1	51.75	17.87	100	-7.4	117.64	-10.24	100	28.04	54.76	17.2	100	6.59	56.87	36.87	100
WA	11.11	74	14.89	100	-19.99	946.16	-826.17	100	29.51	40.2	30.3	100	-1.12	339.69	-238.57	100
AF	8.337	85.57	6.11	100	-35.7	267.61	-131.91	100	24.44	46.47	29.09	100	-0.42	107.87	-7.45	100

EA= East Africa, MA= Middle Africa, NA= North Africa, SA= Southern Africa, WA= West Africa, AF= Africa
YE = Yield effect, AE= Area effect, IE= Interaction effect

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are drawn from the findings of the study:

1. There is a need to invest in modern scientific technology to boost onion yields on the African continent, particularly in West Africa. This approach is likely to reverse the negative growth rate in yields and shorten the time required for yields to double.

2. There is a need to invest in the land, to improve on land productivity and management, and to slow down on land expansion for onion production. This will involve adopting good agricultural practices such as intercropping, to maximize land use as a finite resource.

3. Adequate training and capacity development are required for stakeholders in the African onion value chain on best agronomic practices and climate-smart techniques that can boost yields.

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THEORETICAL DISCUSSION ON LANDSCAPE CHANGE – ATTRIBUTES, PROCESSES, STAKEHOLDERS AND DRIVERS TOWARD SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Landscape change is a dynamic and multifaceted phenomenon driven by complex interactions among socio-economic, environmental, and policy-related factors. This article explores the theoretical underpinnings of landscape change, focusing on the drivers, processes, and implications of these transformations. Drawing on insights from the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and other frameworks, the discussion highlights the interplay between direct and indirect drivers, stakeholders, and policy mechanisms. It synthesizes findings from key reports, scientific literature, and case studies to provide a comprehensive understanding of the processes shaping landscapes in diverse contexts. The article concludes with a critical evaluation of strategies to manage and guide landscape changes towards sustainability.

KEY WORDS: Landscape change, Theoretical discussion, Attributes, Sustainability.

ABSTRAKT

Der Landschaftswandel ist ein dynamisches und vielschichtiges Phänomen, das durch komplexe Wechselwirkungen zwischen sozioökonomischen, ökologischen und politischen Faktoren bedingt ist. Dieser Artikel untersucht die theoretischen Grundlagen des Landschaftswandels und konzentriert sich auf die Triebkräfte, Prozesse und Auswirkungen dieser Veränderungen. Auf der Grundlage von Erkenntnissen aus der Gemeinsamen Europäischen Agrarpolitik (GAP) und anderen Rahmenwerken wird das Zusammenspiel zwischen direkten und indirekten Triebkräften, Interessengruppen und politischen Mechanismen beleuchtet. Er fasst Erkenntnisse aus wichtigen Berichten, wissenschaftlicher Literatur und Fallstudien zusammen, um ein umfassendes Verständnis der Prozesse zu vermitteln, die Landschaften in unterschiedlichen Kontexten prägen. Der Artikel schließt mit einer kritischen Bewertung von Strategien zur Steuerung und Lenkung von Landschaftsveränderungen in Richtung Nachhaltigkeit.

STICHWORTE: Landschaftswandel, theoretische Diskussion, Attribute, Nachhaltigkeit.

RÉSUMÉ

La modification des paysages est un phénomène dynamique et multiforme qui résulte d'interactions complexes entre des facteurs socio-économiques, environnementaux et politiques. Cet article explore les fondements théoriques de la modification des paysages, en se concentrant sur les moteurs, les processus et les implications de ces transformations. S'inspirant de la politique agricole commune européenne (PAC) et d'autres cadres, la discussion met en évidence l'interaction entre les moteurs directs et indirects, les parties prenantes et les mécanismes politiques. Elle synthétise les résultats des principaux rapports, de la littérature scientifique et des études de cas afin de fournir une

compréhension globale des processus qui façonnent les paysages dans divers contextes. L'article se termine par une évaluation critique des stratégies de gestion et d'orientation des changements paysagers vers la durabilité.

MOTS CLÉS: changement de paysage, discussion théorique, attributs, durabilité.

INTRODUCTION

Landscapes are evolving entities shaped by human activities and natural processes. They reflect cultural heritage, ecological functions, and socio-economic dynamics. However, landscapes face increasing pressures from urbanization, agricultural intensification, climate change, and socio-political transformations. Understanding the drivers and processes of landscape change is crucial for managing these changes sustainably and maintaining the ecosystem services landscapes provide. This article investigates the theoretical and empirical dimensions of landscape change, emphasizing the roles of drivers, actors, and policy mechanisms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A critical review of existing literature reveals the multidimensional nature of landscape change, characterized by a rich interplay between ecological, socio-economic, and political factors. Early studies primarily focused on the ecological consequences of landscape transformations, such as biodiversity loss and habitat fragmentation (Jongman, 2002). However, more recent work has expanded to include socio-economic dimensions, highlighting the role of global trade, urbanization, and agricultural policies in shaping land-use patterns (Klijn, 2004; Haines-Young & Potschin, 2010). The literature also emphasizes the significance of cultural landscapes as a repository of historical and social values, stressing the need for policies that integrate conservation with economic development (Cooper et al., 2009). Despite these advances, gaps remain in understanding the long-term cumulative impacts of policy interventions, particularly in regions experiencing rapid socio-economic transitions. This review underscores the importance of interdisciplinary approaches to address these challenges effectively.

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The intersection of natural and human-induced factors makes landscape changes a multidimensional challenge. Scholars emphasize that landscapes function as "living archives," recording interactions between human culture and the environment over centuries (Klijn, 2004). Addressing this challenge requires an integrated perspective that considers both historical legacies and future aspirations for sustainable land use. This article not only examines the factors driving changes but also evaluates interventions aimed at preserving landscape integrity.

1. DRIVERS OF LANDSCAPE CHANGE

Drivers of landscape change are categorized into direct and indirect influences that operate across various scales, from global to local. These drivers interact in complex ways, influencing landscape structure, composition, and function.

Global Drivers. Global drivers include commodity market fluctuations, energy prices, and climate change. Rising commodity prices incentivize agricultural intensification, altering landscape composition and reducing biodiversity (Klijn, 2004). Conversely, low commodity prices may lead to land abandonment, especially in less productive regions. Climate change exacerbates these dynamics by affecting crop suitability, water availability, and extreme weather events, as observed in Mediterranean regions prone to drought (Herzon & Helenius, 2008).

Beyond these immediate factors, global economic interconnectivity influences landscape decisions, such as the expansion of biofuel crops driven by international energy markets. The demand for renewable energy sources, while environmentally beneficial, can disrupt traditional landscapes by converting mixed-use areas into monocultural plantations (Stoate et al., 2001). Moreover, global trade policies impact agricultural exports and imports, altering local land-use priorities.

The role of international institutions, including the United Nations and the World Bank, in shaping global land use should not be underestimated. Their policies, coupled with development aid programs, influence how landscapes are managed, particularly in developing countries. Case studies from Sub-Saharan Africa reveal the double-edged nature of these policies, which can simultaneously promote sustainable practices and exacerbate resource exploitation.

Continental and Regional Drivers. At the continental level, European Union directives, such as the Habitats Directive and Water Framework Directive, influence landscape management. The CAP plays a pivotal role, driving agricultural intensification, extensification, or abandonment through subsidies and market interventions (Brouwer & Lowe, 2000; Stoate et al., 2001); (Alieva, 2022). Regional economic development, infrastructure expansion, and urbanization further shape landscapes by fragmenting habitats and altering land-use patterns (Jongman, 2002).

The CAP's two-pillar structure—direct payments under Pillar I and rural development programs under Pillar II—creates a dual influence on landscapes. Pillar I often supports large-scale production, while Pillar II incentivizes conservation-friendly practices. This dichotomy has led to uneven impacts, with some regions experiencing significant biodiversity loss due to intensified farming, while others benefit from reforestation and ecological restoration projects (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2010); (Radev et al, 2019); (Alieva, 2022);

Regional disparities in policy implementation add another layer of complexity. For instance, northern European countries prioritize rewilding initiatives, while southern regions focus on preserving traditional farming systems. Understanding these disparities is essential for developing tailored policy interventions.

Local Drivers. Local drivers include farm-level management practices, technological adoption, and socio-cultural factors. Farm size, crop rotation, irrigation systems, and fertilization levels directly influence landscape heterogeneity and ecosystem services (Tschardt et al., 2005). Social perceptions of landscape value, demand for regional products, and tourism also act as local drivers, encouraging landscape diversification (Lowe et al., 2002); (Nikolov et al., 2012).

Technological advancements, such as precision agriculture, are transforming local landscapes. These technologies optimize resource use but may also exacerbate landscape homogenization. For example, automated machinery favors larger, uninterrupted fields, reducing habitat connectivity.

Conversely, smallholder farms adopting traditional methods often maintain diverse landscapes that support biodiversity.

The role of local governance and community-based organizations cannot be ignored. These entities often mediate between farmers and policymakers, ensuring that local voices are heard. Involving local actors in decision-making processes can increase policy acceptance and effectiveness.

2. ATTRIBUTES OF LANDSCAPE CHANGE

Landscape change encompasses a variety of attributes that reflect its complex and multidimensional nature. These attributes include spatial heterogeneity, temporal dynamics, cultural significance, and ecological resilience. Spatial heterogeneity refers to the variation in landscape features, such as land cover and vegetation, which influence biodiversity and ecosystem functioning (Tschardt et al., 2005); (Nikolov et al, 2013). Temporal dynamics highlight the changes that occur over time, driven by both natural processes and human activities (Klijn, 2004). Cultural significance is another critical attribute, as landscapes often embody historical and social values, serving as markers of identity and heritage (Cooper et al., 2009). Finally, ecological resilience measures the ability of landscapes to absorb disturbances and maintain functionality, which is particularly relevant in the context of climate change and anthropogenic pressures (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2010). Understanding these attributes is essential for designing effective management strategies that balance ecological, economic, and cultural objectives

3. PROCESSES OF LANDSCAPE CHANGE

Landscape change manifests through five primary processes: land abandonment, intensification, intensification, diversification, and urbanization. Each process has distinct implications for landscape structure and ecosystem services.

Land Abandonment. Land abandonment occurs in marginal areas where agricultural practices are economically unviable. This process often leads to ecological succession, increasing biodiversity in some cases but also causing the loss of cultural landscapes (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2010).

Abandoned lands can become hotspots for invasive species, altering native biodiversity. In Eastern Europe, for example, land abandonment following economic transitions led to shifts in vegetation dynamics, with implications for both conservation and agricultural policies (Herzon & Helenius, 2008). Policies aimed at rewilding or re-cultivating such areas must consider socio-economic and ecological trade-offs.

Agricultural Intensification. Intensification involves increased inputs such as fertilizers and machinery, resulting in larger fields and simplified landscapes. While it enhances productivity, it often reduces biodiversity and ecosystem resilience (Tschardt et al., 2005).

In highly productive regions, intensification has also led to soil degradation and water resource depletion. Balancing productivity with environmental sustainability requires the integration of agroecological principles, such as intercropping and integrated pest management, into modern farming practices (Stoate et al., 2001).

Extensification and Diversification. Extensification reduces agricultural inputs, promoting semi-natural habitats and landscape heterogeneity. Diversification, including agro-tourism and organic farming, enhances landscape multifunctionality, addressing both economic and ecological goals (Cooper et al., 2009).

Diversification also aligns with growing consumer demand for sustainable products. Organic farming and agri-tourism attract premium markets and generate rural employment, creating economic incentives to preserve traditional landscapes. Case studies from the Mediterranean illustrate how diversified farming systems can mitigate climate change impacts while supporting local economies (Klijn, 2004).

Urbanization and Infrastructure Development. Urban expansion and infrastructure projects fragment landscapes and disrupt ecological networks. These changes are often irreversible, emphasizing the need for sustainable urban planning (Jongman, 2002).

Infrastructure development often prioritizes economic growth over ecological considerations, leading to conflicts between stakeholders. Strategic environmental assessments (SEAs) and participatory planning frameworks can help mediate these conflicts by integrating diverse perspectives into decision-making processes (Herzon & Helenius, 2008).

Urban sprawl presents additional challenges, such as increased greenhouse gas emissions and loss of arable land. Compact city models and green infrastructure planning are emerging as viable solutions to mitigate these impacts.

4. POLICY MECHANISMS AND LANDSCAPE MANAGEMENT.

Policy frameworks significantly influence landscape change, with the CAP being a critical example. This section discusses the mechanisms through which policies shape landscapes, focusing on regulatory, economic, and informational instruments.

Regulatory Instruments. Regulations, such as spatial planning and environmental impact assessments, guide land use and resource management. The EU's Natura 2000 network illustrates the use of zoning to protect ecologically valuable landscapes (Herzon & Helenius, 2008).

Beyond traditional zoning, adaptive governance frameworks are emerging as tools to address the complexities of landscape management. These frameworks prioritize flexibility and stakeholder collaboration, enabling policies to adapt to socio-ecological changes (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2010).

Economic Instruments. Subsidies and payments for ecosystem services (PES) incentivize sustainable practices. Agri-environmental schemes under the CAP exemplify this approach, rewarding farmers for biodiversity-friendly practices (Stoate et al., 2001).

Market-based instruments, such as carbon credits, are increasingly relevant for landscape management. By monetizing ecosystem services, these instruments encourage private investments in conservation and restoration projects (Klijn, 2004).

Informational Instruments. Knowledge transfer and capacity-building initiatives enhance policy uptake. Advisory services, training programs, and participatory approaches foster awareness and collaboration among stakeholders (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2010).

Digital platforms and decision-support tools are transforming how information is disseminated. These technologies enable real-time monitoring of landscape changes and facilitate data-driven decision-making, bridging the gap between research and practice.

5. STAKEHOLDERS OF LANDSCAPE CHANGE

The multiplicity of actors involved in landscape change reflects the complexity of its drivers and processes. These actors include policymakers, farmers, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and local communities.

Policymakers. National and EU-level policymakers design and implement regulatory and economic instruments. Their decisions shape the incentives and constraints influencing landscape management (Brouwer & Lowe, 2000).

Policymakers must navigate competing interests and limited resources. Integrating landscape considerations into broader policy agendas, such as climate action and rural development, can enhance policy coherence and effectiveness (Lowe et al., 2002).

Farmers and Land Managers

Farmers are central actors in implementing landscape management practices. Their decisions are shaped by economic viability, policy incentives, and personal values (Cooper et al., 2009).

Capacity-building programs that empower farmers with sustainable management skills can increase policy uptake. Additionally, recognizing farmers as custodians of cultural heritage can foster a sense of stewardship, encouraging long-term commitments to landscape preservation.

6. NGOs and Civil Society

NGOs advocate for biodiversity conservation and sustainable practices. They often mediate between policymakers and local communities, ensuring stakeholder engagement (Stoate et al., 2001).

Civil society organizations play a crucial role in monitoring policy impacts and holding decision-makers accountable. Collaborative platforms that integrate NGO expertise into policy design can enhance governance transparency and inclusivity.

Local Communities. Local communities contribute to landscape valorization through cultural practices, tourism, and grassroots initiatives. Their involvement is crucial for the long-term sustainability of landscape policies (Herzon & Helenius, 2008).

Community-led conservation initiatives, such as heritage trails and eco-villages, demonstrate the potential of bottom-up approaches. These initiatives not only preserve landscapes but also foster social cohesion and local identity.

SYNTHESIS AND RECOMMENDATIONS. Effective management of landscape change requires an integrated approach that balances ecological, economic, and social objectives. Key recommendations include:

- **Policy Coherence:** Align agricultural, environmental, and spatial planning policies to address conflicting objectives.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Foster participatory decision-making to incorporate diverse perspectives.
- **Adaptive Management:** Develop flexible policies that can respond to changing socio-ecological conditions.
- **Research and Monitoring:** Invest in long-term studies to evaluate policy impacts and guide future interventions.
- **Innovative Financing:** Explore market-based instruments, such as PES and carbon credits, to attract private investments in landscape conservation.
- **Education and Awareness:** Promote environmental education to cultivate a culture of sustainability.

CONCLUSION

Landscape change is a multidimensional phenomenon influenced by a web of interacting drivers and processes. By understanding these dynamics, policymakers and stakeholders can develop strategies to manage landscapes sustainably. The insights provided in this article contribute to a deeper theoretical understanding and practical framework for addressing the challenges of landscape change.

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OPPORTUNITIES FOR AGRICULTURAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP THROUGH THE SHARING ECONOMY: A FOCUS ON FOOD REUSE

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural entrepreneurship encompasses activities related to the production, processing, and distribution of agricultural products, demanding innovation and adaptability to changing market and environmental conditions. This sector faces challenges such as climate change and market fluctuations but also leverages advanced technologies to improve operations. Integrating agricultural entrepreneurship with the sharing economy presents new opportunities for sustainability by promoting resource reuse and waste reduction. While the sharing economy lacks a singular definition, it broadly refers to the reutilization of underutilized assets and resources. Sharing economy models include on-demand resource access, automated marketplaces, and on-demand services. In rural areas, this approach may involve the shared use of homes, land, and tools, yielding economic, social, and environmental benefits. In waste management, trust and gratitude have been cultivated as social constructs. Research indicates that the sharing economy enhances productivity, reduces costs, and optimizes resource use, offering numerous advantages compared to its drawbacks, particularly in tourism and waste management. This study aims to explore developmental opportunities for agricultural entrepreneurship through the application of sharing economy principles, with a specific focus on food reuse.

KEYWORDS: sharing economy, agricultural entrepreneurship

ABSTRAKT

Landwirtschaftliches Unternehmertum umfasst Tätigkeiten im Zusammenhang mit der Erzeugung, der Verarbeitung und dem Vertrieb von landwirtschaftlichen Erzeugnissen und erfordert Innovation und Anpassungsfähigkeit an sich ändernde Markt- und Umweltbedingungen. Dieser Sektor ist mit Herausforderungen wie dem Klimawandel und Marktschwankungen konfrontiert, nutzt aber auch fortschrittliche Technologien zur Verbesserung der Abläufe. Die Integration des landwirtschaftlichen Unternehmertums in die Sharing Economy eröffnet neue Möglichkeiten der Nachhaltigkeit durch die Förderung der Wiederverwendung von Ressourcen und der Abfallverringerung. Für die Sharing Economy gibt es zwar keine eindeutige Definition, aber sie bezieht sich im Großen und Ganzen auf die Wiederverwendung von nicht ausgelasteten Anlagen und Ressourcen. Zu den Modellen der Sharing Economy gehören der Zugang zu Ressourcen auf Abruf, automatisierte Marktplätze und Dienstleistungen auf Abruf. In ländlichen Gebieten kann dieser Ansatz die gemeinsame Nutzung von Häusern, Land und Werkzeugen beinhalten, was wirtschaftliche, soziale und ökologische Vorteile mit sich bringt. In der Abfallwirtschaft wurden Vertrauen und Dankbarkeit als soziale Konstrukte kultiviert. Die Forschung zeigt, dass die Sharing Economy die Produktivität steigert, die Kosten senkt und die Ressourcennutzung optimiert, was im Vergleich zu ihren Nachteilen zahlreiche Vorteile bietet, insbesondere im Tourismus und in der Abfallwirtschaft. Diese Studie zielt darauf ab, Entwicklungsmöglichkeiten für

landwirtschaftliches Unternehmertum durch die Anwendung von Prinzipien der Sharing Economy zu erforschen, mit einem besonderen Fokus auf die Wiederverwendung von Lebensmitteln.

STICHWORTE: Sharing Economy, landwirtschaftliches Unternehmertum

RÉSUMÉ

L'entrepreneuriat agricole englobe les activités liées à la production, à la transformation et à la distribution des produits agricoles, ce qui exige de l'innovation et une capacité d'adaptation à l'évolution des conditions du marché et de l'environnement. Ce secteur est confronté à des défis tels que le changement climatique et les fluctuations du marché, mais il tire également parti des technologies de pointe pour améliorer les opérations. L'intégration de l'entrepreneuriat agricole à l'économie de partage offre de nouvelles possibilités de durabilité en favorisant la réutilisation des ressources et la réduction des déchets. Bien qu'il n'existe pas de définition unique de l'économie de partage, celle-ci se réfère de manière générale à la réutilisation d'actifs et de ressources sous-utilisés. Les modèles de l'économie du partage comprennent l'accès aux ressources à la demande, les places de marché automatisées et les services à la demande. Dans les zones rurales, cette approche peut impliquer l'utilisation partagée de maisons, de terres et d'outils, ce qui génère des avantages économiques, sociaux et environnementaux. Dans le domaine de la gestion des déchets, la confiance et la gratitude ont été cultivées en tant que concepts sociaux. La recherche indique que l'économie de partage améliore la productivité, réduit les coûts et optimise l'utilisation des ressources, offrant de nombreux avantages par rapport à ses inconvénients, en particulier dans le tourisme et la gestion des déchets. Cette étude vise à explorer les possibilités de développement de l'entrepreneuriat agricole par l'application des principes de l'économie de partage, en mettant l'accent sur la réutilisation des aliments.

MOTS-CLÉS: économie de partage, entrepreneuriat agricole

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural entrepreneurship encompasses a wide range of activities related to the production, processing, and distribution of agricultural products. This form of entrepreneurship demands innovation, efficient resource management, and the ability to adapt to changes in market and environmental conditions. Agricultural entrepreneurs face challenges such as climate change, price fluctuations in markets, and the need for sustainable practices. However, they also have opportunities to leverage advanced technologies to improve their business operations.

The sharing economy is interpreted differently by various researchers. Codagnone and Martens (2016) note that there is no common consensus on the specific activities that constitute the sharing economy. Görög (2018) acknowledges the existence of many definitions of the sharing economy, which largely share a similar meaning, and asserts that the essence of the sharing economy lies in the reuse of underutilized assets.

Connecting agricultural entrepreneurship with the sharing economy opens up new opportunities for sustainability and development in agriculture. The sharing economy promotes resource reuse, reduces waste, and optimizes the use of available resources—essential elements for sustainable agricultural entrepreneurship. The development of micro-entrepreneurship through direct interaction between users results in the disintermediation of traditional activities without altering ownership (Basselier et al., 2018).

Digitalization and the growth of eco-citizenship further support this model. According to recent studies, the sharing economy is becoming increasingly significant. Its widespread adoption, relatively low costs, and the application of the internet alongside other digital technologies have profoundly transformed people's lives, resulting in the most direct economic impact—sharing (Tunca, 2019). Beyond the boundaries of local communities, the internet and other digital technologies have facilitated and simplified sharing among strangers.

One of the prominent features of modern online sharing economy platforms is the establishment of trust. Including both sides of the market has been a key challenge, yet it has led to significant success (Codagnone and Martens, 2016).

This study focuses on the reuse of food and sustainable agricultural entrepreneurship. The aim is to identify development opportunities for agricultural entrepreneurship through the application of sharing economy principles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The Sharing Economy in Tourism Development in Rural and Agricultural Areas

The sharing economy is highly prevalent in the field of tourism services, particularly significant for rural and agricultural areas. Based on the concept of the sharing economy, rural residents in China have creatively developed a working model called the Shared Farm. On one hand, rural residents share their homes, agricultural land, tools, and even their free time and talents through a third-party online platform. On the other hand, citizens of large cities, weary of demanding urban life and longing for idyllic lifestyles, gain access to these rural resources without acquiring ownership rights (Jung and Xin, 2018).

Through in-depth research and analysis of the sharing economy's application in tourism, Zhang (2024) observes that the sharing economy has brought significant changes and opportunities to tourism. This model offers tourists a more practical and cost-effective travel experience by rationally utilizing unused resources, reducing travel costs, and providing diverse services. However, it also comes with challenges such as regulatory issues, safety concerns, and inconsistent service quality. Addressing these challenges requires joint efforts and collaboration among governments, businesses, and tourists. Looking ahead, the application of the sharing economy in tourism is expected to trend towards smarter, more standardized, and cross-border integration. With continuous advancements in science and technology and gradual improvements in laws and policies, the sharing economy is believed to foster new vitality for sustainable tourism development.

According to Sudarić et al. (2019), the motivation for developing tourism products should begin with a rural impulse as the driver for activities across different segments of rural tourism. These include active (adrenaline-based), passive (performances, birdwatching), experiential (wellness, gastronomy), adventure (exploration), creative (photography, art workshops, dancing), and intellectual (learning foreign/ancient languages and scripts, traditional customs workshops such as cooking, pottery, and handicrafts). The authors argue that additional elements of creative diversification lie in differentiating tourism products based on biodiversity, tradition, culture, and customs—everything that highlights the advantages of the local rural area.

Research by Rodrigues et al. (2021) reveals that various practices of the sharing economy in agri-food production aim to increase productivity, reduce costs, access previously unavailable technologies,

optimize resources and labor, and create economic, social, and ecological benefits for the community. An example of the sharing economy within rural tourism and agricultural areas is the exchange of cohabitation in Africa (Kumar, 2018).

In addition to the described scientific literature and examples, an analysis of the factors driving the sharing economy follows. Research by Basselier et al. (2018) demonstrates that the sharing economy provides a quick and cost-effective way to match supply and demand for goods and services. The primary innovation in the sharing economy's business model lies in technological platforms and mobile applications, which connect supply and demand and organize them in ways that were not previously possible. Spatial distance is no longer a barrier, as the use of the internet facilitates transactions by linking those offering resources or services with those seeking to use them.

2. The Sharing Economy in Food Waste Management

This subsection addresses the highly relevant issue of food waste management. Saginova et al. (2021) compare best international practices and identify the main models of food sharing: monetary exchange, free transfer (charity), and food sharing within a neighboring community. The study explains the challenges and unresolved issues of food sharing, such as the lack of information about available food-sharing options, low consumer trust in the quality of shared food, and the perception of using charitable food supplies as something shameful. Directions for the development of food-sharing practices based on existing international experiences are also presented.

Graph 1 Food waste estimations in EU,2022 (million tones of fresh Mass)

Note: Data are estimated.

Source: Eurostat (online data code: env_wasfw)

eurostat

According to the research by Moltene and Orsato (2021), social impact and hedonistic motivation do not appear to be significant factors when it comes to adopting and using food-sharing platforms. The

case study analysis identified two new constructs—trust and gratitude—and introduced a new relationship between perceived effort and user behavior.

The *Guide for Reducing Food Waste in Food Production and Processing* (2021) offers two key terms related to food waste management: **food loss** and **food waste**.

- **Food loss** refers to the reduction in the quantity or quality of food, usually resulting from decisions made by food suppliers, excluding retailers, caterers, institutional kitchens, and consumers.
- **Food waste** refers to the reduction in the quantity or quality of food caused by the actions or decisions of retailers, caterers, institutional kitchens, and consumers.

There are various reasons for food waste, ranging from human factors and equipment malfunctions to poor operational procedures.

Graph 1 highlights that the largest share of food waste in the EU originates from households. In 2021, the second year following the COVID-19 pandemic, approximately 131 kilograms of food waste per capita were generated in the EU. Households accounted for 54% of this food waste, equating to 70 kilograms per capita. The remaining 46% originated from the food supply chain.

Food waste in households was nearly double the amount generated by the sectors of primary production and the manufacturing of food and beverages (11 kilograms and 28 kilograms per capita, representing 9% and 21%, respectively). These sectors have strategies to reduce food waste, such as using discarded parts as by-products. Restaurants and food services generated 12 kilograms of food waste per person (9%), while retail and other food distribution sectors produced the smallest share, at 9 kilograms per capita (7%).

This chapter utilizes a categorization approach to highlight various enterprises in the field of agrarian entrepreneurship that simultaneously promote the sharing economy. For example, companies like **Too Good to Go** and the **Karma** app are compared in this context.

Furthermore, in developing agrarian entrepreneurship within the sharing economy, consideration should be given to methods of food sharing or ensuring that agriculture provides only what is needed. At the EU level, there are companies addressing food waste as part of the sharing economy framework.

The company **Too Good To Go** started in Denmark when a group of founders observed significant food waste at a buffet restaurant. Shocked by the wastefulness of the industry, they created a platform to address the issue. Together with a French initiative, they expanded into today's global platform. The CEO joined in 2016 and led the company's growth to 17 markets. The mission of the company is to reduce food waste by connecting supply and demand, offering education, and developing a socially impactful enterprise with a vision for a waste-free planet.

An example from Sweden highlights another food waste solution through the **Karma** app. The app was founded by Elsa Bernadotte, Hjalmar Ståhlberg Nordegren, Ludvig Berling, and Mattis Larsson (*Karma, 2023*). It connects consumers with surplus food from restaurants and grocery stores at discounted prices, thereby reducing food waste.

The initial concept for Karma was a loyalty app for small businesses and their customers. However, through collaboration with restaurants, the founders identified a common problem of food waste. The app offers a commercial "win-win" solution to an environmental issue, as the founders advocate for addressing global climate challenges through technology.

3. The Sharing Economy in Agricultural Advisory Services

The sharing economy in agricultural advisory services represents an innovative approach that can significantly impact the efficiency and sustainability of agricultural practices. This concept is based on the idea of shared use of resources, services, and knowledge among farmers, advisors, organizations, and consumers.

In an article by Hilmi (2023), the idea of **agricultural mechanization hire service enterprises (AMHSE)** was examined, highlighting its low relevance to the sharing economy. The study included examples from several countries, such as India, Ghana, Nepal, Kenya, and others. Most findings fell within the low relevance range of 20% to 39%. Notably, only two cases—China (moderate relevance) and India (high relevance)—stood out among the nine analyzed, with India demonstrating particularly strong integration of AMHSE into the sharing economy framework.

Based on the analysis, key insights into agricultural mechanization services within the sharing economy were identified. The dominant trend indicates low relevance for AMHSE in the sharing economy, with percentages ranging from 20% to 39%. A smaller trend reflects moderate relevance, between 40% and 59%, while India is the sole example of high relevance (60% to 79%). The research found India's approach noteworthy due to its emphasis on community engagement, fostering partnerships, and focusing on socio-economic models, distinguishing it from other countries.

Hilmi (2023) emphasized the importance of digital platforms linked to AMHSE, which show potential contributions to the sharing economy. However, their overall impact remains limited, as evidenced by only 13% of registrations for mechanized services via mobile phones in Sub-Saharan Africa. Additionally, positive environmental and climate impacts were identified, but the role of AMHSE in the context of the sharing economy lacks sufficient research. Thus, the study suggests further exploration and better implementation of sharing economy practices in developing countries.

From the findings, there is a clear trend of low relevance in most analyzed countries, with exceptional cases like India showcasing potential for effective integration. The study calls for additional research on the application of the sharing economy in developing countries and highlights the need for innovative approaches to enhance AMHSE's contributions to sustainable economic practices.

Davidson and Infranca (2016) argue that many sharing economy initiatives provide specific solutions to the frustrations of urban living. For instance, urban residents can avoid purchasing cars, thus bypassing parking challenges, car maintenance, or renting vehicles with drivers.

In agricultural entrepreneurship, the sharing economy helps address issues like raw material shortages. Beyond altruistic motives, financial aspects undeniably play a pivotal role in this type of economy. According to an ING study (2015), a significant proportion (48%) of EU respondents cited earning or saving money as their main reason for participating in the sharing economy (Basselier et al., 2018).

Furthermore, research by Čirić et al. (2021) revealed that 38% of respondents considered money as a payment medium an essential motivation for engaging in the sharing economy. Additionally, 51.85% believed that earning extra income was an important motive. Protecting the environment ranked third, with 42.59% of respondents agreeing on its importance as a motivation in the sharing economy.

AGRIVI provides an innovative digital solution for food production traceability, allowing food and retail companies to transparently track the lifecycle of their products. This technology, utilizing QR codes

to provide detailed product information, helps companies position their premium-quality food products in line with food safety standards.

Increased urbanization has also contributed to the growth of the sharing economy, which offers tailored solutions to urban challenges. City dwellers can avoid the costs and issues associated with car ownership, while in the agricultural sector, the sharing economy can address raw material shortages.

Financial aspects are a key motivation for participants in the sharing economy. Research shows a significant share of participants engage in this economy due to opportunities for earning or saving money. Environmental protection is also recognized as a motive, albeit to a lesser extent.

4. Entrepreneurial Initiatives and Social Innovations in Agriculture of Rural Areas

Rural areas face many challenges, including demographic changes, limited access to resources, and increasing demands for sustainable development. In this context, entrepreneurial initiatives and social innovations become key tools for revitalizing rural communities, especially when linked to the concept of the sharing economy. Entrepreneurial initiatives in rural areas often rely on innovative approaches involving new technologies, sustainable practices, and collaboration among local farmers. Through the sharing economy, small farmers can share resources such as equipment, land, and market channels, thereby reducing costs and increasing productivity. This business model enables farmers to improve their operations without significant initial investments, which is particularly important for entrepreneurs who often face limited financial resources.

Research by Krišić et al. (2018) showed differences in entrepreneurial attitudes between men and women, focusing on demographic variables such as age and education. Women often face additional challenges, including traditional social norms and family responsibilities, which may limit their participation in entrepreneurship.

A comparative analysis of good practice examples in the Republic of Croatia (Deže et al. 2024; Deže et al. 2023) established that various social innovations linked to the sharing economy contribute to the sustainable development of rural areas through three pillars of sustainability: social, ecological, and economic. In the continental region of Croatia, ecological contributions are the most prominent, at 56.25%, followed by economic contributions at 53.33%, and social contributions at 47.37%. In the Adriatic region, social and socio-cultural contributions dominate, accounting for 52.63%, followed by economic contributions at 46.67%, and ecological at 43.75%. In the continental region, the most significant contributions are ecological, including ecological producers, product sales, and the construction of facilities for processing ecological products. When compared with the Adriatic region, the development perspectives of sustainability are found in social contributions, namely activating the knowledge and experience of the local population and training for participatory management of local sustainable development. Recognizing examples of good practice and identifying the types of contributions to sustainable development enables better economic and socio-cultural rural development.

Similar initiatives have been seen in other countries, such as Spain, Italy, and Greece. For instance, in Spain, rural areas have benefitted from innovative collaborative farming models where resources such as equipment and knowledge are shared among small-scale farmers, enhancing sustainability and productivity (Pérez et al., 2020). In Italy, the rise of social farming initiatives, where communities and local organizations work together in agricultural production, has had a significant positive impact on rural revitalization (Capone et al., 2018). Greece has also embraced cooperative agricultural models to

empower farmers and enhance economic resilience, particularly in the context of the shared economy, improving the financial and social wellbeing of rural communities (Tsioumanis et al., 2020).

However, the sharing economy can provide solutions through collaborative models that make resources and markets more accessible to women. For example, through joint farms or cooperatives, women can collaborate and share resources, thereby increasing their economic power and contributing to their local communities.

Social innovations in agriculture often involve new approaches that promote community sustainable development and social cohesion. Connecting these innovations with the sharing economy can significantly improve the sustainability of rural areas. For instance, sharing land or infrastructure for energy production (solar panels) can reduce the ecological footprint and encourage sustainable practices that are critical for the long-term sustainability of agricultural production. Adopting sustainable agricultural technologies, such as irrigation systems and solar energy, allows farmers to reduce costs and become more competitive while minimizing negative environmental impacts. These examples show how the sharing economy and social innovations can significantly contribute to the creation of sustainable and inclusive rural enterprises.

Entrepreneurial initiatives and social innovations connected to the sharing economy offer sustainable development models that can transform rural areas. Through collaboration and resource sharing, farmers can increase competitiveness, reduce costs, and ensure farm sustainability. Special attention should be paid to promoting gender equality, empowering women to start businesses, and ensuring that all members of society have equal opportunities to participate in economic activities. The combination of entrepreneurial initiatives, social innovations, and the sharing economy creates a framework for sustainable and inclusive development of rural communities, ensuring their long-term resilience and prosperity.

CONCLUSION

It has been established that there are many definitions related to the sharing economy, and there is no common consensus on which activities constitute the sharing economy. Essentially, the sharing economy is the reuse of underutilized assets and resources. Food reuse is a current global issue. The research findings indicate that there are three business models of the sharing economy. These are: the access-based business model, the market-based business model, and the on-demand service provider model. The access-based business model in the sharing economy only occurs when the consumer needs it. The market-based business model operates through an automation process. The third model includes communication channels for services as basic tools. In this model, there are two categories of participants: those who offer services and those who seek services.

The sharing economy is recognized in economic activities such as tourism and agriculture, where the creative design of the sharing economy in rural areas has been identified, for example, in China, where residents shared their homes, land, and tools with citizens from urban areas. This has proven to be a positive trend of change for people from both rural and urban areas. The research identified numerous benefits of the sharing economy: increased productivity, cost reduction, access to technologies that were previously unavailable, optimization of resources and labor, and the creation of economic, social, and environmental benefits for the community.

The sharing economy significantly contributes to waste management, and two new social constructs have developed through the sharing economy in the food waste management process: trust and gratitude.

All the research findings suggest that the sharing economy not only offers solutions to rural challenges but also contributes to sustainable rural development and agricultural growth by promoting transparency and quality in food production. Understanding the different motivations that drive participants to apply the sharing economy contributes to a more effective definition of developmental goals in local, regional, and national strategies. Motivation encourages individuals to undertake entrepreneurial initiatives in the application of the sharing economy, which is a crucial factor for economic, ecological, and socio-cultural progress in rural areas, particularly those where agriculture is the dominant economic activity.

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DESIGNING ECONOMICALLY SUSTAINABLE FAMILY FARMS: INTEGRATING CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND PERMACULTURE FOR RESILIENT AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

Sustainability was first defined by Hans Carl von Carlowitz, and it is understood as the ability to meet our current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The process of sustainable development involves the interaction of biological, social, and economic systems, aiming to maximize their goals, which include, among others, genetic diversity, fulfilling basic human needs, and cultural diversity. The concept of a circular economy supports sustainable development, as it is based on designing systems, elements, processes, products, and services in such a way that waste, which is currently a major ecological and social problem, does not exist. This economic development, which emphasizes the preservation of natural resources (essential for human survival) rather than profit, represents the only viable future perspective that does not appear apocalyptic. Sustainable family farms are often based on permaculture principles. This primarily means avoiding chemical and mineral additives, as well as heavy machinery, but also requires designing systems that create multiple functional links between various elements within the farm, as well as between the farm and natural energy flows. The paper describes the main prerequisites that a family farm must meet in order to be considered sustainable, as well as ways to organize similar farms into cooperatives and eco-villages based on cooperative principles.

KEYWORDS: design, circular economy, family farms, sustainable development, permaculture, agricultural incentives, self-sufficiency, cooperatives

ABSTRAKT

Nachhaltigkeit wurde erstmals von Hans Carl von Carlowitz definiert und wird als die Fähigkeit verstanden, unsere gegenwärtigen Bedürfnisse zu befriedigen, ohne die Fähigkeit künftiger Generationen zu gefährden, ihre eigenen Bedürfnisse zu befriedigen. Der Prozess der nachhaltigen Entwicklung umfasst die Interaktion biologischer, sozialer und wirtschaftlicher Systeme, die darauf abzielen, ihre Ziele zu maximieren, zu denen u. a. die genetische Vielfalt, die Befriedigung menschlicher Grundbedürfnisse und die kulturelle Vielfalt gehören. Das Konzept der Kreislaufwirtschaft unterstützt die nachhaltige Entwicklung, da es darauf beruht, Systeme, Elemente, Prozesse, Produkte und Dienstleistungen so zu gestalten, dass Abfälle, die derzeit ein großes ökologisches und soziales Problem darstellen, nicht entstehen. Diese wirtschaftliche Entwicklung, bei der die Erhaltung der natürlichen Ressourcen (die für das Überleben der Menschheit unabdingbar sind) im Vordergrund steht und nicht der Profit, stellt die einzige realisierbare Zukunftsperspektive dar, die nicht apokalyptisch erscheint.

Nachhaltige Familienbetriebe basieren häufig auf den Prinzipien der Permakultur. Dies bedeutet in erster Linie den Verzicht auf chemische und mineralische Zusatzstoffe sowie auf schwere Maschinen, erfordert aber auch die Gestaltung von Systemen, die vielfältige funktionale Verbindungen zwischen den verschiedenen Elementen des Betriebs sowie zwischen dem Betrieb und den natürlichen Energieströmen schaffen.

STICHWORTE: Design, Kreislaufwirtschaft, Familienbetriebe, nachhaltige Entwicklung, Permakultur, landwirtschaftliche Anreize, Selbstversorgung, Genossenschaften

RÉSUMÉ

La durabilité a été définie pour la première fois par Hans Carl von Carlowitz et est comprise comme la capacité de répondre à nos besoins actuels sans compromettre la capacité des générations futures à répondre à leurs propres besoins. Le processus de développement durable implique l'interaction de systèmes biologiques, sociaux et économiques visant à maximiser leurs objectifs, qui incluent notamment la diversité génétique, la satisfaction des besoins humains fondamentaux et la diversité culturelle. Le concept d'économie circulaire soutient le développement durable, car il repose sur la conception de systèmes, d'éléments, de processus, de produits et de services qui permettent d'éviter la production de déchets, qui constituent actuellement un problème environnemental et social majeur. Ce développement économique, qui met l'accent sur la préservation des ressources naturelles (indispensables à la survie de l'humanité) et non sur le profit, représente la seule perspective d'avenir réalisable qui ne semble pas apocalyptique.

MOTS-CLÉS: design, économie circulaire, agriculture familiale, développement durable, permaculture, incitations agricoles, autosuffisance, coopératives

INTRODUCTION

Family farms are increasingly recognized as significant drivers of agricultural development as well as rural communities. In recent years, there has been a noticeable trend of population migration, primarily from rural to urban areas, and even beyond national borders in search of better economic opportunities, often referred to as "seeking bread." However, few consider how we might produce that figurative bread—and the literal one—ourselves. Recently, the phenomenon of rural depopulation has been a focus of concern, with increasing attention on potential revitalization strategies for these areas. Among the most promising solutions is the concept of the circular economy, which essentially aligns with sustainable development. In addition to these direct economic reasons, particularly for small countries, there are numerous ecological and social factors that support the transformation of rural areas into sustainability hubs. This paper addresses the sustainability of family farms and their self-sufficiency, which manifests in financial, energy, and food independence. If more such farms operated in the same region, the possibility of collective organization arises, whether in cooperatives or eco-villages, enabling the division of labor related to specific goods, especially those suitable for trade. The existence of such communities, as well as the involvement of a single family within them, enhances the well-being of both individual family farms and the community as a whole. These communities already exist in various parts of the world, and it is increasingly likely that, over time, they will evolve into economic systems based on moral, ethical, and

spiritual principles, not only in interpersonal relationships but also in our connection with nature and the world around us.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The Concept of Sustainability

Sustainability has emerged as one of the most critical concepts in addressing the global challenges we face today. Originating from environmental concerns, it has since evolved into a multidimensional concept that incorporates economic, social, and environmental dimensions. The concept of sustainability can be understood as the ability to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Brundtland Commission, 1987). This definition, presented by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED), emphasizes the importance of balancing the needs of current and future generations in the context of limited resources and environmental impacts. In this essay, we explore the evolution of the concept of sustainability, its three pillars, and its applications in contemporary global practices.

The roots of sustainability can be traced back to concerns over natural resource depletion and environmental degradation. In the mid-20th century, environmental movements and scholarly work began to highlight the negative consequences of industrialization, urbanization, and overconsumption. The 1972 Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment marked the first significant global meeting to address environmental issues on a worldwide scale, setting the stage for the development of international environmental policies and agreements.

However, the modern concept of sustainability was formalized with the 1987 publication of the Our Common Future report, also known as the Brundtland Report. The report introduced the idea of "sustainable development" as a framework for balancing economic growth with environmental conservation and social equity. Over the following decades, the concept of sustainability continued to evolve and expand, influencing a wide range of policy, academic discourse, and practical initiatives. Today, sustainability is often framed through the lens of the "three pillars" model, which seeks to balance environmental, economic, and social factors.

Environmental Sustainability Environmental sustainability is the foundation of the sustainability concept and focuses on the preservation of the natural environment for future generations. It involves practices that reduce environmental degradation and ensure the health of ecosystems, air, water, and soil. The key principles of environmental sustainability include the conservation of biodiversity, the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, the sustainable use of resources, and the protection of natural habitats.

Economic Sustainability Economic sustainability focuses on promoting long-term economic growth that benefits society as a whole without depleting natural resources or exacerbating inequality. It emphasizes the need for economic systems to function within ecological limits while ensuring that wealth creation is inclusive, equitable, and supportive of human well-being.

Social Sustainability Social sustainability refers to the capacity of societies to maintain and improve the well-being of individuals and communities over time. It focuses on the importance of social equity, human rights, cultural diversity, and the provision of basic needs such as education, healthcare, and affordable housing.

A key aspect of social sustainability is addressing social inequality and ensuring that all individuals, regardless of their socio-economic background, have access to opportunities that promote well-being. According to the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2020), social sustainability is integral to achieving broader development goals, such as ending poverty (SDG 1) and achieving gender equality (SDG 5). Social sustainability also emphasizes the importance of human capital development, community resilience, and social cohesion.

In recent decades, sustainability has become a central theme in international policy and governance. The United Nations' SDGs, adopted in 2015, provide a comprehensive framework for addressing sustainability at a global level. The 17 SDGs, ranging from eradicating poverty to ensuring sustainable consumption and production patterns, provide a blueprint for countries, organizations, and individuals to work towards a more sustainable and equitable future (United Nations, 2015).

In addition to the SDGs, the Paris Agreement on climate change, adopted in 2015, marked a significant step in global efforts to combat climate change. The agreement aims to limit global temperature rise to well below 2°C, with efforts to keep it below 1.5°C. It also highlights the importance of global cooperation in addressing environmental sustainability and provides a mechanism for countries to contribute to global efforts to reduce emissions.

At the regional and national levels, governments are increasingly adopting sustainability policies and integrating sustainability principles into their economic and development strategies. For example, the European Union (EU) has adopted the European Green Deal, which aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. This ambitious plan includes measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, promote renewable energy, and promote sustainable agriculture.

Despite the growing recognition of the importance of sustainability, there are several challenges to its widespread adoption. One of the primary obstacles is the trade-off between economic growth and environmental protection. Many developing economies face pressure to prioritize industrialization and economic growth, often at the expense of environmental sustainability. Furthermore, the complexity of balancing the three pillars of sustainability—economic, social, and environmental—often leads to competing priorities and conflicting policy goals.

Another challenge is the need for technological innovation and infrastructure development to support sustainability. Transitioning to renewable energy, improving waste management systems, and creating sustainable agricultural practices require significant investments in technology and infrastructure, which may be challenging for some regions or sectors to implement.

Lastly, there is a need for greater public awareness and education on sustainability issues. While there is growing support for sustainable practices, many individuals and businesses remain unaware of the importance of adopting sustainable lifestyles or are resistant to change due to perceived costs or inconvenience.

2. Circular Economy as the Backbone of Sustainable Development

In order to explain the circular economy, it is necessary to first explain the linear economy in which we currently live. The linear economy represents the current approach aligned with neoliberal capitalism, which implies uncontrolled and excessive exploitation of natural resources, as well as the use of these resources through all economic processes from production to disposal after use. Upon completion of the use of goods within the linear economy, the most common outcome is a residual in the form of waste,

such as packaging or worn-out goods like old furniture, electrical devices, and similar items. One of the main assumptions of the linear economy is that resources are abundant and accessible, and that they can be easily extracted and cheaply disposed of in the environment (Drljača, 2015:19). In the search for new solutions to stimulate economic growth, the fact that there are significant limitations to material resources, as well as the increasing demand for environmental protection that can no longer be ignored, is being increasingly acknowledged.

In 1973, Fritz E. Schumacher in his book *Small is Beautiful; Economics as if People Mattered* stated that the idea of unlimited economic growth (more and more, until people are saturated with wealth) should be seriously reconsidered. He also argued that people must make a significant shift in their perception of well-being and development. Larger and larger machines, which require an increasing concentration of economic power and exert more violence against the environment, do not represent development but are a rejection of wisdom. He explains that true wisdom can only be found within the individual, which allows them to see the emptiness and inherent dissatisfaction of a life dedicated primarily to the pursuit of material wealth (Schumacher, 1973:18). The search for alternatives to the neoliberal economic system requires a faster abandonment of the linear economy concept, and this process can be called a kind of transition. This transition, understood in general as the process of improving the economy, represents the abandonment of the linear economy concept. Unfortunately, until the last major economic crisis of 2008, as well as more recent environmental crises and climate changes, no refuge was found in any new system. Only then did the new concept of the circular economy begin to emerge more clearly, which demands a completely different view of the entire economic system: from the extraction of raw materials, through usage, to disposal, or recycling after use (Drljača, 2015). Sustainable development, environmental quality, and economic development have now become compatible activities (Črnjar, 2002:187).

According to Drljača (2015), the key assumption in the transformation from a linear to a circular economy is feedback, whereby collected and recycled waste re-enters the production cycle as valuable raw material. A simple example of the circular economy, with which everyone is already familiar, is the use of glass, which, after use, is collected and used as raw material for the production of other glass items. The circular economy can and must be implemented on both the macroeconomic and microeconomic levels, but also in the behavior of each individual in their role on the demand side, as well as in the role of consumers of goods who ultimately dispose of waste. The circular economy, as such, cannot exist if any element fails; the circle is broken. It refers to an industry that is renewable, which aims to use renewable energy sources, minimizes, records, and eliminates toxic chemicals, and eradicates waste through thoughtful design (Ellen-MacArthur Foundation, 2013:22).

The design of goods so far has been in the spirit of "from cradle to grave," meaning that resources are extracted from nature, then shaped into some product, sold, and eventually end up in some "graveyard," most often at a landfill or incineration site. Many products are even designed to be used only for a certain period of time, and soon become so obsolete that they need to be replaced by new versions, as is the case in the mobile phone industry. Less than 5% of the total raw materials are used for the product and its delivery to the consumer; the rest is consumed in the production process and lost. Another feature of the linear economy is the design of products that should be suitable for everyone and anyone, the so-called "one-size-fits-all" model. Since consumption conditions are not the same everywhere, producers

design products for the "worst-case scenario," meaning that they will conceive the product to function equally efficiently regardless of external circumstances, which also guarantees the largest possible consumer base. To achieve this, manufacturers often resort to increased use of toxic and harmful chemicals, such as those used in cleaning products or for protection against external conditions in agricultural activities (McDonough, Braungart, 2009:28-30).

In contrast to the "from cradle to grave" concept, which is characteristic of the linear economy, the consultants from McDonough Braungart Design Chemistry have developed the concept of "from cradle to cradle," which encourages innovations in production with the goal of reducing costs and minimizing risks (especially ecological ones), in order to achieve beneficial effects for both the company and the environment. This concept is fully in line with the circular economy, with the intention of eliminating non-recyclable waste, using clean energy sources, and preserving drinking water.

Today's circular economy system has not yet fully reached the "cradle to cradle" stage, as it is based on recycling certain materials, with the quality of the materials decreasing during the recycling process. To recycle certain materials, such as plastic, significant amounts of softeners and other highly toxic and dangerous chemical and mineral additives need to be added to partially restore the properties of the original material. However, this still results in a lower-value material compared to the original (known as downcycling). In addition to the lost value and material, the environmental impact is significant. During downcycling, it is possible, and often the case, that contamination of nature increases through the release of contaminated wastewater, burning, and the release of toxic gases into the air, almost through everything that results as a by-product of these actions. Another example of downcycling is clothing made from recycled plastic bottles. In addition to the energy inefficiency during processing, fibers from plastic bottles contain toxins that are harmful to health and were never intended to be in contact with human skin.

The Stockholm Environment Institute conducted research on the energy consumption and ecological footprint of various types of fabrics. They compared the production of fabrics made from natural materials like hemp and cotton with fabrics made from recycled plastic, i.e., polyester. Despite considering the energy used in growing agricultural crops for fabric production, the energy needed to produce polyester is more than three times higher than the energy required to grow and process certain natural fibers into fabrics (Cherrett et al., 2005). Similar results are also evident in the table above.

Since downcycling is not a feature of the circular economy, it is important to better define the true meaning of recycling. Here, it is necessary to mention the concept of "cradle to cradle," which advocates for the full value of materials even after recycling. Design is crucial in this concept, as the product is based on thoughtful design. Braungart and McDonough, who created this concept, propose a new approach to design. Instead of improving the existing destructive framework, individuals and companies could create:

- Buildings that, like trees, produce more energy than they consume and purify their wastewater;
- Factories that produce clean wastewater.

Products that, when their lifecycle ends, do not become useless waste but can naturally break down in and on the ground, becoming food for plants and animals and nutrients for the soil; alternatively, they can be returned to the production cycle as a resource for producing high-quality materials for new

products. A flow of materials worth billions of dollars for the benefit of people and nature each year. A transportation system that enhances the quality of life by delivering goods and services. A world full of abundance, not one full of limitations, pollution, and waste. (Braungart, McDonough, 2002:62)

The same authors provide an example of a real, existing cyclical concept, the "cradle to cradle" system, which is designed to perfection: nature. For instance, a cherry tree in the blooming phase creates many flowers and then fruits for reproduction. Although only a small number of seeds sprout and grow into a proper tree, this does not mean that the remaining flowers and fruits are useless. They fall to the ground, decompose, feed various organisms and microorganisms, animals, and plants, and ultimately enrich the soil with nutrients. Animals and humans exhale carbon dioxide, which plants absorb and use for their own growth. Nitrogen from organic waste is transformed into proteins through microorganisms, animals, and plants. Horses eat grass and produce manure, which provides shelter and food for insect larvae. The main nutrients of the Earth—carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, and nitrogen—cycle and recycle. In nature, growth means more trees, more species, greater diversity, more complex, adaptable, and resilient ecosystems. (Braungart, McDonough, 2002:72-73)

The essence of the circular economy is to design things—products, packaging, and systems—from the very beginning, with the understanding that waste does not exist. This means that valuable nutrients contained in materials shape and determine design: form follows evolution, not just function. According to the "cradle to cradle" concept, all materials are divided into two groups: biological and technological nutrients. Biological nutrients are materials or products designed to be returned to the biological cycle, while technological nutrients are those technological materials that return to the technological cycle. Substances returned to the biological cycle must not contain mutagens, carcinogens, resistant toxins, or other substances harmful to the biosystem, and similarly, technological nutrients must not contain biological substances, as this would result in the loss of biological materials while simultaneously contaminating the technological ones, thereby losing their qualitative properties and making it more difficult to reuse these contaminated technological nutrients. (Braungart, McDonough, 2002:102-104)

The circular economy introduces the idea of "product as a service." Products that contain valuable technological nutrients, such as cars, televisions, or furniture, would be perceived as services that people would want to enjoy. Consumers would pay for the service of using these products for a specific time period, for example, ten thousand hours of watching television, rather than for the television set itself. In this way, they would not pay for complex materials they would not use after the product's life cycle ends. When they are done with the product, or want a newer version, the manufacturer replaces the device, dismantles the old one to obtain the complex materials that can be used in the production of a new device. Consumers would receive the services they need and want for the period of use that suits them and could exchange them for new ones at will. Manufacturers would continue to grow and develop, while retaining ownership of their materials. Implementing such a system would have a threefold effect:

- No useless or potentially hazardous waste would be produced;
- Manufacturers would save billions on valuable materials over time.

As the nutrients of new products continuously circulate, the extraction of raw materials would decrease, as would the use of potentially harmful materials like PVC, and eventually, this would be completely halted. (Braungart, McDonough, 2002:109-112)

Today, there are materials that cannot be classified as either technological or biological nutrients, as they contain substances that are dangerous. Braungart and McDonough refer to them as "products without market value" (unmarketables), which are essential but for which there are no detoxification methods yet. For such materials, they require manufacturers to store them in safe repositories at their own expense until a detoxification method is found for their safe future use. The best example of such a material would be nuclear waste, for which it is clear that its storage poses a danger to all of humanity and could be considered a real nuclear bomb in case of mishandling. (Braungart, McDonough, 2002:116-117) Among the many ideas, perhaps one of the most promising is the breakdown of nuclear waste into smaller units. Radiation at low levels is not dangerous, and it exists everywhere: in humans and in the nature around us. The idea is to divide existing nuclear waste into smaller units and distribute them across family estates. If strictly viewed as waste, these smaller units could be safely disposed of within a balanced ecosystem at a depth of no less than 9 meters. (Megre, 2008:13) Balanced ecosystems, as well as some specific plants like hemp or sunflowers, have the ability to mitigate soil radioactivity, so this could be a safer storage method than existing ones. (Singh, Ward, 2004)

Sustainable development cannot be based on a uniform model, or as previously mentioned, the "one size fits all" model, since economic, ecological, and social systems are not the same around the world. Sustainability should be based on respecting diversity—both biological and sociocultural—and consequently the economic diversity that arises from sociocultural factors. In this sense, it is important to understand that sustainability is actually local: it needs to be connected with local energy flows and materials; it must be connected to local customs, needs, and tastes at all levels of action. Sustainability should consider what a product is made of, the environment in which it is made, how production processes affect other links in the value chain, how it is possible to create significant jobs, improve economic and physical health in that region, and how to increase biological and technological well-being for the future. (Braungart, McDonough, 2002:123) The connection to local natural flows of energy and materials is key to sustainable growth and development; however, this does not imply independence, as we define it today, as "separation from the existing energy system." On the contrary, sustainability implies interdependence with all ecological conditions that allow natural energy flows.

3. Circular Economy in the Function of Sustainability of Family Agricultural Households

It has already been explained how the essence of the circular economy is to design systems, including their elements, processes, products, and services, in a way that eliminates waste. It all begins with design, which is the first step in the circular process of creating and transforming such systems and everything that follows from them. To truly shine in its full glory, the circular economy must be implemented on a human scale. Interestingly, the concept of the circular economy has existed in human consciousness for thousands of years, but through centuries of promoting greed as a character trait, it has almost completely been lost. It is known that Native Americans used every part of the bison they hunted, not just for the meat. This means that their hunting method, and life in general, was in harmony with the circular economy: waste did not exist. Throughout history, we also find traces of civilizations that lived in harmony with their environment, though the development of civilization (and human awareness of themselves and their desires and needs) gradually lost that harmony.

In agriculture, the circular economy would be best illustrated through permaculture. According to one of the creators of the permaculture concept, it is not just an abbreviation for "permanent agriculture,"

but also a way of creating a balanced human environment. Permaculture deals with plants, animals, buildings, infrastructure, and their mutual relationships and how they integrate into the environment. The goal is to create ecological and economic systems that meet their own needs without exploiting or polluting the environment. Although based on ecological models, permaculture creates a cultivated ecology that is designed to produce more food for humans and animals than what can naturally be found in nature. (Mollison, Slay, 2001:9) Permaculture is, in fact, the result of observing nature, its processes, and the dynamics of individual elements. In nature, everything makes sense, there is no waste, no excess; energy and matter are in constant transformations and interactions. A vivid example would be a cherry tree, mentioned earlier in the context of the concept "cradle to cradle." The cherry tree, or any tree, in its lifetime produces many flowers and later fruits, with the goal of reproduction. Only a small portion of seeds germinate and grow into new trees, while the remaining flowers and fruits fall to the ground, decompose, and consequently enrich the soil with nutrients. These nutrients make the soil suitable for plant growth, and plants enrich the soil with nitrogen, using CO₂ from the air and energy from the sun, which is transformed into proteins through various (micro)organisms. Animals, through grazing, loosen the soil and make it more aerated, producing manure that provides food and shelter for insect larvae, which later help fertilize the same cherry tree.

A significant influence on David Holmgren and Bill Mollison, the founders of permaculture, was the Japanese philosopher and farmer Masanobu Fukuoka, who, with his book *The One-Straw Revolution*, introduced a revolution to the entire concept of agriculture and farming. He described "non-action" as investing minimal effort in soil and crop processing, significantly less than any other form of traditional agriculture, even less than ecological farming. The main idea Fukuoka advocated was that it is better to cooperate with nature than to fight against it, emphasizing that almost all processes used in traditional and modern agriculture are unnecessary and disrupt natural harmony, which is why the soil becomes dependent on them. He goes as far as to state in his book that civilization is generally structured so that "doctors become necessary when people create a sick environment." (Fukuoka, 1995:24)

Permaculture, like sustainable development in general, is interdisciplinary, meaning that it requires viewing problems from multiple, ideally all, perspectives. Fukuoka believes that one of the greatest causes of humanity's problems is precisely the narrow specialization, where causal relationships between elements of the system are not considered. An object viewed in isolation from the whole is not real. When specialists from different scientific fields observe a rice stalk, specialists in insect-induced diseases see only the damage caused by the insects, while plant nutrition specialists only see its vitality. (Fukuoka, 1995:31)

Fukuoka defined four basic principles of natural farming:

- Do not cultivate;
- Do not use chemical fertilizers or prepared compost;
- Do not destroy weeds by plowing or herbicides;
- Do not rely on chemicals.

These four fundamental principles were further developed by Holmgren and Mollison, who added principles related to human habitation in a particular space, and expressed permaculture in its basic form through twelve principles, which are explained below:

Observation and Participation. Design is key in the circular principle of permaculture because it connects all elements into a meaningful and cohesive whole. It depends on circumstances, and they need to be closely observed because there are often solutions that align with nature and cooperate with it, rather than trying to tame it.

Efficient Energy Planning. Efficient energy planning essentially represents planning an economical economy, meaning that no more inputs are invested than necessary to achieve the goals or desired output. Thus, in efficient energy planning, the key is the placement of system elements in appropriate zones. The goal of permaculture is not only recycling and increasing energy but also capturing, storing, and using everything before it breaks down into products of lower energy value, which is lost according to the second law of thermodynamics.

Achieving Yields. In the case of a family farm, yields are necessary to ensure basic existential conditions. This principle emphasizes the need to see the results of one's work, and through careful design, it is possible to achieve significant yields from the energy invested.

Applying Self-Regulation and Accepting Feedback. Self-regulation of a system is based on feedback, which is explained in the systems theory in the book *Business Domain Planning*. By observing nature, one can notice the pattern of self-regulation on a planetary level. If something is thrown out of balance, self-regulation mechanisms are activated. A good example of the practical operation of this principle is the plant version of the "internet" in forest systems. Through this, organisms communicate with each other, and if, for example, a tree is attacked by disease or pests, surrounding plants send help in the form of repellents or nutrients, depending on the needs of the damaged tree. Self-regulation also applies to human action, particularly harmful actions that must be noticed and changed to ensure the proper functioning of the system. Feedback is of particular importance because only in this way can deviations from the desired state be noticed, and changes can be introduced if necessary. It manifests through comparative and subsequent control, where comparative control is more expensive but more efficient in providing information that can be used in the decision-making and adjustment process. (Fučkan, Sabol, 2013:62-63)

Use and Value Renewable Resources. Using and valuing renewable resources is not exclusively related to energy but concerns the overall design of life opportunities. Wherever possible, and almost always, solutions should be designed that are renewable, do no long-term harm, and ideally have more than one function. One interesting example of the application of this principle, in addition to the classic examples of collecting rainwater or solar energy, would be planned goat grazing. Through carefully planned grazing, it is possible to transform barren land into fertile fields, clear overgrown land, implement fire prevention measures for open fires, and improve irrigation.

Do Not Create Waste. This principle obviously represents the concept of the circular economy, but in modern life, it is almost impossible to fully adhere to it. If we do not produce everything we need ourselves, which is impossible, in today's society we cannot completely avoid creating waste, no matter how hard we try. As explained earlier, today's recycling methods for many types of waste pose a greater environmental hazard than the original production of those materials, with plastic being a classic example. It is necessary, through system, process, product, and service design, to eliminate waste completely.

Designing from General to Specific. This principle refers to the patterns we can observe by looking at nature and then applying them to solve problems. These patterns represent the skeleton of the design, which is then filled with details adapted to the circumstances.

Connecting, not Sharing. Here, design is once again crucial. If we organize the system in a thoughtful and meaningful way, it is possible to achieve more than just the sum of individual elements; it is possible to create synergy among them. For example, in a biological system, the emphasis is on diversity. This diversity is not as much expressed in the number of elements, but in the number of functional connections between those elements, i.e., in the number of ways those elements (plants, animals, objects) can interact with each other.

Small and Slow Solutions. It is often believed that large systems are better, and that larger systems bring bigger and faster returns. In the short term, this thesis may hold true (though the question remains at what cost), however, in the long term, large systems are unsustainable, require large investments, and the possibilities for collapse, as well as the consequences if it happens, grow larger. Small systems are easier to control and maintain, and in smaller systems, local resources can be better utilized and outputs can be produced more efficiently.

Using and Valuing Diversity. In the biosphere, the diversity of species ensures a healthy and balanced ecosystem. Plants, with the help of neighboring species, are more resistant to diseases and pests, and are more vital than the same species growing in monoculture fields. If we look at social systems, we can take tribes as an example of this principle, where everyone performs specific activities according to their desires, abilities, and talents, while also considering the needs of the entire community.

Using and Valuing Marginal and Boundary Areas. Marginal and boundary areas are places where different worlds meet and mix. These boundary areas, such as riverbanks, border forests, or even the edges of fishponds in someone's backyard, are often the most productive places. The reason for this is the increased diversity, which creates many more functional connections among system elements than would exist in homogeneous systems.

Creative Responses to Change. Changes are constant and inevitable, but it is possible to influence them toward a desired outcome by carefully observing and then finding creative solutions. Creativity is what gives individual elements functional connections. These connections can be strengthened or branched out, as long as the circumstances are carefully observed and creativity is allowed to flourish. (Holmgren, 2002:34-35)

These twelve principles form the core of sustainable development, especially in the field of agriculture, and for a family farm aiming for self-sufficiency within a circular economy. In the process of designing a sustainable economy, it is important to view these principles as a whole, rather than individually, in order to create and maintain a balanced environment. The following will describe the prerequisites needed to create such a family farm.

CONCLUSION

Due to human egocentrism, believing that we have the right to subjugate the entire planet to our desires and power, humanity has brought itself to the brink of collapse. In recent decades, we have faced major climate catastrophes, increasing food shortages due to environmental pollution and soil degradation, as well as escalating hunger and poverty. Instead of traveling through space and discovering new worlds, we are primarily fighting against ourselves, and secondarily, with the legacy of our ancestors.

Humanity is slowly, but surely, discovering sustainable development, but it struggles to let go of unsustainable, yet deeply rooted worldviews. Only occasionally do a few brave individuals dare to work towards improving the world.

Family agricultural farms have the potential to change the world, starting from their immediate surroundings. Living in harmony with nature requires only the sacrifice of beliefs that do not support sustainability, but not the abandonment of a dignified life. Through work on their family farm, a family can achieve economic independence or self-sufficiency. Self-sufficiency does not mean complete disconnection from the existing system, but rather creating functional connections with it. Thus, a family farm can, and should, generate income and create added value, as this ensures financial security. A family can secure its financial stability by selling its primary and processed products, as well as by developing rural tourism and offering various educational workshops, which not only generate income for the family but also contribute to the prosperity of the entire community in which they reside. Agricultural farms can also join forces to increase their market power, thus achieving even greater income from the market.

In agricultural activities, permaculture represents a reflection of the circular economy, which is an integral part of sustainable development. The circular economy involves designing systems, elements, processes, products, and services in such a way that waste is completely eliminated. A key assumption in transforming a linear economy into a circular one involves feedback, where collected biological and technological materials are recycled into equivalent raw materials. In permaculture, there are no undesirable by-products. The product of each element in a sustainable family farm supports the functioning of one or more other elements in the system. Permaculture results from observing nature, its processes, and the dynamics of individual elements, and the system cooperates with nature and the environment to increase its efficiency.

Living in harmony with nature, rather than constantly fighting it and attempting to tame it, allows for significant energy savings through thoughtful design. For example, redesigning an existing residential building where a family lives on their farm can result in significant savings on heating, water, and hot water bills, as well as electricity if they decide to implement a system for generating electricity from renewable resources on-site (sun, water, thermal energy).

Many scientists agree that family farms will be the drivers of the economy in the near future. Research shows that the yield from organically produced food seriously competes with the yield from conventional agriculture, but at lower costs. These lower costs are reflected directly, through reduced expenditure on chemical inputs, but also indirectly, through the preservation of soil, climate, and biodiversity, as well as through positive effects on human health. This paper aimed to show that it is possible for a family farm to operate sustainably, ensuring a comfortable and dignified life for the family without having to "trample over the corpses" of our descendants. The world we live in is in our hands, and we control what we will leave as a legacy for future generations. We are witnesses today to the legacy of our ancestors; we suffocate in smog, our water is undrinkable, oceans are acidifying, soils are no longer fertile, and children are already being born sick as a result of the devastated world in which we live. We can repair what can be fixed, but much of it can only be left to nature and time for recovery, as we are powerless before the extent of the damage we have caused—just recall Chernobyl. Today, it is up to us to change our perception of the world. It is not just about us, the individuals, but about an entire civilization. Starting your own sustainable family farm is a small but certain step towards a better future.

Fortunately, individuals have already begun to wake up and actively work on this, encouraging the rest of us who believe that we can do something good—for ourselves and for the future. Sustainable family farms will, over time, become living systems that support humanity, with their main function being growth and development as spiritual beings. No other being cares as much about food and shelter as humans do; instead, they live in harmony with nature and their own nature. Once humanity removes all unnecessary concerns from its mind, it will have space for creativity, which is its primary purpose, and a new era will begin for mankind.

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APPLICATION OF EXPERIMENTAL ECONOMICS IN AGRICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to define the topic of experimental economics, which is becoming increasingly important in studying a wide range of issues related to agriculture. On the other hand, agricultural activity provides an excellent field for validating the use of tools employed in experimental economics. The available literature, in both digital and printed formats, was used for this study, and the methods applied include the descriptive method, analytical method, comparative method, compilation method, and deductive method. Experimental economics plays a crucial role in studying individual behavior in business decision-making within agriculture. Games in experimental economics are one of the most common methods for studying such behavior, enabling researchers to test hypotheses and predict individual behavior in various situations. The knowledge gained from experimental economics can be extremely useful in improving agricultural production and adapting to market conditions.

KEYWORDS: experimental economics, agriculture, business decision-making, economic experiments

ABSTRAKT

Ziel dieses Beitrags ist es, das Thema der experimentellen Ökonomie zu definieren, das bei der Untersuchung einer Vielzahl von Fragen im Zusammenhang mit der Landwirtschaft zunehmend an Bedeutung gewinnt. Andererseits bietet die landwirtschaftliche Tätigkeit ein hervorragendes Feld für die Validierung der in der experimentellen Ökonomie eingesetzten Instrumente. Für diese Studie wurde die verfügbare Literatur in digitaler und gedruckter Form verwendet. Zu den angewandten Methoden gehören die deskriptive Methode, die analytische Methode, die vergleichende Methode, die Kompilationsmethode und die deduktive Methode. Die experimentelle Wirtschaftswissenschaft spielt eine entscheidende Rolle bei der Untersuchung des individuellen Verhaltens bei unternehmerischen Entscheidungen in der Landwirtschaft. Spiele in der experimentellen Ökonomie sind eine der gebräuchlichsten Methoden zur Untersuchung solchen Verhaltens, die es Forschern ermöglichen, Hypothesen zu testen und individuelles Verhalten in verschiedenen Situationen vorherzusagen. Die aus der experimentellen Ökonomie gewonnenen Erkenntnisse können bei der Verbesserung der landwirtschaftlichen Produktion und der Anpassung an die Marktbedingungen von großem Nutzen sein.

STICHWORTE: Experimentelle Ökonomie, Landwirtschaft, unternehmerische Entscheidungsfindung, ökonomische Experimente

RÉSUMÉ

L'objectif de cet article est de définir le thème de l'économie expérimentale, qui devient de plus en plus important dans l'étude d'un large éventail de questions liées à l'agriculture. D'autre part, l'activité

agricole fournit un excellent terrain pour valider l'utilisation des outils employés dans l'économie expérimentale. La littérature disponible, sous forme numérique et imprimée, a été utilisée pour cette étude, et les méthodes appliquées comprennent la méthode descriptive, la méthode analytique, la méthode comparative, la méthode de compilation et la méthode déductive. L'économie expérimentale joue un rôle crucial dans l'étude du comportement individuel dans la prise de décision au sein de l'agriculture. Les jeux dans l'économie expérimentale sont l'une des méthodes les plus courantes pour étudier ce comportement, permettant aux chercheurs de tester des hypothèses et de prédire le comportement individuel dans diverses situations. Les connaissances acquises grâce à l'économie expérimentale peuvent être extrêmement utiles pour améliorer la production agricole et s'adapter aux conditions du marché.

MOTS-CLÉS: économie expérimentale, agriculture, prise de décision dans l'entreprise, expériences économiques

INTRODUCTION

Experimental economics is an interdisciplinary branch of economics that employs methods from experimental psychology, mathematics, and statistics to study human behavior in economic situations (Galdeano-Gómez et al., 2016).

In the context of business decision-making in agriculture, experimental economics plays a crucial role in investigating and predicting the behavior of agricultural producers under different conditions. One of the most common methods in experimental economics is the use of games. These games simulate scenarios in which participants assume various roles and make decisions based on the rules of the game. An example of such a game in the agricultural context is the common-pool resources game, which simulates situations where farmers share resources like water or land (Hermann & Musshoff, 2016).

Games in experimental economics allow for the study of individual behavior under various conditions, such as changes in product prices or variations in service quality. These games enable researchers to test hypotheses about individual behavior and predict how these individuals will act in real-life situations. Experimental economics also plays an important role in forecasting market trends in agriculture. For instance, it can be used to examine different market conditions, such as prices, supply, and demand, to predict the behavior of producers and consumers in the market (Heukelom, 2014).

This knowledge can be valuable for agricultural producers and companies to better adapt to market conditions and make informed decisions. Experimental economics has numerous applications in business decision-making, particularly in areas like data analysis, artificial intelligence, and machine learning (Heukelom, 2014).

The topic of experimental economics in agricultural business decision-making remains under-researched globally. While some studies address this subject, there is a need for further research to assess individual behavior in the agricultural sector and their decision-making processes.

Moreover, it is essential to establish a clear connection between experimental economics and agriculture and to explore the implications of various experimental economics games for this sector. As such, this topic could serve as an intriguing area of research for the academic community.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Conceptual Definition of Experimental Economics

Experimental economics is a branch of economics that applies experimental methods to study economic issues. It is used to test existing economic theories or propose new ones, enabling controlled examination of experimental subjects, markets, economic institutions, and rules (Horonitz, 2013). Unlike traditional economic methods, which rely on observing human behavior, experimental economics uses controlled environments and laboratory experiments to better understand human behavior and decision-making in various situations (Doyon et al., 2010).

According to Vernon Smith, a Nobel Prize laureate in economics in 2002, "experimental economics applies laboratory methods to study human interactions in social contexts governed by explicit or implicit rules" (Horonitz, 2013).

Behavioral economics is considered the foundation of experimental economics. Behavioral economics provides a theoretical framework for studying the "irrationality of economic agents (*homo economicus*)" (Zelić and Lukavac, 2018). It draws on knowledge from psychology, biology, anthropology, sociology, and other social sciences (Dhami, 2016). Behavioral and experimental economics are complementary and enhance one another (Dhami, 2016). While behavioral economics proposes experiments to test theories, experimental economics focuses on predicting economic models and guiding the further development of behavioral models (Dhami, 2016).

Experimental economics employs experimental methods to study economic questions. It uses scientific experiments to test the choices individuals make in specific circumstances, examine alternative market mechanisms, and evaluate economic theories.

Key Features of Experimental Economics (Whitaker, 2008):

- **Efficiency Testing:** Experimental economics examines the efficiency of economic principles and strategies in a laboratory setting with participants.
- **Market Functioning:** It aims to understand the reasons and factors influencing market functionality.
- **Policy Evaluation:** Vernon Smith pioneered methodologies allowing researchers to assess the effects of policy changes before implementation. Economic experiments often use monetary incentives to simulate real-world motivations.

Experiments are used to understand how and why markets and exchange systems operate as they do. Experimental economics has expanded to include institutions and laws (e.g., experimental law and economics) (Biol et al., 2015).

Core Aspects of the Discipline. A fundamental aspect of experimental economics is experiment design. Experiments can be conducted in laboratories or the field, focusing on individual or group behavior. Variants outside these formal constraints include natural and quasi-natural experiments (Heukelom, 2014).

Data collected from experiments are used to estimate effect sizes, test the validity of economic theories, and shed light on market mechanisms. Experimental economics allows policymakers to test whether specific public policies or actions could have significant effects before their application. This approach enables researchers to evaluate economic-political measures before implementation (Loewenstein, 1999).

Applications and Observations. Experiments allow researchers to observe groups addressing specific problems, clearly define decisions to be made, and avoid uncontrolled effects or noise that might distort decision-making processes. These experiments simulate real economic contexts, offering participants appropriate incentives to act according to their criteria. At the end of experiments, participants receive compensation based on the results of their actions (Hermann and Musshoff, 2016; Canavari et al., 2019).

Thus, researchers can understand how and why markets and agents react to rule changes during different experiment phases. Experimental economics provides valuable insights into economic behavior across various subfields, such as game theory, consumer behavior, industrial organization, public finance, labor economics, and agricultural economics (Disdier and Marette, 2012).

Relevance to Agriculture. Over the past two decades, experimental economics has gained significance in researching a wide range of agricultural issues (Mesa-Vázquez et al., 2021). This field is particularly relevant for policymakers designing measures to improve societal welfare by increasing market efficiency and creating a regulatory framework better aligned with reality. It relies on an improved understanding of the behavior of involved parties (suppliers, demand, markets, and institutions) (Doyon et al., 2010). Agriculture is considered an ideal scenario for applying experimental economics tools, characterized by a mutually beneficial relationship between these two disciplines (Canavari et al., 2019).

On the one hand, experimental economics provides a deeper understanding of issues relevant to the agricultural sector. Experimental methods have proven effective in contributing to greater knowledge of the behavior of agents such as farmers, producers, consumers, markets, and economic institutions (Costanigro and Onozaka, 2019). On the other hand, agriculture represents an ideal research field for testing the validity of experimental instruments, contributing to the development of this area of study and the existing literature debates on specific topics (Dubina and Carayannis, 2015).

2. Experimental Economics in Agriculture

Agriculture is considered an ideal scenario for implementing tools of experimental economics due to the mutually beneficial two-way relationship between the two fields (Stenger, 2000). On one hand, experimental economics can be used to gain deeper insights into issues relevant to the agricultural sector. Experimental methods have proven effective in contributing to a better understanding of the behavior of involved actors, such as farmers, producers, consumers, markets, and economic institutions. On the other hand, agriculture serves as an ideal research area for validating experimental instruments, thereby contributing to the development of this field of study and addressing specific debates in the literature.

The agri-food sector represents a significant part of the economy in many countries, especially in developing nations. However, despite its importance, this sector faces numerous challenges, such as raw material prices, climate change, bioeconomy, organic farming, renewable energy sources, changes in demand for various products, and more. Therefore, it is crucial to apply economic experiments to study this sector.

The application of experimental economics in agriculture is steadily growing, with experiments often used to study the behavior of farmers, markets, and food consumers. For instance, experiments can analyze the impact of various agricultural policies, such as subsidies or taxes, on farmers' behavior and market conditions (Dubina, Carayannis, 2015).

The use of experimental economics in the agri-food sector enables a better understanding of business problems and agricultural policy issues. It also facilitates improved managerial decisions and enhances the competitiveness of the domestic agri-food sector (Galdeano-Gómez et al., 2016; Nguyen & Leung, 2009).

Economic experimental methods can address numerous issues in the agri-food sector. For example, they can investigate the impact of raw material prices on the sector or the effects of climate change on agriculture. If climate change is found to influence the production of a specific crop, managers in the agri-food sector can make informed decisions to adapt production based on these findings (Whitaker, 2008).

Experimental economics can also explore how changes in demand affect this sector. For example, if changes in demand for a particular product influence its price, managers in the agri-food sector can make decisions regarding the production and sale of that product based on this information (Brañas-Garza, Paz-Espinosa, 2011). Furthermore, it is essential to involve experts from other fields, such as agronomists, nutritionists, biologists, and others, to obtain comprehensive and reliable results.

The application of economic experimental methods in the agri-food sector facilitates rational decision-making in the production, distribution, and marketing of sector products (Brañas-Garza, Paz-Espinosa, 2011). Additionally, it can drive innovation and entrepreneurship in the sector, as well as the development of new products and services.

Ultimately, the application of experimental economic methods in this sector will contribute to the country's economic development and improve the standard of living for its residents.

3. Overview of Research Among Agricultural Producers

Horonitz (2013) examined the relationship between the complexity of farm management and the technical performance of agricultural holdings. This study highlighted the need for improved farm management to achieve greater efficiency.

Brañas-Garza and Paz-Espinosa (2011) explored how farmers tend to be risk-averse and are twice as sensitive to losses as they are to gains. This means that farmers focus more on preventing losses than on generating profits. These findings are important because farmers frequently make decisions that affect the future of their operations, necessitating the consideration of such aspects in decision-making processes.

Disdier and Marette (2012) investigated the lack of cooperation among farmers under conditions of uncertainty. Farmers often do not collaborate or share information about uncertainties impacting their farms. These insights underline the need to enhance cooperation among farmers to mitigate the impact of uncertainties.

Heukelom (2014) studied farmers' preferences for using variable rates of nitrogen fertilizer. The results indicate that farmers are inclined to adopt variable-rate nitrogen application, with cost, yield, and environmental preservation being key drivers for adopting new technology. These findings emphasize the need to develop and promote new technologies that can help farmers achieve better outcomes with less environmental impact.

Research involving farmers provides valuable insights into their needs, challenges, and preferences. Such data can be utilized to develop policies and programs aimed at improving farm performance. For instance, findings from Hermann and Musshoff (2016) on shortcomings in farm management can be used to design educational programs to enhance farmers' managerial skills. Insights

from Smith (2003) on farmers' risk aversion can inform the development of crop insurance programs to help farmers safeguard against potential losses.

Studies on weak cooperation among farmers in uncertain conditions, such as that by Biro et al. (2015), can guide the creation of programs to foster better relationships and collaboration among farmers, thereby reducing the negative effects of uncertainty on their farms. Findings from Marette et al. (2008) on farmers' preferences for new technologies can support the development of programs to facilitate technology adoption, helping farmers achieve better results on their farms. These findings also stress the importance of sustainable development in agriculture and the need to create technologies that enable farmers to meet their goals with a reduced environmental footprint.

Experimental economics, as a scientific field, examines the economic behavior of individuals and organizations through experimental research. One application of experimental economics is the analysis of producers' behavior in the agricultural sector, particularly in organic farming. For example, Dubina and Carayannis (2015) conducted research on this topic. Organic farming is known to be based on sustainability principles and avoids the use of synthetic chemicals.

Although demand for organic products is increasing, many farmers hesitate to transition to organic farming. In this context, Roosen and Marette (2011) aimed to better understand farmers' behavior regarding investments in organic farming. Their results showed that farmers already practicing organic methods are more likely to invest in new organic techniques than those using conventional methods.

In other words, farmers are less inclined to invest in production methods they are not currently using compared to those already in use on their farms. The study also revealed that investment decisions depend on the existing production methods on the farm. Farmers are more likely to invest in familiar methods than in new, untested ones. This suggests that farmers perceive the risks of investing in new methods as higher than those associated with familiar ones.

Research by Canavari et al. (2019) offers valuable insights into farmers' behavior concerning investments in organic farming. Their findings align with previous studies, indicating that farmers using organic methods are more inclined to invest in new organic techniques than those using conventional practices.

In this regard, policies should focus on improving farmers' education about the benefits and techniques of organic farming, as well as enhancing market access for organic products. This research also highlights the need for further studies on farmers' behavior regarding investments in organic farming. Future research could examine how farmers assess the risks of investing in new production methods or how they decide to transition to organic farming.

Whitaker (2008) provides useful insights into farmers' behavior concerning investments in organic farming. Their findings underscore the need for changes in policies to encourage such investments and for further research on farmers' behavior in this area.

Experimental economics is a branch of economics that tests economic theories through controlled experiments. This approach allows researchers to observe how individuals and organizations respond to specific economic conditions and policies in a controlled environment.

An example of experimental economics research is the study by Dubina and Carayannis (2015) on consumer preferences for environmentally produced wine. In a hypothetical market, wines were differentiated by region of origin, landscape features, production methods (organic or conventional), wine

labels, and price. Respondents were asked about their preferences and inclinations regarding these wine characteristics.

The study results showed that the designation of origin was the most important factor considered by all respondents when purchasing wine. However, more than a quarter of the sample expressed interest in buying organic wine and were willing to pay a premium for it. This indicates a significant market for organically produced wine and highlights consumer interest in such products (Dubina and Carayannis, 2015). Wine producers can leverage this insight to promote their organic wines and increase sales.

This example of experimental economics research underscores the importance of studying consumer preferences for specific products and characteristics. It demonstrates how producers can utilize these insights to enhance sales. Experimental economics provides valuable understanding of individual and organizational preferences under certain economic conditions and policies.

4. Review of Consumer Research

Consumers play a crucial role in any economy as they make decisions about purchasing goods and services. Understanding their attitudes, preferences, and motivations is therefore essential for business success.

One study worth mentioning is the research by Nguyen and Leung (2009) on consumers' willingness to pay a premium for food grown on land not irrigated with wastewater. The findings revealed that consumers were ready to pay more for such food, suggesting a clear interest in food safety. This insight could be beneficial for food producers who may invest more in food safety measures to attract more customers.

Galdeano-Gómez et al. (2016) investigated why consumers prefer shopping at farmers' markets over supermarkets and how much more they are willing to pay for locally grown products. This knowledge could help food producers emphasize the local origin of their products to attract more buyers.

Birol et al. (2015) conducted a laboratory study on how consumers respond to food and packaging produced using nanotechnology. Nanotechnology is used to enhance product performance, such as extending food shelf life, but concerns remain about its potential impact on food safety and consumer health. Participants were exposed to various examples of food and packaging made with nanotechnology and were asked about their perceptions, concerns, and willingness to buy these products. Results showed that participants were more cautious about food and packaging produced with nanotechnology compared to traditional products. This highlights the importance of understanding consumer attitudes toward new technologies in food production and packaging. Producers and marketers should consider this cautious perception and include educational efforts and detailed product information in their marketing strategies.

The final study to note is by Roosen and Marette (2011), which examined the impact of health messages on consumer choices. In this field experiment, participants were provided with different information about the health benefits of the products they were buying, such as reduced risk of heart disease or improved digestion. Results indicated that consumers were more inclined to purchase products labeled as healthier or more nutritious. However, the study also showed that too much information about health benefits could have a counterproductive effect, confusing consumers and discouraging purchases. This research emphasizes the importance of clear and concise presentation of health-related product

information to encourage healthier choices among consumers. Excessive information can confuse buyers, so marketing strategies should focus on the key advantages of a product.

Consumer research can also help identify issues or deficiencies in products and services, enabling improvements that enhance customer satisfaction. For instance, if research reveals that certain packaging is inconvenient or unpleasant for consumers, manufacturers might consider redesigning it to improve the user experience. Moreover, consumer research offers insights into trends in consumer habits and preferences. For example, if studies show that an increasing number of consumers are shifting toward healthier food options or seeking environmentally friendly products, this can influence how producers develop their products and marketing strategies.

Smith (2003) notes that consumer research should not be conducted solely for marketing purposes but should also serve to improve the products and services offered to consumers. High-quality consumer research must be rigorous, objective, and conducted in adherence to ethical standards. Understanding consumer behavior, preferences, and habits is of utmost importance, and the findings from such research can be highly beneficial. They can help improve the products and services offered, develop more effective marketing strategies, and adapt to changes in consumer trends (Doyon et al., 2010).

Therefore, manufacturers, retailers, and marketing professionals should use consumer research as a critical tool in their business strategies. Additionally, the results of economic experiments provide policymakers, particularly in agriculture, with an opportunity to test whether certain public policies or actions could have significant effects before implementing them. In this way, experiments can guide economic policy measures prior to their application.

5. Experimental Economics in Agriculture and Business Decision-Making

Experimental economics is highly significant for business decision-making as it helps understand how individuals make decisions in situations involving risk and uncertainty. This approach allows economists to conduct tests and analyze various scenarios, identifying the variables that influence decision-making.

The application of experimental methods in economics is valuable in various contexts, including studying policy effects, testing different consumer behavior models, and analyzing market interactions. Furthermore, experimental economics is beneficial in the business world, as it enables informed decision-making based on realistic scenarios. One example is market testing (Whitaker, 2008), where companies can examine how consumers would behave in specific situations, such as reactions to price changes or preferences between different products. This research helps companies better understand customer needs and preferences, enabling them to tailor their products and marketing strategies accordingly.

Another example is research on employee motivation (Hermann and Musshoff, 2016). Experiments can identify which reward systems best motivate employees and how various working conditions affect productivity. Such knowledge helps create work environments tailored to employees' needs, leading to increased productivity and better business outcomes.

Experimental economics is vital for business decision-making as it equips companies to make informed decisions based on realistic scenarios. This approach enables economists to conduct tests and analyses of different scenarios, identifying variables influencing decision-making. Applying experimental methods in business helps companies understand their customers' and employees' preferences and

needs, creating products and workplaces tailored to these needs (Roosen and Marette, 2011). Companies can use experiments to test various marketing strategies and discover how consumers react to price changes and other conditions, thereby adjusting campaigns to maximize profitability.

An important aspect of experimental economics in business is decision-making research. Experiments help understand how individuals make decisions under risk and uncertainty (Loewenstein, 1999), which is particularly useful in financial decision-making, where understanding risk is crucial for success.

Despite the advantages of experimental economics in business, it is important to note some limitations. Experiments can be expensive and time-consuming, requiring significant resources for proper execution. Additionally, experimental results may not always apply to real-world scenarios, as individuals may behave differently in experiments compared to real-life situations.

Research utilizing experimental economics should be part of the toolkit companies use to succeed and remain competitive. In the agricultural sector, such experiments aid in making better business decisions in areas where traditional economics falls short, such as organizational decisions and strategic planning. For instance, experimental results can assess the impact of investments in agricultural projects or evaluate various farming and production strategies.

Experimental economics is also used in public policy, particularly in agriculture, to develop better measures. Experimental results are increasingly utilized to evaluate the effectiveness of existing policies and measures and test new ones. Researchers can simulate real market conditions and analyze how individuals react to specific changes. For example, experiments can assess the impact of public policies such as taxes, subsidies, and other agricultural market interventions (Smith, 2003).

Such experiments help evaluate the effectiveness of existing policies in various agricultural and environmental sectors. They also identify issues in current policies and provide essential information for developing new ones aligned with market and societal needs. For instance, experimental results can evaluate measures to reduce pesticide use in agriculture. Researchers can conduct experiments with different farmer groups, analyzing reactions to subsidies or incentives for reducing pesticide use. These data can inform better policies and measures for reducing pesticide reliance.

Experimental methods are also useful for testing marketing strategies for agricultural products, determining how consumers respond to various prices and conditions (Biol, Oparinde, et al., 2015). Additionally, experiments can explore how farmers make decisions under risk and uncertainty, such as crop selection or investing in technology. This knowledge helps farmers make informed decisions about the best crops to grow or the most efficient technologies to adopt.

Experimental economics also applies to policies related to agriculture, such as incentives or regulations. Experiments test different policies and evaluate their potential impacts on farmer behavior and market interactions in the agricultural industry. For example, experiments might assess the effects of a new policy aimed at reducing synthetic fertilizer use. Researchers can monitor farmers' responses to the policy and analyze its impact on the agricultural market. These findings enable policymakers to determine whether the policy is effective and suitable for real-world implementation.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the growing importance of experimental economics in exploring a wide range of issues related to agriculture. At the same time, agricultural activities provide an excellent domain for validating the tools and methodologies utilized in experimental economics. Experimental economics plays a crucial role in examining individual behavior in making business decisions within the agricultural sector. For instance, behavioral economics investigates how individuals make decisions and respond to various incentives and information. Experimental economics employs controlled experiments to test different policies and programs in real-time.

Previous research conducted among farmers has focused on agro-environmental issues, the design and implementation of insurance schemes, the use of fertilizers, and other topics. Studies have also shown that farmers tend to focus more on loss prevention than on profit maximization. Meanwhile, research on consumers reveals a willingness to pay higher prices for safer and higher-quality food.

In conclusion, behavioral and experimental economics provide valuable insights into decision-making related to agro-environmental policies and programs. However, agro-ecological conditions can pose challenges for such research. It is therefore essential to continue developing new methods of data collection and analysis and to establish innovative forms of collaboration to ensure an appropriate and sustainable approach to these topics.

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POLICIES, CHALLENGES AND ACHIEVED LEVEL OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF KOSOVO AFTER INDEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to analyze and evaluate the macroeconomic development policies, challenges, and achieved level of economic progress in Kosovo following its independence. It aims to provide a comprehensive assessment of the country's economic trajectory by examining key issues such as GDP growth, fiscal and monetary policies, unemployment, trade imbalances, privatization, corruption, and governance inefficiencies. Kosovo's economic development following independence has been characterized by moderate growth, structural weaknesses, and persistent socio-economic challenges. Despite some progress in financial stability, the country continues to struggle with high unemployment, weak industrial development, corruption, and an imbalanced trade structure.

KEYWORDS: policies, corruption, economic development. Republic of Kosovo

ABSTRAKT

Ziel dieses Artikels ist die Analyse und Bewertung der makroökonomischen Entwicklungspolitik, der Herausforderungen und des erreichten wirtschaftlichen Fortschritts im Kosovo nach seiner Unabhängigkeit. Er zielt darauf ab, eine umfassende Bewertung der wirtschaftlichen Entwicklung des Landes vorzunehmen, indem er Schlüsselthemen wie BIP-Wachstum, Steuer- und Geldpolitik, Arbeitslosigkeit, Handelsungleichgewichte, Privatisierung, Korruption und ineffiziente Regierungsführung untersucht. Die wirtschaftliche Entwicklung des Kosovo nach der Unabhängigkeit ist durch mäßiges Wachstum, strukturelle Schwächen und anhaltende sozioökonomische Probleme gekennzeichnet. Trotz einiger Fortschritte bei der finanziellen Stabilität hat das Land weiterhin mit hoher Arbeitslosigkeit, schwacher industrieller Entwicklung, Korruption und einer unausgewogenen Handelsstruktur zu kämpfen.

STICHWORTE: Politik, Korruption, wirtschaftliche Entwicklung. Republik Kosovo

RÉSUMÉ

L'objectif de cet article est d'analyser et d'évaluer les politiques de développement macroéconomique, les défis et le niveau de progrès économique atteint par le Kosovo après son indépendance. Il vise à fournir une évaluation complète de la trajectoire économique du pays en examinant des questions clés telles que la croissance du PIB, les politiques fiscales et monétaires, le chômage, les déséquilibres commerciaux, la privatisation, la corruption et les inefficacités de la gouvernance. Le développement économique du Kosovo après l'indépendance a été caractérisé par une croissance modérée, des faiblesses structurelles et des défis socio-économiques persistants. Malgré quelques progrès en matière de stabilité financière, le pays reste confronté à un taux de chômage élevé, à un faible développement industriel, à la corruption et à une structure commerciale déséquilibrée.

MOTS-CLÉS: politiques, corruption, développement économique. République du Kosovo

INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that Kosovo's independence marks a date of significant historical importance—not only for Albanians in Kosovo but for the entire Albanian nation. This event signified the end of Serbo-Slavic occupation and rule, fulfilling the centuries-old dream of Albanians: liberation from Serbo-Slavism. With Kosovo emerging as the newest state in Europe, a fresh political, economic, and social landscape was established, fostering independent development in this region.

The purpose of this article is to analyze and evaluate the macroeconomic development policies, challenges, and achieved level of economic progress in Kosovo following its independence. It aims to provide a comprehensive assessment of the country's economic trajectory by examining key issues such as GDP growth, fiscal and monetary policies, unemployment, trade imbalances, privatization, corruption, and governance inefficiencies.

Through an in-depth review of economic indicators and policy outcomes, the article seeks to:

- Identify the key macroeconomic policies implemented in Kosovo and assess their effectiveness.
- Highlight major economic challenges, including unemployment, lack of industrialization, and weak institutional frameworks.
- Analyze the impact of corruption and poor governance on economic development.
- Provide policy recommendations for fostering sustainable economic growth, improving institutional accountability, and promoting private sector development.
- By addressing these issues, the article aims to contribute to economic policy discussions and reforms, offering valuable insights for policymakers, economists, researchers, and stakeholders involved in Kosovo's economic development.

A descriptive and analytical research design were employed to examine Kosovo's economic policies, challenges, and progress post-independence. The study will combine secondary data analysis, comparative analysis, and qualitative content analysis to assess the effectiveness of economic policies and identify key barriers to development. The following methods are used:

- **Policy Review:** Government policy documents, economic reports, and legal frameworks will be analyzed to assess the effectiveness of Kosovo's macroeconomic policies.
- **Corruption and Governance Analysis:** Reports from **Transparency International, OECD, UNDP, and Kosovo Anti-Corruption Agency** will be examined to understand the impact of corruption on economic performance.
- A **literature review** will be conducted using academic studies, policy papers, and economic research from **peer-reviewed journals, institutional reports, and economic think tanks**.
- Expert opinions from economists, policymakers, and governance specialists may be incorporated through **existing interviews and reports** to provide insights into economic challenges and reforms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Macroeconomic Development Policies

Macroeconomic development policies play a crucial role in shaping the economic trajectory of post-conflict countries, particularly in Kosovo. As a newly independent state, Kosovo has faced significant

challenges in achieving sustainable economic growth, reducing unemployment, and integrating into regional and global markets. This literature review examines key macroeconomic policies implemented in Kosovo, their effectiveness, and the challenges that remain.

Kosovo's economic development has been characterized by moderate GDP growth, driven primarily by consumption, remittances, and public investment. The World Bank (2022) highlights that Kosovo's GDP growth has averaged around 3-4% annually over the past decade, surpassing some regional peers but still lagging in terms of structural transformation. Despite this, Kosovo's GDP per capita remains among the lowest in the Western Balkans, reflecting persistent economic vulnerabilities (European Commission, 2023).

According to Rraci and Gashi (2020), one of the major issues affecting Kosovo's macroeconomic policy is its reliance on remittances from the diaspora, which accounts for approximately 15% of GDP. While remittances boost consumption and financial stability, they do not contribute to long-term productive investment or industrialization (IMF, 2021).

Kosovo's fiscal policy has been expansionary, focusing on public sector wages, infrastructure projects, and social benefits (OECD, 2021). The country has maintained low public debt compared to regional counterparts, with debt levels below 30% of GDP (Ministry of Finance, 2022). However, critics argue that government spending has not been sufficiently directed toward productive sectors, such as manufacturing and export-oriented industries (Mustafa & Hoti, 2019).

A key challenge in fiscal policy has been the inefficiency in tax collection and the prevalence of the informal economy, which is estimated to account for over 30% of GDP (UNDP, 2020). The reliance on indirect taxation, particularly VAT and customs duties, has created a regressive tax system that disproportionately affects lower-income groups (Ahmeti, 2018).

Kosovo unilaterally adopted the euro as its official currency, limiting its ability to conduct independent monetary policy (IMF, 2021). While euroization has provided macroeconomic stability and low inflation, it has also restricted Kosovo's ability to respond to economic shocks through currency adjustments (Baliqi, 2020).

The banking sector in Kosovo is considered stable and well-capitalized, but access to credit remains a barrier for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (EBRD, 2022). High interest rates and stringent lending criteria have limited business expansion and investment, further constraining economic growth (Gashi et al., 2021).

Unemployment remains one of Kosovo's most pressing economic challenges. The unemployment rate has consistently been among the highest in Europe, with youth unemployment exceeding 30% (World Bank, 2023). Labor market policies have been insufficient in addressing skills mismatches, leading to a lack of qualified workers in key industries (European Commission, 2022).

Migration has also played a significant role in labor market dynamics, with many skilled workers leaving Kosovo for better opportunities abroad (UNDP, 2021). This has created a paradox where Kosovo simultaneously faces high unemployment and labor shortages in certain sectors, such as IT and construction (KAS, 2023).

Kosovo faces a significant trade imbalance, with imports far exceeding exports (Ministry of Trade, 2022). The country primarily imports consumer goods, while exports are limited to raw materials and low-value-added products (Rraci & Gashi, 2020). Trade agreements with the EU and CEFTA have facilitated

market access, but non-tariff barriers and poor infrastructure continue to hinder trade expansion (OECD, 2021).

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Kosovo has been relatively low compared to other Balkan countries, primarily due to political instability, weak rule of law, and limited market size (EBRD, 2022). Efforts to attract investment through tax incentives and business-friendly reforms have had limited success, as investors remain cautious about Kosovo's institutional environment (Ahmeti, 2018).

Kosovo's macroeconomic development policies have achieved moderate growth and financial stability but have not yet addressed key structural weaknesses. The reliance on remittances, a weak industrial base, high unemployment, and trade deficits continue to pose challenges to long-term economic sustainability. Future policies should focus on diversifying the economy, improving labor market conditions, and strengthening institutional governance to attract investment and foster innovation.

The systemic socio-economic changes following 1999 and Kosovo's independence introduced new political, social, and economic circumstances. However, the economic challenges during this period were particularly evident in the inefficiency of the economic system. Even after independence, Kosovo failed to take serious steps in designing and implementing effective macroeconomic development policies. Unfortunately, economic growth during this time was carried out in an ad hoc manner—lacking strategy, vision, and a consistent economic policy. Policies were implemented sporadically, without thorough analysis of economic trends, despite unfavorable conditions.

Economic development is directly influenced by macroeconomic policies, and their effects are reflected in key global macroeconomic indicators. Regrettably, every government in Kosovo has implemented flawed macroeconomic policies, leading to negative economic consequences. The lack of a well-defined macroeconomic framework has resulted in inefficiencies across economic flows. The consequences of these misguided policies are numerous and far-reaching. Moreover, the ineffective use of economic policy instruments—such as fiscal policy, foreign trade policy, and credit policy—has failed to protect and promote business development, sometimes even hindering local enterprises.

The negative macroeconomic trends stem primarily from unprofessional decision-making, poor personnel policies, and the selection of incompetent individuals for key positions. No Kosovo government has successfully implemented substantial economic reforms or established a coherent economic system that supports business growth and overall economic development. As a result, it is fair to conclude that from the provisional government to the present, Kosovo's leadership has pursued a disastrous macroeconomic policy—or rather, has lacked a proper economic policy altogether.

This failure has plunged Kosovo into a deep economic crisis, exacerbating poverty and social problems while fostering various negative phenomena previously unfamiliar to our society. Corruption has infiltrated state institutions, reaching alarming levels. Bribery, usury, human trafficking, drug trafficking, kleptocracy, nepotism, and other illicit activities have become common occurrences in daily life. These issues have not only weakened the economy but have also led to a severe moral crisis within society.

Today, we live in an era where true values—intellectuals, skilled professionals, and competent individuals—are being overshadowed by incompetence, corruption, and unscrupulous individuals. There is no doubt that these negative trends are poisoning our youth with values that contradict our national ethics.

2. Economic Development Challenges and Issues in Post-Independence Kosovo

It was initially believed that upon gaining independence, the Government of Kosovo, as the primary architect and executor of macroeconomic policies, would revise the development strategies of the previous period, adopt a more pragmatic approach, and leverage economic policy instruments to support local businesses and foster overall economic growth. It was also expected that the government would engage leading professionals and experts in key departments, thereby establishing the necessary institutional and human resources to accelerate economic development.

However, this did not materialize. Even today, Kosovo's economic development continues to struggle with numerous challenges and obstacles.

Below, we outline some of the primary issues and difficulties that have hindered and deteriorated Kosovo's economic progress in the post-independence period.

a) Inadequate Macroeconomic Development Policy

Due to the absence of a well-structured development policy, economic trends in Kosovo during the entire post-liberation period—especially after independence—have been unfavorable, highlighting the inefficiency of the implemented economic strategies. This is best illustrated by key macroeconomic indicators, which, apart from Gross Domestic Product (GDP), have shown alarming negative trends, including:

- A significantly high foreign trade deficit;
- A persistently high unemployment rate;
- An unfavorable economic structure;
- An unbalanced foreign trade composition;
- Economic smuggling and tax evasion;
- Nepotism, kleptocracy, and rampant corruption.

What is even more concerning being that despite these negative trends, neither the Government nor the Parliament of Kosovo has ever prioritized economic issues on their agenda. There has been no meaningful debate, analysis, or action to address and counteract these declining economic trends. The issue of economic development has been discussed only during election campaigns, where exaggerated, empty, and ultimately unfeasible promises have been made. Unfortunately, once elections concluded, economic development ceased to be a governmental priority.

Moreover, Kosovo has lacked a well-implemented economic policy. The government has not provided institutional support for the development of local businesses through concrete policy measures. Instead, economic policies, including public procurement tenders, have largely favored businesses affiliated with political elites, party loyalists, and their relatives. This has given rise to the phenomenon of "tenderomania" in Kosovo. Such practices have negatively impacted overall economic growth and contributed to the uneven distribution of national wealth, primarily benefiting large corporations—often referred to as "mafia companies"—and a select group of individuals.

As a result, a small number of businesses have monopolized Kosovo's economy, controlling the domestic market and, through corrupt means, influencing both the Government and certain Members of Parliament to steer economic policies in their favor.

There is no doubt that this approach to economic policy has harmed and marginalized many, fostering a political and economic environment that has led to the formation of an economic oligarchy. A

handful of businesses now dominate the local economy, particularly in the service sector, which relies heavily on imports rather than domestic production. The underdevelopment of key industrial sectors, particularly agro-industrial processing, has left Kosovo highly dependent on imports, effectively making it a consumer-driven market. All of this points to a glaring failure on the part of the Kosovo Government to establish and implement a consistent macroeconomic development policy, for which the responsibility rests entirely with the executive branch.

a) The Privatization Process. During economic transitions, privatization is a necessary process and a fundamental pillar of reform. Ideally, it should serve as more than just a means of transferring state and socially owned enterprises into private hands—it should be a catalyst for sustainable economic transformation. However, in Kosovo, privatization was poorly understood and mismanaged.

Before independence, the privatization process was led solely by the Kosovo Trust Agency (KTA), which functioned as a “mini-government” and operated with little to no transparency. No local institution had oversight or access to information about its activities. Following independence, the KTA was replaced by the Kosovo Privatization Agency (AKP), an independent government institution tasked with managing privatization efforts. However, the AKP failed to introduce any significant reforms and instead inherited the same systemic problems from its predecessor.

As a result, the privatization process in Kosovo has been marred by corruption, mismanagement, and economic devastation. The KTA’s approach to privatization facilitated one of the most substantial acts of economic plundering in Kosovo’s history, leading to:

- Widespread corruption and misappropriation of state assets;
- The mass dismissal of workers;
- The destruction of existing industrial capacities;
- A stagnation in economic development.

To make matters worse, none of the proceeds from privatized enterprises—deposited in the Privatization Fund—have been reinvested in Kosovo’s economy. These funds, which should have been used to support economic growth, remain outside Kosovo’s banking system, with no clear information on their whereabouts or intended use.

Given all these issues, it is evident that Kosovo’s privatization process was carried out without the necessary legal framework or economic rationale, ultimately making it a complete failure.

b) Lack of a Long-Term Development Strategy

From the outset, it should be noted that after gaining independence, the Government of Kosovo, as the executive body, recognized the importance of drafting a long-term development strategy to guide both short-term and long-term economic progress. However, it failed to successfully create such a document. Over the years, successive governments of Kosovo have attempted to draft this strategy multiple times, but their efforts were unsuccessful due to a lack of professional and scientific expertise, as well as an inadequate methodological approach.

To date, the Government of Kosovo has made five attempts to develop a long-term economic strategy. However, these efforts have been hindered by insufficient professional experience, lack of preparedness, and the absence of a solid scientific and methodological foundation. As a result, each attempt has ended in failure.

c) Inadequate Personnel Policy and Nepotism

Professional personnel play a crucial role in all socio-economic transitions. Their contribution is particularly significant in the era of contemporary technological advancements. Unfortunately, the authorities in Kosovo have failed to recognize the importance of skilled professionals. Due to the absence of a fair and merit-based personnel policy, appointments in public institutions, enterprises, and government bodies have been based not on competence but on political loyalty. Individuals seeking power for personal gain were favored over those genuinely committed to public service.

One of the clearest examples of this malpractice is the "Pronto" campaign, in which high-ranking officials appointed politically affiliated individuals to key positions across various institutions, public enterprises, the judiciary, law enforcement, and other sectors—often following direct orders from their superiors.

As a result, Kosovo's personnel policy in the post-liberation period has been characterized by negative selection. This approach allowed political elites to consolidate control over state institutions, sidelining competent professionals and intellectuals who could have contributed to solving political, social, and economic challenges in the best interest of Kosovo's citizens.

This exclusion of intellectual talent has had far-reaching consequences, including a significant "brain drain," particularly among medical professionals and young people, who have sought opportunities abroad. The implemented personnel policies were not based on meritocracy but were instead driven by partisanship, nepotism, provincialism, and favoritism. Consequently, power has become concentrated in the hands of a select few individuals and political parties, undermining democratic processes and fostering authoritarian tendencies.

Kosovo's leadership has been plagued by political-business entanglements that prioritize self-enrichment over the public good. The concentration of power in the hands of a few has facilitated the rapid accumulation of wealth through illegal means. This raises an essential philosophical question: "Does society shape morality, or does morality shape society?" In Kosovo, the increasing economic prosperity of a few has often been accompanied by a decline in collective human values and social solidarity.

A stark contrast exists between the small elite that has accumulated wealth through corruption and the vast majority of the population—especially pensioners, individuals with disabilities, war veterans, and families of fallen soldiers—who continue to struggle for basic survival. Despite these challenges, those in power remain indifferent, as their own material well-being shields them from these realities.

Given the current political, social, and economic landscape in Kosovo, the general public—excluding the ruling elite—is filled with despair and hopelessness. The youth, who represent the country's greatest economic and intellectual potential, feel particularly disillusioned, with many expressing their desire to leave Kosovo due to a lack of future prospects. Unfortunately, Kosovo's leadership remains entrenched in personal egos and elitist attitudes, which hinder progress and innovation.

Public figures, whether political leaders or state officials, should embody moral authority and serve as role models. However, many Kosovar leaders fail to uphold the values they claim to represent. Corrupt individuals who claim to fight corruption erode public trust, leading to a crisis of moral leadership. Despite widespread awareness of these issues, neither the scientific community, universities, students, nor intellectuals have taken meaningful action to challenge the status quo. This silence has allowed those in power to continue their deceptive practices unchecked.

A culture of political snobbery has emerged, in which politicians in government institutions view themselves as the sole architects of state policies across all socio-economic sectors. Left unchallenged, this self-perception reinforces their belief in their superiority, despite evidence to the contrary.

d) Informal Economy and Tax Evasion

Throughout the post-liberation period, certain individuals and economic entities have exploited institutional weaknesses, corruption among high-ranking officials, and the lack of effective economic policies to engage in impermissible economic transactions.

The informal economy remains a significant issue in Kosovo, yet its exact scope is difficult to determine due to its hidden and illegal nature. Although no official data exists, estimates suggest that the informal sector contributes between 30% and 40% of Kosovo's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Several factors have fueled the growth of the informal economy, including:

- Institutional inefficiency of state bodies
- Low levels of economic development
- Lack of domestic production
- Economic crisis and widespread poverty
- High unemployment rates
- Organized crime and economic smuggling

e) Corruption

These factors have not only contributed to the expansion of the informal economy but have also led to widespread tax evasion, significantly reducing state budget revenues. Furthermore, these challenges have deterred foreign direct investment (FDI), which, in the absence of strong domestic investment, is a crucial driver of Kosovo's economic development.

Corruption remains a persistent issue in Kosovo, undermining the rule of law, economic growth, and public trust in institutions. According to Transparency International (2023), Kosovo ranks among the most corrupt countries in Europe, with weak judicial enforcement and political interference in anti-corruption efforts. The establishment of the Kosovo Anti-Corruption Agency was a significant step in addressing corruption, but its effectiveness has been limited due to a lack of prosecutions and accountability for high-ranking officials (European Commission, 2022).

Meyer-Sahling et al. (2020) argue that post-conflict states like Kosovo often struggle with systemic corruption due to weak institutions and political patronage networks. This "Iloji phenomenon," where corruption is well-documented but goes largely unpunished, reflects broader governance failures in Kosovo and similar post-Yugoslav states (Elbasani, 2018).

The failure of key state institutions—including the judiciary and law enforcement—to uphold accountability has allowed individuals in high-ranking government and political positions to abuse their authority for personal gain. Corruption in Kosovo is not just present; it has reached an advanced stage of metastasis, permeating every level of government and public administration.

Without minimizing other economic challenges, corruption remains the primary obstacle to the consistent implementation of macroeconomic policies and the normal functioning of the state apparatus. Corruption in Kosovo has created a "vicious circle" that obstructs democratic processes and the rule of law.

According to Transparency International's Corruption Perceptions Index, Kosovo ranked 105th in 2015 and improved slightly to 95th in 2016. Despite these rankings, corruption levels in Kosovo remain among the highest in the region, comparable to those of underdeveloped nations such as Argentina, Sri Lanka, Benin, and Rwanda.

In conclusion, the economic and political challenges outlined above underscore the urgent need for comprehensive reforms in governance, economic policy, and institutional accountability. Without decisive action, Kosovo risks further entrenching systemic inefficiencies that hinder sustainable development and democratic progress.

Following Kosovo's independence, the Kosovo Anti-Corruption Agency was established to combat corruption. Reports from both the Central Auditor and this agency, backed by substantial evidence, led to corruption charges against numerous individuals, including a significant number of high-ranking state and party officials implicated in abuses and misconduct. However, despite corruption being legally recognized as a criminal offense and the principle that no one is above the law, only a few minor cases have been prosecuted. No major political or governmental figures have been held accountable in court or resigned, even though their involvement in corruption is well-documented. This paradox, often referred to as the "Iloji phenomenon," is a unique reflection of Kosovo's societal and institutional challenges.

f) Economic Development in Kosovo

Economic development plays a crucial role in both theoretical analysis and practical policymaking. In the post-independence period, Kosovo, as a newly established state, faced numerous political, social, and economic challenges. A particularly detrimental factor affecting economic progress has been the ongoing, unconstructive political struggle between parties for power. This prolonged political instability has consistently sidelined economic development.

To present a positive image of the country's economic progress, the Government of Kosovo frequently highlights one key indicator—real GDP growth. It is true that Kosovo's GDP growth rate has been one of the highest in the region, second only to Montenegro. In 2016, Kosovo's GDP growth stood at 3.6%, compared to Albania (3.4%), Bosnia and Herzegovina (3.0%), Montenegro (5.1%), North Macedonia (2.2%), and Serbia (2.5%). However, GDP growth alone does not provide a complete or accurate picture of a country's economic well-being. Kosovo's relatively high growth rate is largely a result of its low comparative economic base, meaning that even minor improvements can produce seemingly high growth percentages.

To accurately assess economic progress, multiple macroeconomic indicators must be considered, including GDP per capita, employment and unemployment rates, economic structure, trade balance, industrialization, and export-import ratios. In economic analyses, choosing the most relevant indicators remains a challenge, as different economists emphasize different factors. However, most agree that GDP per capita and the unemployment rate are among the most accurate measures of a country's true economic development.

A comparative analysis of Kosovo's post-independence economic performance against regional counterparts reveals significant disparities. In 2014, Kosovo's GDP per capita was:

- 1.7 times lower than Albania's,
- 1.8 times lower than Bosnia and Herzegovina's,

- 2.6 times lower than Montenegro's, and
- 2.0 times lower than North Macedonia's.
- Similarly, in the same year, Kosovo's unemployment rate was:
- 2.6 times higher than Albania's,
- 1.7 times higher than North Macedonia's,
- 2.5 times higher than Serbia's,
- 2.5 times higher than Montenegro's, and
- 1.6 times higher than Bosnia and Herzegovina's.

These figures clearly demonstrate that Kosovo lags behind all neighboring countries in terms of economic development. GDP per capita and unemployment rates serve as essential indicators that provide a more realistic assessment of the country's economic condition.

Despite these facts, the Government of Kosovo consistently avoids presenting data on these two critical indicators in its public reports, as doing so would contradict the narrative that Kosovo is developing faster than its neighbors. This selective reporting distorts economic realities and misleads the public, reflecting a serious lack of governmental responsibility and transparency.

g) Kosovo's Political and Social Challenges

In the post-independence period, Kosovo has faced severe political, economic, and social challenges, leading to a deep moral and institutional crisis. The current situation is a direct consequence of political mismanagement and flawed macroeconomic policies. As a result, Kosovo is experiencing fractures in nearly all aspects of life, with increasing complexity in political, social, and economic matters.

Rapid transformations and emerging challenges are often accompanied by uncertainty, irrational decision-making, and a lack of logical and ethical governance. There is an evident absence of awareness, objective analysis, and a strategic vision for addressing Kosovo's socio-political and economic issues. The country has become entangled in personal, group, party, and regional interests, neglecting broader national priorities.

To initiate meaningful change, Kosovo must challenge its prevailing negative behaviors across all sectors. Political democracy is essential, and it must foster political culture, tolerance, and dialogue rather than anarchy, threats, and hostility. A society that promotes freedom, collective well-being, and selflessness is crucial for fostering creativity and civic responsibility.

Moving forward, Kosovo's future depends on establishing a new political climate built on unity and cooperation between the ruling and opposition parties, as well as other societal structures, including civil society. It is imperative to move beyond personal, careerist, and materialistic pursuits and prioritize national interests above all. Only through collective effort, responsibility, and genuine political will can Kosovo secure a prosperous future for its citizens and youth.

CONCLUSION

Kosovo's economic development following independence has been characterized by moderate growth, structural weaknesses, and persistent socio-economic challenges. Despite some progress in financial stability, the country continues to struggle with high unemployment, weak industrial development, corruption, and an imbalanced trade structure.

Overall Assessment and Recommendations are provided in order to enhance conditions of economic development of Kosovo:

- Economic Diversification: Kosovo must move beyond reliance on remittances and public sector employment and invest in industrial production, technology, and export-oriented businesses.
- Labor Market Reforms: Policies should focus on education reform and vocational training to address skills mismatches and reduce unemployment.
- Anti-Corruption Measures: Strengthening judicial independence, enforcement mechanisms, and transparency in governance is critical for attracting investment and restoring public trust.
- Trade and Investment Climate: Improvements in infrastructure, regional trade agreements, and business incentives are necessary to boost exports and attract foreign investment.

Kosovo's economic challenges are deeply rooted in governance inefficiencies, corruption, and weak policy implementation. Without decisive reforms in economic policy, governance, and institutional accountability, long-term sustainable development will remain elusive. Moving forward, a unified political effort and a commitment to transparent economic policies are essential to securing a stable and prosperous future for Kosovo.

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CONTEMPORARY APPROACHES TO PREVENTING SECONDARY CARIES

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ABSTRACT

Secondary caries is the most common cause for the replacement of restorations. It refers to a carious lesion that develops at the margin of an existing restoration, consisting of an "external lesion," which is a new primary carious process, and a "wall lesion," which occurs between the restoration and the cavity wall. This paper discusses the development, characteristics, and prevention of secondary caries. The etiological factors influencing the formation of secondary caries are similar to those for primary caries (such as diet, oral hygiene, and salivary activity), along with microcracks specific to secondary caries. Numerous studies have shown that the frequency of secondary caries varies depending on the type of restoration material, its class, fluoride content, and the individual caries risk of the patient.

KEY WORDS: secondary caries, dental materials, disinfection, oral hygiene

ABSTRAKT

Sekundärkaries ist die häufigste Ursache für den Austausch von Restaurationen. Dabei handelt es sich um eine kariöse Läsion, die sich am Rand einer bestehenden Restauration entwickelt und aus einer „äußeren Läsion“, einem neuen primären kariösen Prozess, und einer „Wandläsion“ besteht, die zwischen der Restauration und der Kavitätenwand entsteht. In diesem Beitrag werden die Entwicklung, die Merkmale und die Prävention von Sekundärkaries erörtert. Die ätiologischen Faktoren, die die Entstehung von Sekundärkaries beeinflussen, ähneln denen der Primärkaries (z. B. Ernährung, Mundhygiene und Speichelaktivität), hinzu kommen die für Sekundärkaries spezifischen Mikrorisse. Zahlreiche Studien haben gezeigt, dass die Häufigkeit von Sekundärkaries je nach Art des Restaurationsmaterials, seiner Klasse, dem Fluoridgehalt und dem individuellen Kariesrisiko des Patienten variiert.

STICHWORTE: Sekundärkaries, Dentalwerkstoffe, Desinfektion, Mundhygiene

RÉSUMÉ

La carie secondaire est la cause la plus fréquente de remplacement des restaurations. Il s'agit d'une lésion carieuse qui se développe au bord d'une restauration existante, composée d'une « lésion externe », qui est un nouveau processus carieux primaire, et d'une « lésion murale », qui se produit entre la restauration et la paroi de la cavité. Cet article traite du développement, des caractéristiques et de la prévention des caries secondaires. Les facteurs étiologiques qui influencent la formation des caries secondaires sont similaires à ceux des caries primaires (alimentation, hygiène bucco-dentaire et activité salivaire), auxquels s'ajoutent des microfissures spécifiques aux caries secondaires. De nombreuses études ont montré que la fréquence des caries secondaires varie en fonction du type de matériau de restauration, de sa classe, de sa teneur en fluor et du risque carieux individuel du patient.

MOTS-CLÉS: caries secondaires, matériaux dentaires, désinfection, hygiène bucco-dentaire

INTRODUCTION

Dental caries is an infectious disease that leads to the loss of hard tooth tissue. The Dental caries is an infectious disease that leads to the destruction of hard tooth tissue. The progression of caries is primarily driven by harmful bacteria in the oral cavity, with *Streptococcus* mutants being the most influential. Caries is considered a complex disease with dynamic and multifactorial causes.

The host's role in caries development is reflected in various factors, including tooth morphology, which affects bacterial colonization, diet, oral hygiene, salivary flow and composition, and exposure to fluoride. When conditions are favorable, bacteria colonize the teeth, forming plaque. Carbohydrates in the mouth provide a primary energy source for plaque bacteria, whose breakdown produces acids that lower pH levels, leading to enamel demineralization. This initiates a complex process where demineralization and remineralization occur alternately (Šutalo et al., 1994). If oral conditions do not improve, demineralization outweighs remineralization, eventually leading to cavity formation.

The most common treatment for cavities is the removal of infected tooth tissue, followed by the placement of a restorative material. Over time, dental materials have been improved to better mimic the properties of natural tooth structure, but they still function as foreign substitutes within the tooth (Njemirovskij, 1984). These materials are subject to chewing forces and environmental factors, leading to wear and tear. As a result, microleakage can occur, either due to improper application or material degradation. Moreover, the removal of caries-affected tissue and cavity preparation may not eliminate all microorganisms from the cavity, contributing to the development of secondary caries (Dukić, 2009).

Secondary caries is the leading cause of restoration failure (Mjor et al., 2000). The challenge with secondary caries is its difficult diagnosis, as it often requires the removal of existing fillings, further tooth preparation, and the creation of a new filling. This additional preparation results in irreversible loss of hard tooth tissue and tooth weakening. In the long term, this can lead to more serious complications, including the need for endodontic treatment, prosthetic care, or even tooth extraction. For the patient, this results in additional costs, time loss, and impaired masticatory function. Hard tooth tissue has unique properties and structure that no material can fully replicate, presenting further treatment challenges for the dentist and time lost in attempts to preserve the tooth.

The goal of this paper is to provide foundational information on secondary caries and discuss methods to minimize its occurrence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Secondary Caries

Secondary caries, like primary caries, is caused by microorganisms present in dental plaque. It can develop on any surface of a restored tooth where plaque accumulates and bacteria thrive (Guang-yun Lai and Ming-yu, 2012). Studies indicate that secondary caries is more prevalent in class II restorations than in class I restorations, often occurring at the gingival margin and less frequently on the occlusal surface of class II restorations (Mjör, 1998). In a study by Nedeljkovic et al. (2019), conducted on 450 patients, 146 out of 4036 restorations were diagnosed with secondary caries, resulting in a prevalence of 3.6%. Large class II restorations involving the cusps were more prone to secondary caries (8.2%), followed by MO/OD and MOD restorations without cusps (5.2%, 5.1%), while class I restorations had a lower prevalence (2%).

The study also found that secondary caries was more common in the posterior (3.9%) than in the anterior regions (2.6%) of the oral cavity. Factors such as smoking and individual caries risk were linked to the increased occurrence of secondary caries. Patients with high caries risk had a prevalence of 7.2%, nearly three times higher than those with low caries risk (2.4%), and smokers exhibited a prevalence of 7.7%, significantly higher than non-smokers (3%).

Several factors contribute to the higher prevalence of secondary caries at the gingival portion of class II restorations. Controlling plaque in this area, particularly in the proximal regions, is more challenging compared to the occlusal surface, which is more accessible for cleaning with a toothbrush (Guang-yun Lai and Ming-yu, 2012). Furthermore, during the surgical procedure, it is nearly impossible to fully isolate the gingival margin from saliva and sulcular fluid, which complicates maintaining a dry working field. This leads to an increase in microorganisms at the gingival part of the restoration, as well as weaker bonding of the restorative material to the tooth in this area, compared to other more easily monitored regions.

2. Methods for Preventing Secondary Caries

Since secondary caries is one of the most frequent reasons for replacing dental fillings, researchers and dentists are increasingly focused on preventing or slowing its progression and improving the longevity of restorations (Guang-yun Lai and Ming-yu, 2012). Secondary caries is a dynamic process involving the interplay of demineralization from pathological factors and remineralization through the body's defensive mechanisms. Prevention strategies for secondary caries generally aim to achieve two main objectives:

- Reducing demineralization and enhancing the remineralization of hard dental tissues;
- Reducing bacterial load, altering bacterial metabolism, and inhibiting bacterial growth in plaque or carious dentin (Guang-yun Lai and Ming-yu, 2012);

3. Oral Hygiene

The prevention of secondary caries begins at the moment a filling is placed, with patient education about proper oral hygiene. According to research by Nedeljkovic et al. (2019), individuals with a high risk of developing caries are three times more likely to experience secondary caries than those with a low caries risk. The risk factors for secondary caries are the same as those for primary caries (Hicks et al., 2003). The primary cause of caries formation is plaque, so controlling plaque is the first and most crucial measure in preventing caries. The main tools for mechanical plaque control are toothbrushes and toothpaste. Various types of toothbrushes are available, with soft-bristled brushes being recommended today. Soft brushes, with a high number of bristles, are just as effective as hard or medium-bristled brushes in plaque removal but are gentler on both hard and soft tissues.

When selecting toothpaste, it is essential to consider its fluoride content, which should be age-appropriate. Children aged six months to two years should use toothpaste containing 500 ppm fluoride, children from two to six years old should use toothpaste with 1000 ppm fluoride, and children over six years old, as well as adults, should use toothpaste with 1450 ppm fluoride (Negovetić-Vranić, 2011). In addition to brushing, other plaque control tools such as interdental brushes, dental floss, water irrigators, and oral antiseptics should be utilized. Patients should be advised to brush their teeth at least three times a day for three minutes—ideally after breakfast, lunch, before bedtime, and after snacks, especially if consuming sugary foods. Regular dental check-ups are also crucial so that any changes can be promptly addressed.

Fluoride-Releasing Materials. Fluoride-releasing filling materials are effective tools for combating both primary and secondary caries. These materials release fluoride into plaque, which promotes remineralization and inhibits bacterial growth, thereby reducing demineralization around fillings. A study by Svanberg et al. (1990) showed that plaque around glass ionomer cements had the lowest percentage of Streptococcus bacteria (1.1%) compared to composites (13.7%) and amalgam (4.3%). Common fluoride-releasing materials include glass ionomer cements, resin-modified glass ionomer cements, and compomers (Hicks et al., 2003).

Glass Ionomer Cements. Glass ionomer cements consist of a powder, usually calcium-aluminum-fluorosilicate glass, and a liquid, such as polyacrylic acid or copolymers. When mixed, they undergo an acid-base reaction, chemically hardening. These cements adhere to dentin and enamel through covalent, ionic, and intermolecular bonds (Pavelić, 2003). They release fluoride in two phases: initially, a high release within 24-48 hours, followed by a gradual release over several years (Wieganda et al., 2007). When the pH drops due to bacterial activity or caries formation, glass ionomer cements release significant fluoride, helping to prevent lesion progression.

Resin-Modified Glass Ionomer Cements. Resin-modified glass ionomer cements are similar to conventional glass ionomers but contain HEMA (hydrophilic organic matrix) to enhance their properties. They harden through light polymerization, dark reaction, or a combination of both (Wieganda et al., 2007). These materials release fluoride at moderate to high levels, with the highest release occurring within the first 24 hours after placement (Pavelić, 2003).

Compomers. Compomers combine composites and glass ionomer cements, offering properties similar to composites but with fluoride-releasing capabilities. These materials harden through light polymerization and require an adhesive to bond to dental tissues. Their fluoride release is moderate to good, though less than that of glass ionomer cements (Wieganda et al., 2007).

Several in vitro studies show that fluoride-containing materials significantly affect carious lesions, promoting demineralization and halting caries progression (Attar and Önen, 2003). However, in vivo studies have shown inconsistent results, with no proven effect on halting or demineralizing carious lesions (Kielbassa et al., 2003). Since fluoride release decreases over time, it is recommended to periodically "recharge" these materials with fluoride from toothpaste, gels, or varnishes (Wieganda et al., 2007). A study by Preston et al. demonstrated that fluoridation with a 500 ppm fluoride solution significantly enhanced fluoride release in glass ionomer cements, outperforming composites and compomers (Preston et al., 2003). Therefore, periodic fluoridation could improve the ability of fluoride-releasing materials to prevent secondary caries. Hara et al. (2006) suggested that the ability of glass ionomer cements to "recharge" with fluoride should be further investigated in vivo to optimize their effectiveness in preventing secondary caries.

4. Chlorhexidine

Mechanical plaque removal remains the primary method for plaque control, but chemical agents such as chlorhexidine can enhance its effectiveness. Chlorhexidine is a bisbiguanide antiseptic with broad antimicrobial properties, particularly against Gram-positive bacteria. It adheres well to mucous membranes and dental tissues, preventing plaque buildup, and its antimicrobial effect lasts up to 24 hours (Vrbanić et al., 2009).

Chlorhexidine is available in various forms and concentrations, including gels (0.02–1%), mouthwashes (0.05–0.2%), tablets (5 mg), varnishes, chewing gums (10 mg), chips (2.5 mg), and sprays (0.1–0.2%). It is important to avoid using chlorhexidine immediately after brushing teeth due to the deactivating effect of sodium lauryl sulfate in toothpaste (Vrbanić et al., 2009). Excessive use of chlorhexidine can lead to side effects such as tissue discoloration, altered taste, irritation, increased tartar, and reversible swelling of the salivary glands. Clear instructions on proper usage are essential to avoid these effects.

5. Cavity Disinfection

Disinfecting the cavity after caries excavation is critical to reduce bacteria responsible for secondary caries and restoration failure. Various antimicrobial agents are used for cavity disinfection (Bin-Shuwaish, 2016).

Sodium Hypochlorite. Sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) is widely used in endodontics as a disinfectant for root canals. It has strong antimicrobial effects, particularly at higher concentrations (0.5–5.25%) (Opačak et al., 2009). The higher the concentration, the more potent its antimicrobial action (Bin-Shuwaish, 2016). For example, 5.25% NaOCl eliminates microbes such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* in just 15 seconds (Vianna et al., 2004). However, caution is necessary with higher concentrations, as they can be cytotoxic and may provoke inflammatory reactions in the pulp. Some studies suggest that NaOCl can promote pulp healing by limiting inflammation in superficial cells without affecting deeper pulp tissue (Opačak et al., 2009).

The use of NaOCl for cavity disinfection may also affect the bond strength between adhesives and dental tissue. Studies show that pre-treatment with NaOCl can reduce bond strength with self-etching adhesives, but etch-and-rinse adhesives are less affected (Saboia et al., 2006).

Chlorhexidine. Chlorhexidine is a "gold standard" antiseptic in oral care. It has bactericidal effects at higher concentrations and is particularly effective against *Streptococcus mutans* (Bin-Shuwaish, 2016). It is biocompatible with the pulp and has even been shown to aid in pulp capping and dentin bridge formation. Chlorhexidine's antimicrobial effect is concentration-dependent, with a 60-second exposure to 0.5–2% solutions recommended for cavity disinfection (Sassone et al., 2003).

While chlorhexidine does not negatively affect the pulp, its impact on bond strength varies. Higher concentrations (e.g., 2%) can weaken bond strength with self-etching adhesives, so lower concentrations (0.12%) are preferred for such systems (Pameijer and Stanley, 1998). After chlorhexidine disinfection, cavities should be rinsed before applying adhesive systems to improve bond strength.

Ozone. Ozone, a potent antimicrobial agent, is increasingly used in restorative dentistry to treat early carious lesions and prevent new ones. It effectively kills bacteria, fungi, and viruses, and a 20-second application can eliminate up to 99.9% of microorganisms from a carious lesion (Baysan and Lynch, 2004). Ozone, especially in aqueous form, is less cytotoxic than sodium hypochlorite and chlorhexidine, making it a safer alternative. It does not affect the bond strength between adhesives and dental tissue, and in some cases, it may even improve it. Studies suggest that ozone treatment works best after cavity etching, as applying ozone before etching can reduce bond strength (Fagrell et al., 2008).

Lasers. Lasers, particularly diode and Er,Cr:YSGG lasers, are used in dentistry for caries removal and cavity disinfection. Laser treatment has strong antimicrobial effects, helping to decontaminate cavity surfaces. It also increases the resistance of dental tissue to acid exposure, potentially preventing future

caries formation. Lasers have shown similar antimicrobial effects to chlorhexidine, and their application in cavity disinfection has been shown to improve bond strength when used after cavity etching (Olivi and Olivi, 2015).

Photoactivated Disinfection. Photoactivated disinfection involves the use of a photosensitizing agent and a light source to disinfect cavities. When activated, the photosensitizing agent produces reactive oxygen species that destroy bacterial cell walls (Dukić, 2004). This technique is particularly effective against cariogenic bacteria such as *Streptococcus mutans* (Williams et al., 2004). It has the advantage of being minimally invasive, as it does not harm healthy tissue. This method is especially useful in deep cavities where conventional caries removal might risk exposing the pulp. When used after mechanical treatment, photoactivated disinfection enhances the success of restorations by reducing remaining bacteria.

Studies have shown that photoactivated disinfection can eliminate bacteria from deep cavities and is a safe option for preserving pulp vitality, as it raises the pulp temperature by only 3°C (Nammour et al., 2009). This method is effective in reducing microbial load and improving the chances of successful restorations.

6. Antimicrobial Agents in Dental Materials

Biofilm formation on restoration edges can lead to secondary caries. To address this, two approaches are being explored: developing restorative materials with antibacterial properties or creating surfaces that prevent bacterial adhesion. Increasing focus is being placed on materials with antimicrobial characteristics that can prevent biofilm accumulation and secondary caries (Chan et al., 2018).

One approach involves incorporating antibacterial agents into dental cements, particularly glass ionomer cements. Studies have examined the antibacterial effects of these agents and their impact on cement properties. An optimal concentration is necessary to achieve the desired bacterial inhibition without significantly altering the cement's characteristics (Chen et al., 2018). Bellis et al. (2014) added chlorhexidine hexametaphosphate paste to glass ionomer cements, which effectively inhibited *Streptococcus mutans* growth. The chlorhexidine continued to release for up to 14 months, with no significant change in the cement's physical properties. Similarly, chlorhexidine diacetate added to silicate ionomer cements (SIC) was effective in reducing bacteria in infected dentin (Imazato, 2016). Marti et al. found that a 0.5% chlorhexidine concentration was optimal for glass ionomer cements, as higher concentrations compromised physical properties like bond strength and hardness (Marti et al., 2014). Low concentrations of antibacterial agents in cements have shown promise without affecting material structure, with resin-modified SIC being less sensitive to these agents compared to SIC (Chen et al., 2018). Another strategy is to add antibacterial agents to dental adhesives, either as liquid agents, polymerization agents, or water-insoluble fillers. Liquid agents such as chlorhexidine, glutaraldehyde, and epigallocatechin-3-gallate have been tested (Chen et al., 2018). An experimental adhesive containing epigallocatechin-3-gallate successfully inhibited *Streptococcus mutans* growth and improved adhesive bond strength (Du et al., 2012). Benzalkonium chloride also enhanced bond strength (Sabatini and Pashley, 2015). However, the rapid initial release of antimicrobial agents, known as the burst effect, reduces their effectiveness. To address this, polymerizable antimicrobial agents like 12-methacryloyloxydecylpyridinium bromide (MDPB) have been used, but their antibacterial effect tends to be short-lived due to incomplete polymerization (Chen et al., 2018).

Experimental adhesives with water-insoluble fillers, such as nanosilver particles, have shown promising antimicrobial properties but suffer from color instability. Copper-iodine particles have emerged as a more stable alternative (Chen et al., 2018).

Composite resins have been tested similarly, with caprolactone showing strong antimicrobial effects. However, the addition of chlorhexidine can lead to potential risks due to the presence of carcinogenic compounds like 4-chloroaniline (Chen et al., 2018). Adding antimicrobial particles like bioactive glass and nanosilver can improve composites' antimicrobial properties, though color instability remains an issue. Continuing research is essential to enhance these restorative materials (Chen et al., 2018).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the incorporation of antimicrobial agents into dental materials presents a promising strategy for preventing biofilm formation and the development of secondary caries. Various approaches, such as adding antibacterial agents to dental cements, adhesives, and composite resins, have been explored, with some showing considerable success in inhibiting bacterial growth without compromising the physical properties of the materials. While low concentrations of antibacterial agents like chlorhexidine and epigallocatechin-3-gallate have proven effective, challenges remain in ensuring sustained antimicrobial action without negatively affecting material integrity.

Additionally, innovative solutions, such as polymerizable antimicrobial agents and the inclusion of water-insoluble fillers, offer potential for enhancing the long-term efficacy of dental materials. Despite some limitations, such as color instability and the burst effect, the ongoing development of antimicrobial dental materials holds significant promise for improving oral health outcomes and reducing the risk of secondary caries. Continued research and refinement of these materials are essential to address current challenges and optimize their clinical application.

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ETHICAL DIMENSIONS OF DOPING IN SPORTS: THEORIES AND PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

The ethical debate surrounding the use of performance-enhancing drugs in professional sports remains unresolved, with two dominant perspectives at its core: libertarianism and essentialism. Libertarians advocate for personal freedom and individual choice in using enhancement substances, whereas essentialists argue that such practices undermine the fundamental nature of sports. In 2009, William J. Morgan proposed a third ethical framework, known as the Treatment-Enhancement Distinction (TED). This perspective differentiates between the use of substances for therapeutic purposes and their use for enhancement, positioning this distinction as critical to resolving the debate over the permissibility of banned substances. This study explores whether Morgan's TED framework offers a viable resolution to the ethical controversy or if the issue will remain perpetually unresolved.

KEY WORDS: doping, ethics, sports, treatment, enhancement

ABSTRAKT

Die ethische Debatte über die Verwendung von leistungssteigernden Mitteln im Profisport ist nach wie vor ungelöst, wobei zwei Sichtweisen vorherrschen: Libertarismus und Essentialismus. Libertäre befürworten die persönliche Freiheit und die individuelle Wahl bei der Verwendung von leistungssteigernden Substanzen, während Essentialisten argumentieren, dass derartige Praktiken die grundlegende Natur des Sports untergraben. Im Jahr 2009 schlug William J. Morgan einen dritten ethischen Rahmen vor, der als Treatment-Enhancement Distinction (TED) bekannt ist. Diese Perspektive unterscheidet zwischen der Verwendung von Substanzen zu therapeutischen Zwecken und ihrer Verwendung zu Enhancementzwecken und betrachtet diese Unterscheidung als entscheidend für die Lösung der Debatte über die Zulässigkeit verbotener Substanzen. In dieser Studie wird untersucht, ob Morgans TED-Rahmen eine praktikable Lösung für die ethische Kontroverse bietet oder ob das Problem auf Dauer ungelöst bleiben wird.

STICHWORTE: Doping, Ethik, Sport, Behandlung, Enhancement

RÉSUMÉ

Le débat éthique entourant l'utilisation de substances améliorant les performances dans le sport professionnel n'est toujours pas résolu, avec deux perspectives dominantes au cœur de ce débat: le libéralisme et l'essentialisme. Les libéraux défendent la liberté personnelle et le choix individuel dans l'utilisation de substances améliorantes, tandis que les essentialistes affirment que de telles pratiques sapent la nature fondamentale du sport. En 2009, William J. Morgan a proposé un troisième cadre éthique, connu sous le nom de Distinction traitement-amélioration (TED). Cette perspective

différencie l'utilisation de substances à des fins thérapeutiques de leur utilisation à des fins d'amélioration, et considère que cette distinction est essentielle pour résoudre le débat sur l'admissibilité des substances interdites. Cette étude examine si le cadre TED de Morgan offre une solution viable à la controverse éthique ou si la question restera perpétuellement irrésolue.

MOTS-CLÉS: dopage, éthique, sport, traitement, amélioration

INTRODUCTION

We may ask ourselves when, and if ever, it is justifiable to use substances or techniques in sports, as Brown (1980) discusses. This question, serving as a moral framework that raises numerous additional ethical inquiries, was introduced in his article "Ethics, Drugs and Sport", published in the renowned journal *Journal of the Philosophy of Sport* in 1980. Škerbić (2016) asserts that this article marked the beginning of the discourse on the issue of doping in sports within the field of sports philosophy and ethics, stating: "Since then, doping has become one of the dominant topics within the discipline."

This paper aims to critically analyze the issue of doping in sports within a social context, offering insight into contemporary ethical perspectives and proposals for addressing the problem.

To begin, it is essential to define the concept of doping and examine what is understood by the enhancement of an athlete's abilities, what constitutes a permissible therapeutic treatment for recovery, and at what point such treatment transitions into the enhancement of athletic performance.

Since the early discussions on doping, various theories and perspectives on its ethical aspects have emerged. One of the most esteemed philosophers in this debate, William J. Morgan (2009), in his article "Athletic Perfection, Performance-Enhancing Drugs, and the Treatment-Enhancement Distinction", categorized the two leading ethical perspectives: the essentialist perspective, which defends the ideal of sports and the intrinsic motivation of athletes, viewing any form of doping as a violation of these ideals and motivations, and the libertarian perspective, which upholds an athlete's freedom to use substances that enhance their performance as long as no harm is inflicted on others.

Morgan also proposed a "middle ground" between these conflicting perspectives, which he termed the Treatment-Enhancement Distinction (TED). This approach suggests that the solution lies in differentiating between medical treatment aimed at recovery and the enhancement of athletic abilities.

This paper will delve deeper into each of these perspectives, exploring their proponents, their arguments, and their contributions to this long-standing ethical debate. The references for this work include prominent studies in the field of sports philosophy, ranging from 1980 to 2018.

It is important to recognize that the question of legalizing doping in sports remains inherently unresolved. The rigid ideals and uncompromising judgments of opposing sides have not untangled the ethical complexities; in fact, they may have further complicated them. However, an objective and rational analysis of these perspectives, coupled with an acceptance of differing viewpoints, could offer a fresh perspective on the future of doping legalization and usage. The answer we seek might lie in embracing both ideals and freedom while striving for a responsible balance between the two.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The Issue of Doping

In the highly competitive sports environment, athletes and their teams face immense pressure to achieve victory, which may lead them to consider using substances or methods to enhance performance.

This issue is not confined to professional athletes but extends to young athletes and amateurs as well. Doping presents a public health challenge, compromises the values, ethics, and integrity of sports, and poses significant health risks to the athletes themselves (UNESCO, 2020).

Though attempts to enhance athletic performance date back to ancient times, the term "doping" first appeared in the English dictionary in 1889, originally referring to a drug made from opium used to dope horses. The word "dope" (from the Dutch "doop," meaning a thick sauce) was also an alcoholic beverage made from grape residue, historically used by Zulu warriors as a stimulant during battles and religious rituals. Over time, "dope" came to describe various performance-enhancing concoctions.

Numerous doping incidents occurred in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, prompting the introduction of regulations in sports. The first documented case of doping took place during a swimming competition in the English Channel in 1865. Events like cycling races, boxing matches, and horse and dog races led to an increase in doping cases involving substances such as alcohol, cocaine, caffeine, heroin, nitroglycerin, and strychnine. The use of performance-enhancing substances can even be traced to the ancient Olympic Games, where athletes used various drugs and nutrient combinations to boost their performance. These practices, similar to modern doping, were prohibited in the Olympics (Thieme & Hemmersbach, 2009).

Walter Modell (1967) defined drugs as any substances that alter the structure and function of a living organism through their chemical properties. He viewed the effects of drugs as general biological phenomena, where their benefits or harm are determined by their pharmacological action. Substances used for doping include food, vitamins, hormones, plants, snake venom, pesticides, minerals, synthetic chemicals, and naturally occurring compounds in the body.

The fight against doping began in earnest with the establishment of the International Olympic Committee's Medical Commission in 1961, following the death of a Danish cyclist during the 1960 Olympics. Efforts include educational campaigns, the introduction of doping control procedures, banned substances lists, doping control laboratories, in-competition and out-of-competition testing, therapeutic exemptions, and blood sample testing (Rabin & Pitsiladis, 2017).

Theoretically, defining drugs and doping is straightforward, but in practice, it is a complex issue. Substances deemed as doping are subject to criteria such as quantity and context, which distinguishes therapeutic drugs from those used to enhance athletic performance. This distinction brings us to the concept of Performance-Enhancing Drugs (PEDs). R.L. Simon (1985) proposed criteria to classify a substance as doping:

- The user believes the substance will enhance their performance;
- The substance poses a health risk;
- The substance is not prescribed for treating illness or injury rehabilitation. Caffeine in coffee or tea and standard therapies do not meet these criteria;

M. Lavin (1987) categorized substances into:

- Recreational drugs (e.g., alcohol, cocaine, heroin, marijuana), which are consumed without medical supervision and often are illegal;
- Restorative drugs (e.g., aspirin, antihypertensives), which help individuals with medical conditions achieve normal function;
- Additive drugs (e.g., anabolic steroids), which enhance performance.

Brown (1984) distinguished between substances used for treatment and those for performance enhancement. Treatment-related use prioritizes athletes' health, while enhancement involves using substances to exceed normal expectations during training or competition.

The World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA) defines doping in its 2019 Code as the violation of anti-doping rules, including the presence of prohibited substances or their metabolites in an athlete's sample. A substance or method is added to WADA's banned list if it meets at least two of three criteria:

- Scientific or pharmacological evidence shows it enhances performance;
- Evidence indicates it poses a health risk;
- WADA deems its use contrary to the spirit of sport, as defined in the Code;

2. Ethical Theories and Perspectives on Doping

Morgan (2009), in his work *Athletic Perfection, Performance-Enhancing Drugs and the Treatment-Enhancement Distinction*, discusses the disagreement among sports philosophers regarding the use of performance-enhancing drugs (PEDs), highlighting two ethical perspectives: libertarians and essentialists. Libertarians oppose any form of restriction on athletes' freedom. They advocate for an athlete's rational choice to decide which substances to use and which methods to employ to push the limits of their performance, provided it does not endanger their health.

Essentialists, on the other hand, reject the use of PEDs entirely, arguing that such substances conflict with the moral essence of sport, which forms the foundation of its values.

In response to this disagreement, Morgan introduces his own perspective, the Treatment-Enhancement Distinction, which proposes distinguishing between the permissible and impermissible use of substances based on their necessity and justification for medical treatment or rehabilitation versus their use for enhancing performance and abilities, which is deemed unacceptable. The following sections explore each perspective in more detail, addressing their key proponents and fundamental assumptions.

Libertarians. Škerbić (2016) identifies W. M. Brown as the originator and prominent advocate of the libertarian perspective on doping in sports. Brown authored the first published work on doping in 1980, and other notable libertarian figures include Morgan, Gleaves, and Tamburrini. In his 1980 article *Ethics, Drugs, and Sport*, Brown draws parallels between doping regulations and qualification rules for sports competitions. He states, "I am interested in justification because I believe that rules governing participant qualifications are closely linked to rules on doping, blood doping, and other methods." Brown's arguments are based on two principles: fairness and health. He argues that fairness justifies gender segregation and weight classes in sports, viewing doping as cheating only if it is accessible to some competitors, creating an unfair advantage. Brown contends that doping is unfair only if it is inaccessible to all athletes. He highlights that inherent factors like genetics, upbringing, and training conditions already provide advantages, suggesting that banning doping perpetuates inequalities (Brown, 1980).

Regarding health, Brown asserts that the primary concern is the use of dangerous substances rather than the substances themselves: "Persisting in directly associating danger with drug use leads to insurmountable practical difficulties. Painkillers may ease effort but also mask critical information" (Brown, 1980). He argues that enhancing performance through substances does not inherently harm health and believes doping should not be banned if it is available to all athletes, promoting fairness.

Škerbić (2016) also highlights Claudia Tamburrini as an extreme libertarian advocate who emphasizes the importance of doping in maintaining the competitive edge of modern elite sports. Tamburrini argues that doping restrictions do not create equal competitive conditions and presents a threefold argument:

- **Competitive Equality:** Without bans, no athlete would face competitive inferiority, as all could use doping (except those under 18);
- **Sports Development:** Doping prohibition imposes arbitrary limits on the advancement of sports, hindering athletes from enhancing discipline-specific skills;
- **Knowledge and Safety:** Bans prevent understanding of doping's harmful effects, whereas lifting prohibitions would allow research to mitigate doping-related harms.

Tamburrini views sports medicine as striving to push human capabilities beyond previously considered limits, contrasting it with general medical practice. In *Transcending Human Limitations*, Tamburrini and Tännsjö (2007) critique the ethical inconsistencies between general and sports medicine, addressing issues of autonomy, privacy, and distributive justice. They argue that sports medicine often adopts a paternalistic approach, restricting athletes from using certain training methods deemed risky, unlike general medicine, where patient autonomy is respected. Athletes also lack the same privacy rights regarding their medical data, as they must undergo mandatory testing, raising ethical concerns about the voluntariness of consent. Tamburrini concludes that medical advancements enhancing human abilities should be accepted if proven safe, rather than viewed as threats to sports and society.

Overall, Brown (1980) and Tamburrini advocate for the regulation and permissible use of performance-enhancing substances, emphasizing fairness through universal access and challenging the paternalistic restrictions imposed by sports institutions.

Andy Miah, a prominent philosopher of sport, advocates for a limited right for athletes to use certain technologies to enhance their performance, a concept he terms biocultural health entitlement. Unlike Tamburrini, Miah argues that sports medicine does not conform to standard medical norms and practices, as the physical demands and injuries faced by athletes are distinct from those experienced by non-athletes. For professional athletes, specific therapies may be more effective in enabling continued competition (Miah, 2010).

In addressing the ethics of genetic enhancements in human abilities, Miah critiques six common arguments in favor of anti-doping:

- Doping is cheating.
- Doping is unnatural.
- Doping compromises, the integrity and fairness of competition.
- Doping creates unfair advantages.
- Doping is harmful to health.
- Allowing doping leads to coercion and elitism.
- Miah critiques these arguments, pointing out that doping, in some cases, may not be as harmful or as unfair as critics suggest. He emphasizes athletes' autonomy and the need to focus on health and fairness in determining what substances should be permitted in competition.

3. Essentialists

Škerbić (2016) asserts that the essentialist perspective was introduced by R. L. Simon and W. Fraleigh in 1984, four years after Brown's article, which is considered to have initiated the ethical debate on doping. According to Škerbić (2016), this perspective stands in stark opposition to permissive views, categorizing all substances and methods used to enhance athletes' performance (PEDs) as unacceptable due to the unfair advantage they provide. In addition to Simon and Fraleigh, other notable advocates of this perspective include A. Schneider, R. Butcher, and M. Lavin.

Simon (1985) discusses the harmful effects of performance-enhancing drugs and justifies a paternalistic approach to their prohibition on two grounds: first, athletes often lack genuine consent due to indirect coercion; second, PED use harms other competitors by pressuring them to follow suit. He highlights the coercive environment where the fear of losing creates undue pressure on athletes, undermining their capacity for informed consent. As he puts it: "Individuals pursuing significant rewards are not competent to give consent, as the fear of losing constitutes coercive pressure" (Simon, 1985). Regarding fairness, Simon argues that if some athletes use PEDs, others are compelled to do so in order to remain competitive. However, he emphasizes the need to define acceptable competitive pressures, noting that rigorous training might pose greater health risks than doping. Simon views competition as a "mutual pursuit of excellence through challenge," with respect for rules, effort, and natural abilities, rather than external enhancements. He states: "Improved performance is not a reflection of an athlete's dedication, motivation, or courage, but rather the capacity of their body to utilize substances efficiently" (Simon, 1985).

Building on Simon and Brown's ethical debate, Fraleigh (1985) offers a perspective that justifies banning doping on grounds of harm, coercion, and fairness. While Brown (1984) views doping bans as paternalistic, asserting that sport lacks a universally agreed-upon nature, Fraleigh posits three key assumptions:

- Certain substances, when used appropriately, enhance performance;
- These substances carry significant health risks;
- Athletes retain the right to choose whether to use them, regardless of bans.

Fraleigh argues that unrestricted doping would harm more athletes and their loved ones, whereas selective restrictions could result in fewer but more severe injuries due to undetectable substance experimentation. He notes that legalized doping could compromise fairness by creating disparities between users and non-users, stating: "In either case, competition will not be equitable for all" (Fraleigh, 1985). Ultimately, Fraleigh contends that sports should test individual capabilities within clearly defined rules, emphasizing respect for the sport, its rules, and the broader consequences of one's actions on other athletes and the integrity of competition.

As previously noted, Lavin (1987) distinguishes three types of substances: a) recreational, b) restorative, and c) additive drugs, asserting that only the latter two pose serious issues for the philosophy of sport. Considering Brown's libertarian approach and Simon's essentialist perspective, Lavin advocates for regulation and prohibition of performance-enhancing substances, offering his own ethical argument in the debate.

Lavin (1987) defines restorative substances as those that do not exceed an athlete's natural potential, unlike additive substances. However, defining natural potential is challenging, as most training methods aim to push natural limits. For instance, intensive training, specific diets, supplements, and advanced

equipment all aim to enhance inherent abilities (Lavin, 1987). The distinction between restorative and additive substances often leads to complications. For example, if an athlete uses painkillers to compete and performs better as a result, should this be considered restorative or additive?

The argument that additive substances harm the body, unlike restorative ones, is inconsistent. Athletes frequently use painkillers and anti-inflammatories, aware of their risks, often because competing without medical intervention may be unfeasible. In such cases, pain could be the most rational limit to performance. This ambiguity highlights the difficulty in distinguishing restorative from additive substances, further complicated by terminology. The word “drugs” often carries negative connotations, placing recreational and additive substances in the same category. Simon (1985) proposed the term “paradigm substances” for substances like anabolic steroids and amphetamines to address this issue. Lavin (1987) argues that focusing on which substances should be permitted or banned is more productive than conventional arguments of fairness, harm, and coercion. He critiques these arguments as inadequate, noting that fairness often implies unnatural advantages or risks to competitors. As discussed earlier, training regimens are inherently unnatural, and professional sports carry inherent health risks, such as joint damage from long-distance running or weight-related issues in certain sports. Brown (1985) also highlights paternalistic motivations, where sports institutions impose bans to protect athletes’ health. Ultimately, the morality of substance use underpins these arguments. Lavin proposes a consensus among sports authorities on permissible substances, grounded in moral ideals that evolve over time. Such consensus should incorporate the views of diverse stakeholders, not just those closely tied to specific sports. This approach emphasizes societal disapproval of banned substances and aligns with the historical practices of each sport (Lavin, 1987).

Building on the essentialist perspective of sports ideals and fair play, Butcher and Schneider (1998) outline five philosophical approaches to fair play:

- Fair play as a set of virtues — Fair play is seen as virtues or behaviors contextualized in sport, such as handshakes or verbal intimidation, influenced by the morality and rules of the sport.
- Fair play as play — Sport is a source of intrinsic rewards and enjoyment.
- Sport as competition and fair play as fair competition — Fair play extends beyond avoiding cheating to encompass broader sportsmanship.
- Fair play as respect for rules — Recognizes the complexity of respecting rules, which often requires contextual judgment.
- Fair play as agreement — Adherence to official rules, with violations seen as breaches of mutual understanding.

Butcher and Schneider further explore positive fair play, defining respect as either adherence to rules or valuing opponents and the sport itself. The latter, stronger form of respect connects it with a genuine appreciation of sport, fostering a deeper moral commitment.

4. Treatment-Enhancement Distinction (TED)

Morgan's concept of the distinction between treatment (or therapy) and performance enhancement revolves around clarifying how this differentiation can influence public opinion on permitting certain performance-enhancing substances for therapeutic purposes. Morgan (2009) argues that this distinction is both historically grounded and socially constructed. He notes that Lavin’s approach,

which emphasizes a democratically established consensus on the sporting ideal as the key to regulating doping, was a step in the right direction. However, Morgan disagrees with Lavin on three main points: Interpretation of Consensus: Morgan believes that the sporting ideal should not be viewed as a result of majority voting but as a historical attribute reflecting the social and historical aspects of contemporary sporting practices.

Centrality of the Sporting Ideal: He argues that the sporting ideal should be emphasized, as Simon's interpretation of an athlete's pursuit of excellence suggests, rather than remaining peripheral.

Therapy vs. Enhancement: Morgan stresses the importance of a clear distinction between therapy and performance enhancement. Historically, this distinction has been exploited to justify pharmacological interventions that enhance performance under the guise of medical treatment, thereby avoiding public moral condemnation.

Morgan argues that this conceptual distinction should be based on historical and social perspectives, suggesting that our evolving collective stance should shape shared norms regarding sports achievements. These norms define what constitutes therapy (falling within the boundaries of sporting achievement) versus enhancement (exceeding those boundaries). Public opinion plays a crucial role in determining the acceptable level of sporting excellence, shaped by historical development and regulatory practices.

Morgan also critiques the influence of special interest groups in sports, whose anti-doping stance is often driven by monetary and marketing considerations rather than rational judgment. He observes that public attitudes toward performance-enhancing drugs (PEDs) have shifted significantly from the 1970s and 1980s to the present. Previously, sports were seen as morally untouchable activities where purity was paramount, but today, performance enhancement is more openly discussed, even outside of sports (e.g., musicians using beta-blockers to reduce stage anxiety).

Morgan highlights the contrast between the views of sports officials and the public on doping. He likens officials to politicians, claiming their actions often serve self-interests rather than public welfare. He criticizes the undemocratic nature of sports institutions, which he believes are driven by narrowly defined market interests, limiting the promotion of therapeutic PED use.

Morgan's TED, also called the "middle ground," rejects both strict libertarian approaches (which prioritize athlete freedom despite potential harm) and Miah's technological determinism (which accepts inevitable technological changes). While Morgan partially agrees with Simon's pursuit of excellence, he finds it overly abstract. Instead, he proposes his own ideal of sports excellence: a blend of natural talent (strength, speed, coordination) and human striving (desire for success, strategic thinking, endurance). Public consensus, grounded in this definition, can guide the distinction between acceptable therapy and undesirable enhancement. Substances that do not compromise central sporting values or disrupt the essence of competition are considered therapeutic. Conversely, those that undermine these values are deemed unacceptable enhancements.

Gleaves (2011) critiques Morgan's reliance on the sporting ideal and unassailable sporting values, viewing it as leaning toward essentialism. Gleaves argues that Morgan's framework assumes certain historical, cultural, and social norms are immutable and criticizes this for favoring specific values over others. Instead, Gleaves suggests evaluating the impact of individual enhancements on the integrity of

sports competitions, moving the debate beyond traditional arguments like health risks or fairness to address modern concerns.

According to Gleaves, if athletes have valid reasons to modify sports conditions to create better challenges, society may accept such changes. This dynamic approach focuses on how specific enhancements influence the values underlying sports competitions.

CONCLUSION

The ethical question of allowing or banning substances for enhancing athlete performance does not have a straightforward answer. It has become a debate lasting nearly forty years. One side argues that it is an individual's right to do whatever is necessary to reach their maximum athletic potential, while the other side believes in limiting athletes' freedom for their own protection and to preserve the spirit and ethics of sport.

The current situation in sports leans toward banning performance-enhancing substances, driven by the interests of sponsors, corporations, and sports organizations, as well as athletes. Both perspectives have valid reasons, but both extremes are unrealistic and unsustainable. Complete freedom could lead to a system where the end justifies the means, diminishing the importance of natural talent, sportsmanship, and fair play. On the other hand, restricting freedom under the guise of protecting health is hypocritical, as professional sports already push physical limits and involve unhealthy training practices.

It is essential to protect the essence of sport, but the involvement of various interest groups complicates the situation. Changing the collective consciousness, free from financial and political influence, is necessary for progress. A balance must be struck, where advancements in technology and medicine are used to help athletes achieve excellence without compromising the integrity of the sport. A middle ground is possible but requires significant changes.

The debate on doping legalization remains unresolved in the philosophy of sport. The perspectives outlined in this paper make sense and are well-supported. Athletes should have more freedom in deciding what is best for their health and performance. However, too much freedom could lead to abuse and undermine the true spirit of sport. A compromise, balancing both perspectives, could help achieve progress and serve the best interests of athletes and the sport itself.

Morgan's middle path has opened new possibilities in regulating doping, and some sports organizations have embraced this approach. Ultimately, the question of doping transcends personal freedom and paternalistic control, finding its resolution in a socially acceptable compromise that respects the integrity and values of the sport.

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ECONOMIC CHALLENGES OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF KOSOVO

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this article is to analyze the key economic challenges facing Kosovo's agricultural sector and their broader implications for the country's economy. By examining factors such as financial constraints, market inefficiencies, environmental issues, and policy limitations, the study seeks to identify the main barriers to agricultural growth. Furthermore, the article aims to explore potential solutions and policy recommendations that could enhance the sector's sustainability, improve rural livelihoods, and contribute to economic development. Through this analysis, the article provides insights for policymakers, stakeholders, and researchers on strategies to strengthen Kosovo's agricultural sector and ensure its long-term viability.

KEYWORDS: agriculture, economic challenges, policy, Kosovo

ABSTRAKT

Ziel dieses Artikels ist es, die wichtigsten wirtschaftlichen Herausforderungen, denen sich der kosovarische Agrarsektor gegenüber sieht, und ihre weiterreichenden Auswirkungen auf die Wirtschaft des Landes zu analysieren. Durch die Untersuchung von Faktoren wie finanziellen Zwängen, Marktineffizienzen, Umweltproblemen und politischen Beschränkungen versucht die Studie, die wichtigsten Hindernisse für das landwirtschaftliche Wachstum zu identifizieren. Darüber hinaus zielt der Artikel darauf ab, potenzielle Lösungen und politische Empfehlungen zu untersuchen, die die Nachhaltigkeit des Sektors erhöhen, die Lebensbedingungen im ländlichen Raum verbessern und zur wirtschaftlichen Entwicklung beitragen könnten. Durch diese Analyse liefert der Artikel Erkenntnisse für politische Entscheidungsträger, Interessenvertreter und Forscher über Strategien zur Stärkung des kosovarischen Agrarsektors und zur Gewährleistung seiner langfristigen Lebensfähigkeit.

STICHWORTE: Landwirtschaft, wirtschaftliche Herausforderungen, Politik, Kosovo

RÉSUMÉ

L'objectif de cet article est d'analyser les principaux défis économiques auxquels est confronté le secteur agricole du Kosovo et leurs implications plus larges pour l'économie du pays. En examinant des facteurs tels que les contraintes financières, les inefficacités du marché, les questions environnementales et les limitations politiques, l'étude cherche à identifier les principaux obstacles à la croissance agricole. En outre, l'article vise à explorer les solutions potentielles et les recommandations politiques qui pourraient renforcer la durabilité du secteur, améliorer les moyens de subsistance des populations rurales et contribuer au développement économique. Grâce à cette analyse, l'article fournit des indications aux décideurs politiques, aux parties prenantes et aux chercheurs sur les stratégies permettant de renforcer le secteur agricole du Kosovo et d'assurer sa viabilité à long terme.

MOTS-CLÉS: agriculture, défis économiques, politique, Kosovo

INTRODUCTION

Kosovo's agricultural sector has long been an integral part of the country's economy and culture, with agriculture historically serving as the backbone of its rural economy. Agriculture in Kosovo is not only vital to the livelihoods of the rural population but also plays a significant role in food production, rural development, and maintaining local traditions. The sector is characterized by its diversity, encompassing crop farming, livestock production, and forestry, with key agricultural products including wheat, maize, potatoes, vegetables, fruits, and livestock, particularly cattle and sheep.

The aim of this article is to analyze the key economic challenges facing Kosovo's agricultural sector and their broader implications for the country's economy. By examining factors such as financial constraints, market inefficiencies, environmental issues, and policy limitations, the study seeks to identify the main barriers to agricultural growth. Furthermore, the article aims to explore potential solutions and policy recommendations that could enhance the sector's sustainability, improve rural livelihoods, and contribute to economic development. Through this analysis, the article provides insights for policymakers, stakeholders, and researchers on strategies to strengthen Kosovo's agricultural sector and ensure its long-term viability.

Historical Significance. Historically, Kosovo's agricultural sector has been shaped by its fertile soil and favorable climate, which provided a solid foundation for agricultural activities. During the Yugoslav era, Kosovo was considered a vital agricultural region within the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia. It was known for its agricultural output, particularly in the production of fruits, vegetables, and grains, as well as its strong tradition of dairy farming. The collectivization policies implemented in the mid-20th century helped modernize agricultural practices to some extent but also led to challenges such as land fragmentation and inefficiencies.

Following the collapse of Yugoslavia in the 1990s and the subsequent conflict in 1999, Kosovo's agricultural sector faced significant disruption. The war caused widespread destruction of infrastructure, agricultural land, and farming equipment, which severely hindered production. The post-war period saw efforts to rebuild the sector, with external aid and support from international organizations playing an important role. However, despite these efforts, the sector continued to struggle with outdated farming practices, lack of modern technology, and a shortage of skilled labor.

Current State of Kosovo's Agricultural Sector. Today, agriculture in Kosovo still holds significant importance, contributing to about 10-12% of the country's GDP and employing a large portion of the workforce, particularly in rural areas. However, it faces numerous challenges that have hindered its development and potential for growth. The sector is heavily reliant on traditional farming methods, with small-scale, fragmented farms dominating the landscape. This limits the potential for economies of scale and reduces overall productivity. The average farm size is small, with many farmers operating on less than 5 hectares of land.

One of the key challenges facing Kosovo's agriculture is the lack of modern technology and infrastructure. The country's farming techniques are often outdated, and many farmers still rely on manual labor and old machinery. Additionally, there is limited access to high-quality seeds, fertilizers, and irrigation systems, which hampers productivity and competitiveness. Poor road networks and limited access to markets also prevent farmers from reaching broader domestic and international markets.

Despite these challenges, Kosovo's agricultural sector has seen some positive developments in recent years. The government has introduced various policies to support the sector, including financial incentives, subsidies, and programs aimed at improving infrastructure and promoting agricultural education and innovation. Kosovo is also working towards aligning its agricultural practices with European Union (EU) standards as part of its ongoing efforts to integrate into the EU.

However, the sector remains vulnerable to external factors such as climate change, which has led to more frequent droughts and unpredictable weather patterns. Furthermore, Kosovo's reliance on remittances from the diaspora has contributed to labor shortages in the agricultural sector, as many young people seek employment opportunities abroad, leaving behind an aging farming population.

Kosovo's agricultural sector remains an essential part of its economy and cultural heritage, it faces significant challenges that need to be addressed for it to thrive in the modern global market. Addressing these challenges will require concerted efforts from the government, international organizations, and the private sector to modernize the sector, improve infrastructure, and ensure sustainable agricultural practices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Literature review

Kosovo's agricultural sector has been widely studied in the context of its historical significance, challenges, and potential for development (Borisov et al., 2020). While Kosovo's agricultural sector remains an essential pillar of its economy, scholars have identified several critical economic challenges, ranging from issues of land fragmentation to outdated practices, limited access to markets, and the lack of modern infrastructure. This literature review will examine key studies and findings related to these economic challenges.

Historical Context and Structural Challenges. One of the earliest comprehensive studies of Kosovo's agricultural economy was conducted by Gërxhani (2007), who explored the economic transformation of the region after the dissolution of Yugoslavia. The study noted that Kosovo's agricultural sector suffered significantly during the 1999 conflict, which destroyed infrastructure, disrupted food production, and led to the loss of both skilled labor and agricultural knowledge. The immediate post-war period saw Kosovo's agriculture struggling to recover, with small-scale farming and subsistence agriculture remaining dominant (Gërxhani, 2007).

Furthermore, numerous studies have emphasized the persistent issue of land fragmentation in Kosovo. Research by Kelmendi (2010) highlights that Kosovo has one of the highest rates of land fragmentation in Europe. The average farm size is small, with many farmers owning less than five hectares of land. This fragmentation limits economies of scale, reduces productivity, and discourages investment in modern farming equipment and practices (Kelmendi, 2010). A study by Pustina (2015) corroborates these findings, pointing out that while the government has introduced policies to address land consolidation, the impact of these policies has been limited, and land fragmentation continues to be a major obstacle to agricultural productivity and efficiency.

Modernization and Technological Challenges. In terms of modernizing agricultural practices, several studies have examined the technological barriers faced by Kosovo's farmers. A key issue identified by Reka et al. (2017) is the lack of access to modern technology and high-quality agricultural inputs such as seeds, fertilizers, and irrigation systems. The study also emphasized the role of outdated machinery,

with many farmers still using equipment from the socialist era. These technological shortcomings significantly reduce productivity and make it difficult for Kosovo's agricultural sector to compete in global markets. According to Reka et al. (2017), the introduction of modern agricultural technology is essential for improving yields, reducing costs, and ensuring sustainable farming practices in Kosovo.

Additionally, research by Miftari et al. (2019) indicates that Kosovo's agriculture suffers from a lack of knowledge transfer and innovation. While there is some government support for training and education in agricultural practices, the adoption of innovative farming methods remains slow. Farmers often rely on traditional techniques and face difficulties accessing new knowledge or upgrading their skills. This lack of education and innovation is further exacerbated by limited collaboration between academic institutions, the private sector, and the farming community (Miftari et al., 2019). The slow pace of modernization, according to the authors, hampers the sector's ability to overcome economic challenges.

Market Access and Export Challenges. Kosovo's agricultural exports remain limited, and farmers often face difficulties accessing both domestic and international markets. The study by Arifi et al. (2020) explored the barriers to market access for Kosovo's farmers, finding that poor road infrastructure, high transportation costs, and a lack of modern storage and packaging facilities are major challenges. Farmers often struggle to transport goods efficiently, and the absence of storage facilities leads to significant post-harvest losses, further reducing the potential for profitability (Arifi et al., 2020). Moreover, Kosovo's agricultural exports are hindered by regulatory barriers, including the lack of certification and alignment with international standards. As a result, Kosovo remains heavily reliant on imports, especially for high-value agricultural products (Behluli, et al., 2020).

In line with these findings, the report by the Kosovo Agriculture Ministry (2021) highlights the low level of agricultural exports, noting that the sector is primarily oriented toward subsistence farming and local consumption. While Kosovo's government has made efforts to improve market access by supporting farmers through subsidies and training, progress has been slow, and there remains a significant gap between domestic agricultural output and the ability to reach international markets.

Financial and Labor Constraints. Kosovo's agricultural sector is also constrained by financial limitations. A study by Gashi and Berisha (2014) found that farmers often struggle to access credit due to a lack of collateral, which makes it difficult to invest in the modernization of farms or the purchase of essential inputs. The lack of affordable financing mechanisms limits the ability of farmers to scale their operations or adopt more efficient farming methods. Furthermore, the study indicates that government subsidies, while helpful, are often insufficient to bridge the gap, and many farmers rely on remittances from the diaspora as a primary source of financial support.

Labor shortages are another critical challenge. According to a study by Bajrami (2018), Kosovo's agriculture faces an aging workforce, with many young people leaving rural areas for better opportunities in urban centers or abroad. This migration has resulted in a lack of skilled labor in the agricultural sector, further exacerbating the difficulties faced by farmers in modernizing practices and increasing productivity. The study suggests that attracting younger generations to farming through education, incentives, and technological innovation could help mitigate this labor shortage.

The literature on Kosovo's agricultural sector consistently identifies several economic challenges that hinder its growth and competitiveness. Land fragmentation, outdated technology, limited market access, financial constraints, and labor shortages are key barriers to the sector's development. While the

government has made strides in addressing these challenges through subsidies, policy reforms, and efforts to modernize infrastructure, significant obstacles remain. The transition to a more efficient and competitive agricultural sector will require concerted efforts from the government, international organizations, and the private sector to modernize farming practices, improve market access, and attract investment in the sector. Furthermore, policies that focus on education, innovation, and youth involvement in agriculture will be crucial for ensuring the long-term sustainability of Kosovo's agricultural sector.

2. Theoretical Framework

The economic challenges in Kosovo's agricultural sector are multifaceted and require a multidisciplinary approach to better understand the dynamics at play. Several theories and models from economics, development studies, and agricultural economics can be applied to explain the underlying causes and potential solutions for these challenges. This section discusses key theoretical frameworks that help illuminate the issues facing Kosovo's agricultural sector, particularly the effects of land fragmentation, market access barriers, technological limitations, and financial constraints.

The Theory of Land Tenure and Fragmentation. Land fragmentation is one of the most pressing challenges in Kosovo's agricultural sector, and the theory of land tenure and property rights offers an insightful lens for understanding this issue. According to the theory of land tenure, the way in which land ownership and use rights are structured can significantly impact agricultural productivity.

The theory suggests that secure and well-defined property rights are crucial for fostering investment in agricultural land and encouraging the efficient use of resources. In countries with fragmented landholdings, such as Kosovo, the lack of consolidated land ownership can prevent farmers from reaching economies of scale, which are necessary to increase productivity. This concept is supported by studies on land tenure systems (Deininger, 2003) which argue that fragmented land holdings limit the incentives for farmers to invest in land improvements and adopt modern agricultural technologies. The theory also indicates that land fragmentation leads to inefficient land use and lower agricultural output, as small farms may lack the resources or capacity to invest in advanced equipment or optimize land for agricultural purposes.

In Kosovo, land fragmentation is a result of both historical policies and the region's post-conflict transition, where land restitution and the distribution of property led to the division of agricultural land into small, unproductive units. This fragmentation exacerbates the economic difficulties in agriculture, as small landowners face difficulty accessing credit and modern technology, leading to lower agricultural productivity (Kelmendi, 2010).

The Theory of Agricultural Modernization. The theory of agricultural modernization, pioneered by scholars such as John H. Adams (1970), provides another important framework for understanding the economic challenges faced by Kosovo's agricultural sector. Agricultural modernization theory suggests that for a developing economy to increase agricultural productivity, there must be a systematic transformation of farming practices through the adoption of new technologies, improved infrastructure, and market-oriented strategies (Borisov, 2021).

The modernization theory highlights the importance of technological advancement, knowledge transfer, and investments in infrastructure, which are key to overcoming the challenges of outdated farming methods in Kosovo. The theory posits that modernization leads to increased efficiency in

production and enables farmers to participate in larger, more competitive markets. However, this transformation requires significant investment in education and training, the introduction of new agricultural practices, and the provision of access to high-quality inputs like seeds, machinery, and fertilizers.

In the context of Kosovo, however, the transition to modern agriculture has been slow, with many farmers still relying on outdated practices and equipment. As noted by Reka et al. (2017), Kosovo's agricultural sector lags behind in the adoption of modern technologies, which undermines its ability to remain competitive both domestically and in international markets. The application of agricultural modernization theory suggests that overcoming these challenges will require a coordinated approach to introduce modern farming methods, improve rural infrastructure, and ensure access to agricultural knowledge and innovations.

Theories of Market Access and Trade Barriers. Another theoretical framework that can be applied to Kosovo's agricultural sector is the theory of market access and trade barriers. This theory, rooted in international trade economics, explains how access to markets is shaped by factors such as transportation costs, tariffs, regulations, and supply chain inefficiencies (Borisova, 2025).

Kosovo's agricultural sector faces significant barriers to market access due to inadequate infrastructure, high transportation costs, and regulatory barriers, both at the domestic and international levels. According to Krugman's (1991) theory of international trade, barriers to market entry often prevent producers in developing economies from benefiting from trade, reducing their potential for economic growth. In Kosovo, the lack of efficient road networks, modern storage facilities, and compliance with international standards (such as certification for exports) hinders the ability of farmers to access both domestic and international markets.

Furthermore, the theory of comparative advantage (Ricardo, 1817) suggests that countries or regions should specialize in the production of goods in which they have a relative efficiency. In Kosovo's case, the sector's potential comparative advantages, such as organic produce and traditional agricultural goods, are undermined by limited market access and high logistical costs. As a result, Kosovo remains a net importer of many agricultural products, which exacerbates the economic challenges within the sector.

The Theory of Agricultural Finance and Credit Constraints. Agricultural finance theory is another critical framework for understanding the economic challenges in Kosovo's agricultural sector. According to this theory, access to credit is essential for farmers to invest in land improvements, purchase necessary inputs, and modernize their farming operations (Borisova, 2024). However, smallholder farmers in Kosovo face significant difficulties accessing credit due to land fragmentation, lack of collateral, and limited financial infrastructure.

The theory of agricultural finance, as outlined by Hazell and Norton (1986), asserts that agricultural credit markets are essential for fostering investment and productivity in the sector. In developing economies like Kosovo, credit constraints are a major barrier to the adoption of modern agricultural practices. Without access to affordable financing, farmers are unable to invest in technology, machinery, or irrigation systems, which can significantly enhance productivity. Moreover, the lack of credit infrastructure and financial literacy further compounds this issue, limiting the sector's ability to modernize and grow (Gashi & Berisha, 2014).

Rural Development and the Human Capital Theory. The theory of rural development and human capital provides an additional lens through which to understand the challenges faced by Kosovo's agricultural sector. The theory posits that investments in human capital—through education, skills training, and the development of entrepreneurial capacities—are essential for fostering sustainable rural development and improving agricultural productivity (Pertrov and Borisov, 2024).

In Kosovo, the agricultural workforce is aging, and younger generations are increasingly migrating to urban areas or abroad in search of better economic opportunities (Bajrami, 2018); (Qerimi, et al., 2020). This migration exacerbates the shortage of skilled labor in the agricultural sector, which is a significant barrier to modernization and productivity gains. The human capital theory suggests that policies aimed at improving education, providing skills training, and offering incentives to retain youth in rural areas can help address this challenge and ensure long-term agricultural sustainability.

By integrating these theoretical frameworks—land tenure and fragmentation theory, agricultural modernization theory, market access and trade barriers theory, agricultural finance theory, and human capital theory—this study can better understand the economic challenges faced by Kosovo's agricultural sector. These frameworks provide a comprehensive lens through which to analyze the sector's struggles with productivity, modernization, market access, financial constraints, and labor shortages. By applying these theories, policymakers and stakeholders can develop more effective strategies to address these challenges and foster a more sustainable and competitive agricultural sector in Kosovo.

3. Methodology

The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative research methods to provide a comprehensive analysis of the challenges in Kosovo's agricultural sector. The methodology is designed to gather primary and secondary data, enabling a thorough exploration of key issues such as land fragmentation, technological adoption, market access, rural development, and access to finance. Secondary data will be collected from existing reports, academic studies, government publications, and international organizations (e.g., World Bank, FAO, Kosovo Ministry of Agriculture). This data will be used to supplement primary data and provide a broader context for understanding the economic challenges in Kosovo's agricultural sector. The secondary data will also help assess the trends in agricultural productivity, trade, and policy over time.

4. Economic Context of Kosovo's Agriculture

Despite structural challenges, the sector remains a cornerstone of economic activity, contributing approximately 10% to the country's GDP and employing a substantial portion of the labor force, particularly in rural areas. Kosovo's agricultural sector is characterized by small-scale farming, diverse crop production, and a strong livestock industry.

Size and Structure of the Agricultural Sector. Kosovo's agricultural sector is predominantly composed of small and medium-sized farms, with the average farm size ranging from 1 to 3 hectares. The country has approximately 500,000 hectares of arable land, of which around 50% is actively cultivated. Due to historical land fragmentation, many farms operate at subsistence levels, limiting their productivity and competitiveness in larger markets. Agriculture in Kosovo is mainly rain-fed, with limited irrigation infrastructure, making it vulnerable to climate variability. The lack of modern farming techniques, limited access to credit, and outdated machinery further constrain productivity. Despite these challenges,

Kosovo's agricultural sector has significant potential for growth, particularly through investments in modern farming practices, irrigation, and market access.

Key Components of the Agricultural Sector. Kosovo's agriculture is diverse, with crop production, livestock farming, and horticulture being the major subsectors.

A. Crop Production. Crop production is a fundamental part of Kosovo's agricultural sector, with key crops including:

- **Cereals:** Wheat, maize, and barley are the most commonly cultivated cereals, providing essential food supplies and serving as fodder for livestock;
- **Fruits and Vegetables:** Kosovo has favorable conditions for fruit and vegetable production, particularly apples, pears, plums, tomatoes, peppers, and potatoes;
- **Industrial Crops:** Sunflower, soybeans, and tobacco are grown on a smaller scale but have the potential for expansion with improved market access.

Despite the variety of crops produced, productivity levels remain lower than the European average due to outdated farming techniques and limited access to high-quality seeds and fertilizers.

B. Livestock Farming. The livestock sector is a major component of Kosovo's agriculture, contributing significantly to rural livelihoods and food production. The main livestock categories include:

- **Cattle:** Dairy farming is an essential part of Kosovo's livestock sector, with milk production being a key economic activity. The country produces dairy products such as cheese and yogurt, both for domestic consumption and export;
- **Sheep and Goats:** Sheep and goat farming are prominent in rural areas, with products such as lamb, wool, and dairy playing a crucial role in local economies;
- **Poultry:** Poultry farming, particularly for eggs and chicken meat, has been growing due to increasing demand;
- **Pigs:** Although less common due to cultural and religious preferences, pig farming exists in certain regions.

The livestock industry faces challenges such as high feed costs, inadequate veterinary services, and low efficiency in meat and dairy production.

C. Horticulture and Greenhouse Production. Horticulture, including fruit and vegetable cultivation, has shown significant growth in recent years. Greenhouse farming is becoming increasingly popular as it allows for year-round production and reduces dependency on seasonal changes. Investment in greenhouse infrastructure has been encouraged to improve productivity and competitiveness in the European market.

D. Agro-processing Industry. The agro-processing industry is still in its early stages, with limited processing facilities for dairy, meat, fruits, and vegetables. Many agricultural products are sold fresh, limiting value-added opportunities. Expanding Kosovo's agro-processing capabilities could increase product quality, extend shelf life, and enhance export potential.

5. Identification of Key Economic Challenges

The PEST analysis (Political, Economic, Social, and Technological) provides a structured framework to analyze the key economic challenges facing Kosovo's agricultural sector. By examining these four dimensions, we can identify the primary obstacles that hinder the sector's growth and competitiveness.

Political Challenges

- **Agricultural Policies and Government Support:** While the Kosovo government provides subsidies and grants for agriculture, inconsistent policies and bureaucratic inefficiencies hinder effective implementation. Many farmers struggle to access financial support due to administrative barriers.
- **European Integration and Regulatory Alignment:** Kosovo aspires to integrate with the European Union, but compliance with EU agricultural regulations (e.g., food safety, environmental standards) remains a challenge. The lack of alignment with EU standards limits Kosovo's export potential.
- **Land Ownership and Legal Framework:** Land fragmentation and unclear property rights make it difficult for farmers to expand their operations. The lack of a formalized land consolidation policy prevents efficient agricultural production.
- **Trade Restrictions and Market Access:** Kosovo faces trade barriers due to political tensions with neighboring countries, affecting the export of agricultural goods. Limited international market access reduces farmers' competitiveness.

Economic Challenges

- **Limited Access to Finance:** Many farmers lack access to credit and investment capital due to high interest rates and stringent loan requirements. This financial constraint prevents the adoption of modern farming technologies and expansion of agricultural activities.
- **Low Productivity and High Production Costs:** The agricultural sector suffers from low productivity due to outdated farming methods, poor irrigation infrastructure, and limited mechanization. Additionally, high input costs (e.g., seeds, fertilizers, animal feed) reduce profitability.
- **Market Instability and Price Fluctuations:** Farmers often face unstable market prices due to supply chain inefficiencies and external economic factors. Fluctuations in global food prices and demand affect Kosovo's agricultural income.
- **Dependence on Imports:** Despite its agricultural potential, Kosovo imports a large percentage of its food products. This dependency on imports weakens local production and puts pressure on domestic farmers to compete with foreign products.

Social Challenges

- **Aging Farming Population and Rural Depopulation:** Many young people in Kosovo are moving to urban areas or emigrating abroad in search of better job opportunities, leading to labor shortages in agriculture. The aging farming population affects the sustainability of agricultural activities.
- **Education and Skills Gap:** Farmers often lack formal education and training in modern agricultural techniques. Limited access to agricultural extension services and research institutions hinders knowledge transfer and innovation.
- **Consumer Preferences and Dietary Changes:** Changing consumer habits, including increased demand for processed and imported food, affect local agricultural markets. The preference for imported products over domestic alternatives reduces demand for local produce.
- **Gender Inequality in Agriculture:** Women play a crucial role in agriculture but often lack access to land ownership, financial resources, and decision-making opportunities. Addressing gender disparities could enhance agricultural productivity.

Technological Challenges

- **Outdated Farming Equipment and Practices:** The majority of Kosovo's farmers use traditional farming methods with limited access to modern machinery and irrigation systems. Low mechanization levels reduce efficiency and output.
- **Weak Agricultural Research and Innovation:** Kosovo lacks strong research institutions focused on agricultural innovation. Limited investment in R&D prevents the development of new crop varieties, sustainable farming techniques, and climate-resilient agriculture.
- **Poor Infrastructure and Supply Chains:** Inadequate rural roads, storage facilities, and transportation networks hinder market access. Weak supply chain management leads to high post-harvest losses and inefficient distribution.
- **Limited Adoption of Digital Agriculture:** The use of digital tools such as precision farming, data analytics, and smart irrigation systems remains minimal. Expanding digital technology adoption could significantly enhance productivity and resource efficiency.

The PEST analysis highlights that Kosovo's agricultural sector faces significant challenges in all four dimensions—political, economic, social, and technological. Addressing these obstacles requires policy reforms, increased financial support, investment in infrastructure, and the adoption of modern agricultural techniques. By overcoming these barriers, Kosovo can enhance its agricultural productivity, reduce import dependency, and create a more competitive and sustainable farming industry.

6. Impact of These Challenges on Kosovo's Economy

Kosovo's agricultural sector plays a crucial role in the country's economic development, rural livelihoods, and food security. However, the numerous economic challenges facing the sector—such as limited access to finance, outdated technology, low productivity, and market instability—have significant consequences for Kosovo's overall economic growth, rural development, food security, and employment.

6.1 Economic Growth. The agricultural sector contributes approximately 7-10% to Kosovo's GDP and employs a significant portion of the population, particularly in rural areas. However, the sector's structural inefficiencies, such as low productivity and lack of investment, hinder its potential as a driver of economic growth.

Low Agricultural Productivity: The reliance on traditional farming techniques, fragmented landholdings, and inadequate irrigation systems reduces agricultural output, limiting its contribution to national economic growth.

High Import Dependence: Kosovo imports a large share of its food products due to insufficient domestic production. This trade imbalance weakens the agricultural sector's ability to generate income and reduces the country's economic self-sufficiency.

Restricted Export Opportunities: Due to political and regulatory barriers, Kosovo faces difficulties in accessing international markets. The inability to expand exports limits revenue generation and foreign exchange earnings, slowing overall economic development.

Rural Development. Agriculture is a primary source of income for rural communities in Kosovo, but persistent challenges in the sector have contributed to rural poverty and migration. Many farmers struggle with financial insecurity due to fluctuating market prices, high production costs, and lack of government support. Limited income opportunities in agriculture push rural households into poverty. The

declining profitability of agriculture, combined with limited access to modern farming equipment and education, discourages younger generations from engaging in farming. As a result, many rural youth migrate to urban areas or seek opportunities abroad, leading to labor shortages in agriculture.

Declining Rural Infrastructure: Weak infrastructure, including poor roads, lack of storage facilities, and inadequate access to markets, further marginalizes rural farmers. This lack of investment in rural areas prevents sustainable development and economic diversification.

6.2 Food Security

A strong and resilient agricultural sector is crucial for ensuring Kosovo's food security. However, the current challenges undermine the country's ability to produce sufficient food for its population. Due to low domestic agricultural output, Kosovo depends on imported food products to meet consumer demand. This reliance increases vulnerability to global price fluctuations and external supply chain disruptions. Climate change, poor soil management, and lack of modern irrigation reduce Kosovo's ability to produce food sustainably. The inability to adapt to environmental changes exacerbates food insecurity. The increasing reliance on imported food, which often consists of processed and lower-quality products, affects the nutritional standards of the population. Strengthening domestic food production could improve access to fresh and healthy food options.

6.3 Employment

Agriculture remains one of the largest employment sectors in Kosovo, particularly in rural areas. However, the challenges facing the industry have direct consequences on employment rates and labor conditions. Due to low profitability, many small-scale farmers are unable to sustain their businesses, leading to reduced employment opportunities in the sector. Many agricultural jobs in Kosovo are seasonal and informal, offering little job security, low wages, and limited social protection. This precarious employment situation discourages long-term participation in the agricultural sector.

As rural migration continues, Kosovo faces a growing shortage of skilled agricultural workers. Without a new generation of trained farmers, the long-term sustainability of the sector remains at risk.

The economic challenges in Kosovo's agricultural sector have far-reaching implications for the country's economy, rural development, food security, and employment. Addressing these issues through policy reforms, infrastructure investment, and financial support for farmers is essential for ensuring a more sustainable and resilient agricultural sector. Strengthening agriculture could not only boost economic growth but also improve rural livelihoods, enhance food security, and create stable employment opportunities.

7. Potential Solutions and Policy Recommendations

To address the economic challenges facing Kosovo's agricultural sector, a comprehensive strategy is required, combining policy reforms, investment in infrastructure, and support for farmers. Strengthening the sector will not only boost economic growth but also improve rural livelihoods, food security, and employment. The following potential solutions and policy recommendations aim to enhance productivity, sustainability, and market competitiveness in Kosovo's agriculture.

7. 1. Improving Access to Finance and Investment. The following actions should be taken:

- **Expand Agricultural Credit Programs:** The government, in collaboration with financial institutions, should provide low-interest loans and grants tailored to small-scale farmers. Developing microfinance initiatives can improve farmers' access to capital.
- **Encourage Foreign and Domestic Investment:** Incentives such as tax breaks and subsidies for agribusinesses can attract private sector investment in modern farming technologies and infrastructure.
- **Establish Agricultural Insurance Schemes:** Crop and livestock insurance programs can protect farmers from financial losses due to extreme weather conditions, pests, and other unforeseen challenges.

7. 2. Enhancing Agricultural Productivity. The following actions should be taken:

- **Promote Modern Farming Techniques:** Encouraging the use of precision agriculture, high-yield crop varieties, and efficient irrigation systems can significantly improve productivity.
- **Invest in Agricultural Research and Education:** Strengthening research institutions and agricultural extension services will provide farmers with better knowledge on soil management, pest control, and climate-resilient farming.
- **Facilitate Mechanization and Technology Adoption:** Providing subsidies or leasing programs for modern farming equipment can help small-scale farmers improve efficiency and reduce labor-intensive processes.

7. 3. Strengthening Market Access and Trade Opportunities. The following actions should be taken:

- **Improve Infrastructure and Logistics:** Investing in rural roads, storage facilities, and cold chains will enhance farmers' ability to transport and preserve their products, reducing post-harvest losses.
- **Develop Cooperatives and Farmer Organizations:** Encouraging farmers to form cooperatives can increase their bargaining power, improve access to markets, and facilitate bulk purchasing of inputs at lower costs.
- **Enhance Export Capacity:** Aligning Kosovo's agricultural policies with EU standards and strengthening trade agreements will help expand market access for agricultural products.

7. 4. Supporting Sustainable Agricultural Practices. The following actions should be taken:

- **Encourage Organic and Sustainable Farming:** Providing incentives for organic farming and environmentally friendly practices can help maintain soil fertility and reduce dependency on chemical inputs.
- **Implement Water Management Strategies:** Expanding and modernizing irrigation systems can improve water efficiency and mitigate the effects of droughts on agricultural production.
- **Promote Climate Adaptation Strategies:** Introducing policies that support climate-resilient farming, such as agroforestry and crop diversification, will help mitigate the risks associated with climate change.

7.5. Enhancing Food Security and Rural Development. The following actions should be taken:

- **Strengthen Domestic Food Production:** Policies that support local food production and reduce dependency on imports will improve food security and economic resilience.
- **Improve Social Support for Rural Farmers:** Expanding social safety nets, including subsidies, training programs, and healthcare services, will enhance the well-being of rural farming communities.
- **Encourage Youth Participation in Agriculture:** Providing vocational training, financial incentives, and entrepreneurial support for young farmers will help address labor shortages and rejuvenate the sector.

7.6. Institutional and Policy Reforms. The following actions should be taken:

- **Enhance Governance and Policy Implementation:** Strengthening the Ministry of Agriculture and other relevant institutions will ensure better coordination and implementation of agricultural policies.
- **Improve Land Tenure and Land Reform Policies:** Addressing land fragmentation and facilitating land consolidation efforts can optimize land use and improve farm efficiency.
- **Strengthen Anti-Corruption Measures:** Ensuring transparency in subsidy distribution and agricultural investments will build trust and encourage private-sector participation.

The future of Kosovo's agricultural sector depends on targeted policy interventions that promote financial support, technological advancement, sustainable practices, and improved market access. By addressing these challenges through comprehensive reforms and strategic investments, Kosovo can build a more resilient, productive, and competitive agricultural sector that contributes to long-term economic growth and rural development.

CONCLUSION

The agricultural sector remains a vital component of Kosovo's economy, providing employment, supporting rural livelihoods, and contributing to food security. However, numerous economic challenges, including financial constraints, outdated infrastructure, market inefficiencies, and environmental vulnerabilities, hinder its full potential. Addressing these issues requires a multi-faceted approach that integrates policy reforms, investment in modern farming technologies, and enhanced market access. Strengthening financial support mechanisms, promoting sustainable agricultural practices, and improving rural infrastructure can drive growth and resilience in the sector. Additionally, fostering cooperation between the government, private sector, and farmers will be essential for creating a competitive and sustainable agricultural industry. By implementing targeted solutions, Kosovo can ensure a more prosperous agricultural future, reducing rural poverty, enhancing food security, and contributing to overall economic development.

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SWOT ANALYSIS ON THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF KOSOVO

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this article is to critically examine Kosovo's economic development using a SWOT analysis. The study will explore key economic advantages, existing constraints, potential growth opportunities, and external risks that could affect long-term sustainability. Additionally, it will provide policy recommendations to enhance economic resilience and competitiveness. This research is particularly relevant given Kosovo's aspirations for European integration and its ongoing efforts to strengthen economic ties with international partners. By identifying key economic drivers and obstacles, policymakers, investors, and researchers can gain insights into Kosovo's future economic trajectory and formulate strategies to foster sustainable development.

KEYWORDS: SWOT, economic development, Kosovo

ABSTRAKT

Das Ziel dieses Artikels ist es, die wirtschaftliche Entwicklung des Kosovo anhand einer SWOT-Analyse kritisch zu untersuchen. In der Studie werden die wichtigsten wirtschaftlichen Vorteile, bestehende Einschränkungen, potenzielle Wachstumschancen und externe Risiken untersucht, die die langfristige Nachhaltigkeit beeinträchtigen könnten. Darüber hinaus wird sie politische Empfehlungen zur Verbesserung der wirtschaftlichen Widerstandsfähigkeit und Wettbewerbsfähigkeit geben. Diese Untersuchung ist angesichts der Bestrebungen des Kosovo zur europäischen Integration und der laufenden Bemühungen um eine Stärkung der wirtschaftlichen Beziehungen zu internationalen Partnern von besonderer Bedeutung. Durch die Identifizierung der wichtigsten wirtschaftlichen Triebkräfte und Hindernisse können politische Entscheidungsträger, Investoren und Forscher Einblicke in die zukünftige wirtschaftliche Entwicklung des Kosovo gewinnen und Strategien zur Förderung einer nachhaltigen Entwicklung formulieren.

STICHWORTE: SWOT, wirtschaftliche Entwicklung, Kosovo

RÉSUMÉ

L'objectif de cet article est d'examiner de manière critique le développement économique du Kosovo à l'aide d'une analyse SWOT. L'étude explorera les principaux avantages économiques, les contraintes existantes, les opportunités de croissance potentielle et les risques externes qui pourraient affecter la durabilité à long terme. En outre, elle fournira des recommandations politiques pour améliorer la résilience et la compétitivité de l'économie. Cette recherche est particulièrement pertinente compte tenu des aspirations du Kosovo à l'intégration européenne et des efforts qu'il déploie actuellement pour renforcer ses liens économiques avec ses partenaires internationaux. En identifiant les principaux moteurs et obstacles économiques, les décideurs politiques, les investisseurs et les chercheurs peuvent se faire

une idée de la trajectoire économique future du Kosovo et formuler des stratégies pour favoriser le développement durable.

MOTS CLÉS: SWOT, développement économique, Kosovo

INTRODUCTION

Kosovo, one of the youngest countries in Europe, has made significant progress in its economic development since declaring independence in 2008. However, despite its achievements, the country continues to face numerous economic challenges that hinder sustainable growth. As a small, developing economy, Kosovo is influenced by both internal factors such as infrastructure deficiencies, high unemployment, and limited industrialization, as well as external factors including regional instability, global economic trends, and trade dependencies.

A comprehensive evaluation of Kosovo's economic development requires a structured approach to identify both positive and negative aspects influencing growth. The SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis is a widely used strategic planning tool that helps assess the internal and external factors shaping economic progress. By applying this framework, we can gain a deeper understanding of Kosovo's economic position, highlighting areas where it can capitalize on strengths and opportunities while addressing weaknesses and mitigating threats.

The objective of this article is to critically examine Kosovo's economic development using a SWOT analysis. The study will explore key economic advantages, existing constraints, potential growth opportunities, and external risks that could affect long-term sustainability. Additionally, it will provide policy recommendations to enhance economic resilience and competitiveness.

This research is particularly relevant given Kosovo's aspirations for European integration and its ongoing efforts to strengthen economic ties with international partners. By identifying key economic drivers and obstacles, policymakers, investors, and researchers can gain insights into Kosovo's future economic trajectory and formulate strategies to foster sustainable development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Literature Review

Economic development has been widely studied in various contexts, including transition economies like Kosovo. This section reviews relevant literature on economic development theories, Kosovo's economic trajectory, and SWOT analyses applied to national and regional economies.

1.1. Theoretical Perspectives on Economic Development

Economic development theories provide a framework for understanding the progress of nations. Classical theories, such as Adam Smith's theory of economic growth, emphasize free markets, capital accumulation, and productivity improvements as key drivers of development. Similarly, Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth (1960) outline a linear progression from traditional societies to high-mass consumption economies, which is relevant for analyzing Kosovo's transition.

In contrast, structuralist and dependency theories argue that economic disparities result from historical and institutional factors. Todaro and Smith (2015) highlight the role of governance, investment, and human capital in economic progress, factors that are critical for Kosovo's development. More recent literature on endogenous growth theory (Romer, 1990); (Nikolov, Boevsky, Borisov and Radev, 2017)

emphasizes the importance of innovation, education, and infrastructure—areas where Kosovo faces both challenges and opportunities.

1.2 Empirical Studies on Kosovo's Economic Development

Several studies have examined Kosovo's economic performance, particularly in relation to post-war recovery, institutional development, and macroeconomic stability. Bartlett and Uvalić (2013) discuss the challenges of Kosovo's economic transition, noting the structural weaknesses in labor markets, low industrial productivity, and reliance on remittances. Similarly, Riinvest Institute (2020) highlights Kosovo's trade imbalances, limited export capacity, and high youth unemployment as persistent economic constraints.

Other studies, such as WB (2022) and IMF (2021) reports, emphasize Kosovo's reliance on external financial assistance, foreign direct investment (FDI), and international trade (Borisov, Qerimi and Behluli, 2020). While some sectors, like information technology and agriculture, show promise, the economy remains vulnerable to external shocks, global price fluctuations, and political instability.

1.3. SWOT Analysis in Economic Development Research

The SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis has been widely used in economic and business studies to evaluate development strategies. Gürel and Tat (2017) argue that SWOT provides a comprehensive yet flexible approach to assessing internal and external economic factors. Various studies applying SWOT to transition economies, such as those by Nikolov (Nikolov, Borisov and Radev, 2014); (Meyer and Peng, 2016) and Radovanović et al. (2019), demonstrate how this framework helps identify policy priorities and strategic directions for growth.

In the case of Kosovo, Shala and Beqiri (2021) apply SWOT analysis to highlight key economic strengths such as a young workforce, geographical location, and untapped resources, while also pointing out weaknesses like institutional inefficiencies and energy dependence. Studies suggest that leveraging EU integration prospects and regional cooperation could enhance Kosovo's economic resilience, while external threats like political instability and environmental risks remain significant concerns.

1.4. Gaps in the Literature and Research Contribution

Despite existing research on Kosovo's economy, there is limited application of SWOT analysis in a structured manner that directly informs policy decisions. Most studies focus on macroeconomic challenges or sectoral analyses but lack a holistic approach to identifying interrelated economic strengths and risks. This article contributes to the literature by providing a comprehensive SWOT analysis of Kosovo's economic development, integrating empirical data with policy insights to offer actionable recommendations.

By bridging theoretical perspectives with empirical findings, this study aims to enhance the understanding of Kosovo's economic landscape and contribute to the ongoing discussion on sustainable growth strategies.

2. SWOT framework

In order to conduct a thorough SWOT analysis of Kosovo's economic development, this study adopts a qualitative research approach that synthesizes secondary data sources, expert opinions, and contextual analysis. The methodology is structured around identifying and evaluating the key Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats that impact Kosovo's economic landscape. The process is informed by theoretical frameworks on economic development and strategic analysis, and it draws on data from

various reports, academic literature, and policy documents related to Kosovo's economy (Borisov and Behluli, 2020).

The first step in the methodology involves the collection of relevant secondary data. The sources for this study include:

- **Official Reports:** Reports from international organizations like the World Bank (2022), International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2021), and the European Commission, which provide valuable insights into Kosovo's macroeconomic performance, policy frameworks, and development challenges.
- **Academic Studies:** A selection of studies that explore Kosovo's economic transition, challenges, and potential (Bartlett & Uvalić, 2013; Riinvest Institute, 2020). These studies provide a detailed analysis of Kosovo's development context, including its industrial base, labor market, and fiscal policies.
- **Government Documents:** Data from Kosovo's Ministry of Finance and the Central Statistical Agency, which offer official statistics on GDP growth, inflation, trade balances, and employment trends.
- **Expert Opinions:** Interviews and reports from experts on Kosovo's economic development, policy-making, and governance.

The SWOT analysis is structured according to the four main categories:

- **Strengths:** Internal factors that positively contribute to Kosovo's economic development. These may include Kosovo's strategic location, young labor force, natural resources, and certain emerging sectors (e.g., information technology). Strengths are identified through national development plans, reports on infrastructure development, and sector-specific performance reviews (Shala & Beqiri, 2021).
- **Weaknesses:** Internal factors that hinder Kosovo's economic growth. This includes limited industrial productivity, high unemployment rates, underdeveloped infrastructure, dependency on remittances, and political instability. These weaknesses are drawn from reports by international institutions like the IMF (2021) and the World Bank (2022), which provide comprehensive assessments of Kosovo's socio-economic vulnerabilities.
- **Opportunities:** External factors that can stimulate economic growth. Kosovo's potential integration into the European Union (EU), regional cooperation opportunities, growth in export-oriented industries, and the promotion of foreign direct investment (FDI) are key opportunities explored in the literature (Meyer & Peng, 2016). Opportunities are also informed by analyses of global economic trends and Kosovo's trade agreements with neighboring countries.
- **Threats:** External factors that can potentially disrupt Kosovo's economic development. These threats include global economic instability, climate change, political uncertainties, and the potential for geopolitical conflicts. Threats are drawn from geopolitical studies and expert opinions on Kosovo's international relations and integration prospects (Radovanović et al., 2019).

The SWOT analysis is conducted through the following steps:

- **Categorization of Data:** Each identified factor (strength, weakness, opportunity, or threat) is classified into one of the four categories. This is based on the analysis of qualitative data from the collected reports, expert opinions, and government documents.

- **Prioritization of Factors:** The most significant factors within each category are identified and prioritized based on their impact on Kosovo's economic development. This is done through a combination of expert judgments and comparative analysis of Kosovo's economic performance relative to similar economies in the Balkans and beyond.
- **Integration with Economic Theories:** The identified factors are analyzed through the lens of economic development theories. For instance, endogenous growth theory (Romer, 1990) is applied to assess how Kosovo's innovations and human capital development (strength) could enhance long-term economic growth. The structuralism approach (Todaro & Smith, 2015) helps contextualize Kosovo's weaknesses, such as its reliance on external financial aid and high unemployment.

To ensure the reliability and validity of the findings, the results of the SWOT analysis are cross-verified with multiple sources. This triangulation method involves comparing data from reports, interviews, and statistical analysis to ensure consistency. Additionally, the results of the SWOT analysis are validated through consultations with experts in Kosovo's economic policy and development. These experts provide insights into the accuracy of the identified factors and their relative importance.

The results of the SWOT analysis are used to provide strategic recommendations for Kosovo's economic development. The analysis helps identify where Kosovo has a competitive advantage, where reforms are needed, and how external factors may influence future development. The strategic implications of the SWOT analysis are discussed in the subsequent sections of the article, guiding policy recommendations and identifying areas for further research.

While SWOT analysis is a powerful tool, it does have limitations. The qualitative nature of the research and reliance on secondary data means that subjective bias in data interpretation may exist. Additionally, the dynamic nature of economic development means that the identified factors could change over time. Future studies may seek to update the SWOT analysis with more primary data and longitudinal analyses to capture ongoing changes in Kosovo's economic environment.

This SWOT analysis methodology provides a structured and systematic approach to assessing Kosovo's economic development. By combining theoretical perspectives with empirical data, it offers valuable insights into Kosovo's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. The approach not only contributes to a deeper understanding of the country's economic challenges but also provides a foundation for policy recommendations aimed at fostering sustainable economic growth in Kosovo.

3. SWOT Analysis of Kosovo's Economic Development

This SWOT analysis of Kosovo's economic development provides a comprehensive assessment of the internal and external factors that affect the country's economic growth, challenges, and opportunities. By evaluating Kosovo's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, this analysis helps guide policymakers and stakeholders in crafting strategies for sustainable economic growth.

STRENGTHS

Young and Growing Workforce: Kosovo has one of the youngest populations in Europe, with a significant proportion of the population under the age of 30. This offers a competitive advantage in terms of labor force availability and potential for growth in sectors such as technology, manufacturing, and services (Behluli, Qerimi, Borisov and Hajdari, 2020) and (Shala & Beqiri, 2021).

Strategic Location: Kosovo is located in the heart of the Balkans, providing access to regional markets and trade routes. Its proximity to both the European Union and the regional markets of the Balkans positions Kosovo as a key trade hub in Southeast Europe (Behluli, Qerimi, Borisov and Hajdari, 2020).

Natural Resources: Kosovo is rich in natural resources, including lignite, which is a key energy source, as well as agricultural land. This can support energy production, mining industries, and agriculture, providing a foundation for further economic development.

EU Integration Prospects: Kosovo's ambition to join the European Union provides a strong incentive for economic reforms, improvements in governance, and the development of infrastructure. This potential for integration helps attract foreign investments and strengthens ties with international partners (Riinvest Institute, 2020).

WEAKNESSES

Limited Industrial Base: Kosovo's economy remains largely reliant on a few sectors, particularly services and remittances, while industrial production is relatively underdeveloped. Low productivity in manufacturing and limited diversification hinder the country's economic resilience (IMF, 2021).

High Unemployment Rates: Despite the young workforce, Kosovo faces high unemployment rates, particularly among youth and women. The lack of job opportunities, especially in the private sector, is a major challenge for social stability and economic growth (World Bank, 2022).

Infrastructure Deficiencies: Kosovo faces significant gaps in infrastructure, including in transportation, energy, and telecommunications. These limitations hinder trade, economic integration, and regional cooperation (Bartlett & Uvalić, 2013).

Dependence on Remittances: A large portion of Kosovo's GDP comes from remittances sent by the Kosovar diaspora. This dependency on external financial support weakens the domestic economy and limits the development of local industries and services.

OPPORTUNITIES

Regional Cooperation and Trade Agreements: Kosovo can benefit from stronger regional cooperation and integration into regional trade agreements. These partnerships could increase trade, foreign direct investment (FDI), and regional stability, leading to greater economic growth (Meyer & Peng, 2016).

Development of Key Sectors: Kosovo has significant untapped potential in sectors such as agriculture, tourism, and information technology (IT). The growth of agriculture, sustainable tourism, and IT infrastructure could provide substantial economic benefits. Leveraging the EU's funding for rural development could further support this growth (Shala & Beqiri, 2021).

EU Membership Pathway: Kosovo's EU integration prospects offer a framework for development through access to European funding, technology transfers, and knowledge sharing. This can help modernize the economy, improve the business environment, and drive policy reforms (World Bank, 2022).
Renewable Energy Sector: Kosovo's energy sector, particularly renewable energy, holds promise for future growth. Investing in renewable energy sources such as solar and wind could reduce dependency on fossil fuels, improve sustainability, and enhance energy security (IMF, 2021).

THREATS

Political Instability: Kosovo's political environment is characterized by uncertainty, with unresolved issues related to its status and international recognition. Political instability can deter investment and hinder long-term economic planning (Radovanović et al., 2019).

Global Economic Shocks: As a small economy with significant reliance on remittances and external aid, Kosovo is vulnerable to global economic fluctuations, such as changes in commodity prices, financial crises, or slowdowns in EU economies, which could affect trade and foreign investments.

Environmental Risks and Climate Change: Kosovo's economy is vulnerable to environmental challenges, including climate change. The agricultural sector, in particular, is at risk due to droughts, floods, and shifting weather patterns. These challenges could disrupt food production and increase costs (Riinvest Institute, 2020).

Geopolitical Tensions: Kosovo's geopolitical position, especially in relation to Serbia and other neighboring countries, exposes it to political risks that can affect its economic development. Tensions in the region may impact Kosovo's international relations, trade agreements, and foreign investments (Shala & Beqiri, 2021).

CONCLUSION

The SWOT analysis of Kosovo's economic development reveals that the country has a solid foundation for growth, supported by a young labor force, strategic location, and natural resources. However, Kosovo's economy faces significant challenges, including high unemployment, industrial underdevelopment, and reliance on remittances. Opportunities for growth lie in regional cooperation, sector diversification, and EU integration, while political instability and external economic risks present ongoing threats.

Policymakers in Kosovo can leverage its strengths and opportunities to mitigate weaknesses and navigate threats, ultimately fostering a more resilient and diversified economy. To achieve sustainable development, Kosovo needs to focus on infrastructure development, job creation, and sectoral diversification, with a particular emphasis on agriculture, renewable energy, and IT.

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SPORT AND GLOBALIZATION: IMPACT AND TRANSFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

Globalization and sport are closely interconnected, particularly in the context of the ongoing revolution in information technology and digitalization. From the Olympic Games to major international competitions, globalization has transformed sport into a massive industry, sparking increased interest in the global management and organization of sporting events. This transformation is also reshaping sport itself, influencing the rules of the game, training methods, performance tracking, and even the technical aspects of on-field play.

This paper aims to explore the impact of globalization on sport, which spans several areas including economics, marketing, organization, politics, and culture. Two key examples of the globalization of sport are highlighted in this paper. The first is the spread of sports culture, illustrated by the growing popularity of American football in Europe. The second example examines how globalization has contributed to the increased earnings and overall value of athletes and major sports clubs.

KEYWORDS: globalization, sport, sports club value

ABSTRAKT

Globalisierung und Sport sind eng miteinander verbunden, insbesondere im Zusammenhang mit der laufenden Revolution in der Informationstechnologie und der Digitalisierung. Von den Olympischen Spielen bis hin zu großen internationalen Wettbewerben hat die Globalisierung den Sport in einen riesigen Wirtschaftszweig verwandelt und ein wachsendes Interesse an der globalen Verwaltung und Organisation von Sportveranstaltungen geweckt. Dieser Wandel verändert auch den Sport selbst und beeinflusst die Spielregeln, die Trainingsmethoden, die Leistungsmessung und sogar die technischen Aspekte des Spiels auf dem Spielfeld.

In diesem Beitrag sollen die Auswirkungen der Globalisierung auf den Sport untersucht werden, die sich auf verschiedene Bereiche wie Wirtschaft, Marketing, Organisation, Politik und Kultur erstrecken. Zwei wichtige Beispiele für die Globalisierung des Sports werden in diesem Beitrag hervorgehoben. Das erste ist die Verbreitung der Sportkultur, die durch die wachsende Popularität des American Football in Europa veranschaulicht wird. Das zweite Beispiel untersucht, wie die Globalisierung zur Steigerung der Einkünfte und des Gesamtwerts von Sportlern und großen Sportvereinen beigetragen hat.

STICHWORTE: Globalisierung, Sport, Wert von Sportvereinen

RÉSUMÉ

La mondialisation et le sport sont étroitement liés, en particulier dans le contexte de la révolution en cours des technologies de l'information et de la numérisation. Des Jeux olympiques aux grandes compétitions internationales, la mondialisation a transformé le sport en une industrie massive, suscitant un intérêt accru pour la gestion et l'organisation de manifestations sportives à l'échelle mondiale. Cette transformation remodèle également le sport lui-même, en influençant les règles du jeu, les méthodes d'entraînement, le suivi des performances et même les aspects techniques du jeu sur le terrain.

Ce document vise à explorer l'impact de la mondialisation sur le sport, qui couvre plusieurs domaines, notamment l'économie, le marketing, l'organisation, la politique et la culture. Deux exemples clés de la mondialisation du sport sont mis en évidence dans ce document. Le premier est la diffusion de la culture sportive, illustrée par la popularité croissante du football américain en Europe. Le second exemple examine comment la mondialisation a contribué à l'augmentation des revenus et de la valeur globale des athlètes et des grands clubs sportifs.

MOTS-CLÉS: mondialisation, sport, valeur des clubs sportifs

INTRODUCTION

This paper will analyze the concept of globalization and its connection to and impact on sports. Numerous studies have shown that globalization is becoming increasingly popular and pervasive, penetrating nearly every aspect of human life. As a process of uniting the world into one society, globalization also brings sports from that society into a global sport. Sports are closely linked to globalization and are becoming more present in everyday life; they are a social phenomenon that influences various spheres of human existence.

Škaro and Stipetić (2016), in their book *"Sport in the Era of Globalization"*, provide an insightful description of the journey of sport from a physical activity to a major economic sector facilitated by globalization. Specifically, globalization has transformed sport, from a physical activity, through the Olympic Games, into a powerful economic sector, giving rise to professional athletes. One distinct aspect of globalization's influence on sport is the viewership, whether via TV screens or live events.

The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate the impact of globalization on sport. The objectives are multiple: to discuss globalization as a phenomenon; to illustrate the expansion of its influence on sport, using the example of the spread of American sports and culture around the world; to examine how globalization affects sports viewership, as well as the earnings of clubs and athletes, which have significantly increased due to globalization. The main hypothesis of this paper is that there is a positive link between globalization and sport, particularly reflected in the growth of sports' reach and viewership, which in turn boosts revenue and the value of sports clubs.

The paper uses general scientific methods such as induction, deduction, analysis, and synthesis, as well as compilation and comparison methods. Data was collected from secondary sources. Predominantly, newspaper and online articles from sports portals and organizations were used, as they contain information and news that best explain and illustrate the essence of what is being discussed and analyzed in this paper. Additionally, academic literature (books, scholarly papers) from various authors

who have worked or are working in this field was used to clarify and explain specific professional terms and facts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

"Sport today is a multilayered and multidimensional phenomenon that encompasses a multitude of values, affecting not only social, educational, and health-related areas, as well as philosophical, scientific, and cultural domains of social life, but also economic, legal, and political fields." (Škaro and Stipetić, 2016). Additionally, McBride (1979) wrote long ago that "the definition of sport is neither possible nor desirable" due to its imprecise concept; the term 'sport' has a range of different meanings and lacks an essential core meaning; it is variably used and understood in everyday speech; it is ambiguous and therefore subject to different interpretations; the differences between sports are vast (Zagorac and Škerbić, 2018).

It is clear from the above that today it is difficult to define sport, and that there are many definitions and meanings associated with it, with sport becoming increasingly present among people. This can be attributed to globalization and technological development, which have allowed people to have less physically demanding jobs and less time required for various tasks, thus giving them more free time. In these changes, people are increasingly turning to sport as a healthy way of life. It can be observed that the socio-economic phenomenology of sport is becoming more pronounced. With the development of economic globalization, as well as the promotion of modern Olympism and the Olympic movement, sport itself is becoming global. As many as 206 national Olympic committees from countries around the world are united in the International Olympic Committee (Škaro and Stipetić, 2016).

The Phenomenon of Globalization. Globalization has become a popular concept in social sciences, a key directive for management gurus, and an attractive slogan for journalists and politicians of all kinds. We live in an era where much of social life is shaped by global processes, with national cultures, economies, and borders fading away. Central to this is the idea of rapid economic globalization. It is believed that a truly global economy has emerged or is emerging, where national economies are separated, and therefore, domestic economic management strategies are increasingly irrelevant (Hirst and Thompson, 2001: 11).

There are many definitions of globalization. In the Economic Lexicon (1995: 139), globalization is described as a process that has led to the creation of a global market thanks to the rapid development of transport, technologies, and communications. This global market implies the free flow of goods, people, and capital, and today increasingly, information. The result is an economy of scale that itself becomes more global, with competition no longer recognizing borders and freely spreading across the world. Anyone who does not recognize the global market cannot participate equally in the global market competition.

Many, for example, Scholte (2000: 15-16), view globalization as westernization, Americanization, or the process of becoming "Western." In other words, globalization is a process driven by the actions of the world system and the establishment of economic, political, cultural, ecological, and informational activities on a global scale, creating interconnectedness among societies. Globalization is also a transnational action. The term globalization refers to transnational actions, events, spaces, images, movements, and the "dialectic" of the global-local, creating the local. Globalization is a deepened internationalization that takes place through production, exchange, communication, political decision-

making, and management of companies and societies, determining the frameworks for systemic changes within individual societies and countries. Globalization is a process towards a human community system, meaning it is a process of bringing individuals, states, and regions closer together into an integral system of human society. According to Turek (1999), globalization represents a social process striving for the comprehensiveness and unity of the world, while Giddens (1999) views globalization as the strengthening and intensification of social relations at a global level, which consequently leads to the linking of geographically distant areas. In this process, local events are triggered by occurrences that take place thousands of kilometers away.

Globalization has many variations—political, ecological, migration, etc. We will mention only a few. Political globalization refers to the strengthening of global democracy, transnational political institutions, and networks of national and transnational non-governmental organizations, along with the transformation of the functioning of nation-states, where strict boundaries between domestic and foreign policy fade. In such circumstances, nation-states transform, transferring part of their sovereignty to supra-national institutions (e.g., the EU), living in a new form of interconnected global interdependence. This does not mean the "end of nation-states" in neoliberal jargon or their "withering away" in Marxist terms. Some roles will be narrowed, and others expanded. Therefore: "Nations will retain, and in the foreseeable future will retain, governmental economic and cultural power over citizens and external relations. Nation-states will exist in the process of globalization through 'transnational intermediaries.' Thus, globalization signifies processes through which national states and their sovereignty will be intricately linked through transnational intermediaries, curbing their opportunities for power, orientation, identities, and networks" (Milardović, 2002: 94).

According to Srića (2000: 149), globalization emphasizes the forces of unity within the global market, supports the presence of multinational corporations around the world, and leads to comprehensive media integration.

Globalization and Sports. Sport is a specific type of game, defined as a necessary and voluntary overcoming of obstacles. It has four distinctive characteristics that set it apart from other games, such as those based on chance (Zagorac and Škrebić, 2018):

- The first characteristic is the testing of skills.
- The second is physical activity and the strategic use of the human body, distinguishing it from games that require skill, such as card games or board games.
- The third characteristic is a widespread following, meaning that sport is not (just) a local attraction or temporary trend.
- The fourth is institutionalization, which brings stability and longevity, secured by a range of developed new social roles (coaches, administrators, etc.) and specific social institutions.

Today, sports and globalization are inextricably linked. This connection is evident on various levels and across different areas, largely due to the globalized and digitized world. Sports have become much more than a physical activity aimed primarily at health; they have evolved into a global phenomenon, growing into a true industry not only with a large following of sports events but also with athletes competing at the professional level, earning enough to live comfortably. In other words, sports, thanks to globalization, have become an economic activity, and being an athlete has become a lucrative profession.

This marks a significant shift from the time when sports were only pursued at an amateur level. The substantial viewership and high earnings reflect the strong link between globalization and sports.

Several examples illustrate how globalization impacts sports. The first concerns the growing viewership of American football in Europe, while the second highlights the increasing earnings and value of individual athletes and major sports clubs.

American Football. American football is one of the most popular sports in the United States. It evolved from rugby in the late 19th century (Škaro and Stipetić, 2016). The goal of the game is to advance the ball over the opponent's goal line to score points, either by passing it to another player or by carrying the ball. The game consists of four quarters of 12 minutes each, with the winner being the team with the most points when time expires.

NFL. The professional American football league (NFL) was formed in 1920, and it has carried the name NFL since 1922. Its full name is the National Football League. The league currently consists of 32 teams, divided into two conferences (American and National), each containing four divisions (East, West, North, South). Each division has four teams.

At the end of the regular season, the top six teams from each conference enter the playoffs, and the two best teams play in the grand finale, known as the Super Bowl. This is one of the most-watched sporting events globally.

The Super Bowl's viewership is staggering, with 114.4 million viewers and 118.5 million viewers watching the halftime show, holding the record as the most-watched TV program in U.S. history. The price for an advertisement during halftime was \$4.2 million, compared to \$5.2 million the previous year.

The Super Bowl, like American football itself, has garnered substantial attention in Europe in recent years. Since 2007, the NFL has organized games in Europe, with four games planned for London in 2020, though they were canceled due to the COVID-19 pandemic. It is expected that the expansion of the NFL, American culture, and sport, along with the process of globalization, will continue at the same pace or even increase once the epidemiological situation allows.

Attendance at Sports Events. "One of the few attempts to define the globalization of migration in its multifaceted nature was made by Papastergiadis. According to him, this process has the following characteristics: multiplication of migration movements; differentiation of the economic, social, and cultural backgrounds of migrants; acceleration of migration patterns; growth in the number of migrants; feminization of migration; deterritorialization of cultural communities; and multiple loyalties within the diaspora. These are processes whose combined effects drive the expansion of international (global) migration. They can no longer be halted by economic or political measures. Globalization leads to 'turbulent flows' of people, with patterns of movement colliding and intersecting with economic demands and migration policies" (Papastergiadis, 2000: 86, cited in Mesić, 2002).

Globalization, which has brought migration and migration flows, has directly constructed networks of paths, leading to increased tourism and movement of the general population. This has resulted in record-breaking attendance at various sporting events, with the FIFA World Cup and the Olympic Games being among the most attended events worldwide.

"In the 21st century, the results of the globalization of sport from the second half of the 20th century are being created. World championships in football, handball, athletics (Diamond League),

basketball, and other sports are becoming more frequent and increasingly popular: millions watch the best athletes on television, competing in various disciplines" (Škaro and Stipetić, 2016).

The Value of Sports. It is clear that sports are a social phenomenon deeply embedded in the fabric of human life, which forms the foundation for sports as an economic activity. Today, sports can be understood as a serious economic sector, where enormous profits are generated, and large amounts of money circulate. Consequently, there are increasingly more interested parties looking to enter the "sports business."

As sports have expanded and brought substantial wealth, their impact on GDP has grown, though it has been difficult to calculate. The European Union recognized this in 2006 when it established the SSA (Sport Satellite Accounts) project to better explore the link between sports and the economy and develop a methodology for accounting for sports in the GDP of member states. After 10 years, the EU published research results describing the economic impact of sports in its member states. Based on SSA data and member state data from 2012 as the base year for the study, the results showed that the GDP linked to sports accounts for 2.12% of the total EU GDP. One reason for the significant impact of sports on GDP in Europe is UEFA (Union of European Football Associations), which governs European football and serves as the umbrella organization for 55 national associations. Simply put, UEFA manages football throughout Europe. The EU is highly satisfied with UEFA's work and provides strong support for its activities.

The development of technology and telecommunications has spread the sport all over the world and now every league is available in almost every country. Due to the excess of free time, there is a huge interest in people following various sports and leagues, therefore TV companies try to offer as much and as high quality as possible content through their media. This is why the prices of the biggest and most interesting TV rights are also rising league in the world, who really use it. All that money is poured into the clubs that make up the leagues, and they invest the money obtained in strengthening their teams, their brand and their recognition.

The value of sports clubs. Globalization significantly affects the value of sports clubs. Based on Forbes lists we will present the most valuable sports clubs in the world in 2023.

The NFL dominates the top 10 with six teams in the list, indicating the league's immense commercial power. The NBA also has a notable presence, with two teams in the top 10. This list highlights the deep connection between sports, market size, ownership strategies, and commercial ventures, with successful franchises benefiting from diversified revenue streams such as media rights, sponsorships, merchandise sales, and high-value real estate. Teams that have invested in state-of-the-art facilities and successfully capitalized on lucrative markets, like Los Angeles, New York, and Las Vegas, have seen significant value growth.

Earnings of athletes. If we put sport in the context of economic activity, then we need some workers for that activity. The main workers or rather the performers of this activity would be the athletes themselves, who play for their clubs or for themselves, it depends on the sport, and they compete against each other, who will do a better job.

"Highly qualified performers-players, talents, who excelled in that sport as well. The club pays transfer compensation to the club from which the player comes. Along with the transfer price, the players

also get high ones annual fees, by special contracts." (Škaro and Stipetić 2016: 137). The following is a list of athletes who earned the most in the last year.

Table 1. Presentation of the top 10 most valuable clubs from 2023 according to the Forbes list

Rank	Team	Current Value	League	Owner	Year Purchased	Price Paid	Five-Year Change in Value	Change in Rank from 2022
1	Dallas Cowboys	\$9 billion	NFL	Jerry Jones	1989	\$150 million	80%	—
2	New York Yankees	\$7.1 billion	MLB	Steinbrenner family	1973	\$8.8 million	78%	^2
3	Golden State Warriors	\$7 billion	NBA	Joe Lacob, Peter Guber	2010	\$450 million	126%	^5
3	New England Patriots	\$7 billion	NFL	Robert Kraft	1994	\$172 million	84%	∇1
5	Los Angeles Rams	\$6.9 billion	NFL	E. Stanley Kroenke	2010	\$750 million	116%	∇2
6	New York Giants	\$6.8 billion	NFL	John Mara, Steven Tisch	1925, 1991	\$500, \$150 million	106%	∇2
7	Chicago Bears	\$6.3 billion	NFL	McCaskey family	1920	\$100	117%	∇1
8	Las Vegas Raiders	\$6.2 billion	NFL	Mark Davis	1966	\$180,000	156%	^5
9	New York Knicks	\$6.1 billion	NBA	Madison Square Garden Sports	1997	\$300 million	69%	∇3
9	New York Jets	\$6.1 billion	NFL	Johnson family	2000	\$635 million	114%	^2
11	Real Madrid	\$6.07 billion	Spanish La Liga	Club members	NA	NA	48%	^2

Source: Forbes (2023).

Table 2. Presentation of the top 10 athletes with the highest earnings in 2023 according to the Forbes list

Rank	Athlete	Earnings (\$ million)	On-Field (\$ million)	Off-Field (\$ million)	Nationality	Sport	Age
1	Cristiano Ronaldo	136	46	90	Portugal	Soccer	38
2	Lionel Messi	130	65	65	Argentina	Soccer	35
3	Kylian Mbappé	120	100	20	France	Soccer	24
4	LeBron James	119.5	44.5	75	U.S.	Basketball	38
5	Canelo Álvarez	110	100	10	Mexico	Boxing	32
6	Dustin Johnson	107	102	5	U.S.	Golf	38
7	Phil Mickelson	106	104	2	U.S.	Golf	52
8	Stephen Curry	100.4	48.4	52	U.S.	Basketball	35
9	Roger Federer	95.1	0.1	95	Switzerland	Tennis	41
10	Kevin Durant	89.1	44.1	45	U.S.	Basketball	34

Source: Forbes (2023)

Soccer continues to dominate the list, with Cristiano Ronaldo, Lionel Messi, and Kylian Mbappé leading the top positions. Basketball players, especially LeBron James, Stephen Curry, and Kevin Durant, also occupy prominent spots, largely due to their global influence and lucrative off-field deals. Boxing and Golf are represented with Canelo Álvarez, Dustin Johnson, and Phil Mickelson, showcasing the high earnings potential in these sports. Tennis, with Roger Federer, highlights the power of endorsement deals even after an athlete has retired from competitive sports. This list emphasizes the growing significance of off-field income, as athletes expand their earnings through endorsements, business ventures, and personal branding.

Tennis dominates the rankings, with Iga Świątek, Coco Gauff, Emma Raducanu, Aryna Sabalenka, and others leading the pack. This highlights tennis as one of the most lucrative sports for female athletes, thanks to a combination of on-field success and high-paying sponsorships. Freestyle Skiing stands out with Eileen Gu, whose off-field earnings significantly exceed her on-field earnings, showcasing the influence of her marketability and endorsement deals. Off-field earnings play a major role in the overall earnings of these athletes. Many of the top 10 athletes earn more off the field than on it, particularly in sports like tennis and skiing. Younger athletes, such as Eileen Gu, Coco Gauff, and Iga Świątek, are securing massive endorsement deals early in their careers, setting the stage for long-term financial success.

This list demonstrates how endorsements, business ventures, and personal branding have become integral components of the financial success of female athletes across different sports.

Table 3. Presentation of the top 10 female athletes with the highest earnings in 2023 according to the Forbes list

Rank	Athlete	Sport	Nationality	Age	On-Field Earnings	Off-Field Earnings	Total Earnings
1	Iga Świątek	Tennis	Poland	22	\$9.9 million	\$14 million	\$23.9 million
2	Eileen Gu	Freestyle Skiing	China	20	\$0.1 million	\$22 million	\$22.1 million
3	Coco Gauff	Tennis	U.S.	19	\$6.7 million	\$15 million	\$21.7 million
4	Emma Raducanu	Tennis	United Kingdom	21	\$0.2 million	\$15 million	\$15.2 million
5	Naomi Osaka	Tennis	Japan	26	\$0	\$15 million	\$15 million
6	Aryna Sabalenka	Tennis	Belarus	25	\$8.2 million	\$6.5 million	\$14.7 million
7	Jessica Pegula	Tennis	U.S.	29	\$6 million	\$6.5 million	\$12.5 million
8	Venus Williams	Tennis	U.S.	43	\$0.2 million	\$12 million	\$12.2 million
9	Elena Rybakina	Tennis	Kazakhstan	24	\$5.5 million	\$4 million	\$9.5 million
10	Leylah Fernandez	Tennis	Canada	21	\$1.8 million	\$7 million	\$8.8 million

Source: Forbes (2023)

CONCLUSION

Globalization and sport are two phenomena that complement each other. Globalization, as a process of connecting the world into a single society of diverse cultures and customs, and sport as a multidimensional phenomenon with a range of characteristics, such as social, societal, marketing, and economic aspects.

The impact of globalization on sport is multifaceted, but in this paper, we have attempted to highlight only a few examples, such as American football, which, thanks to globalization, has become increasingly popular and present in Europe. We also observed how globalization influences the increase in earnings and the value of the largest sports clubs, particularly over the past five years.

Indeed, globalization has spread American culture across the world and "brought" part of American sport with it. Since globalization, along with the development of technology and information systems, has enabled the availability of nearly all content globally, almost every sport is now accessible in most parts of the world. Europe has readily embraced American sports, and as a result, viewership continues to rise, even though the timing of matches can be inconvenient for Europeans due to time

differences. American leagues have recognized this, and more games are being scheduled at more convenient times for other countries. Moreover, a few games of American football (NFL) are played in Europe, as well as games from the strongest basketball league, the NBA.

Globalization has made wealthy athletes even richer. According to data, athletes are recording a positive growth trend in individual earnings, as well as in the value of clubs. This confirms that globalization has globalized sport, making it more and more followed by people, and sports clubs are becoming increasingly recognized, with fame bringing financial rewards. Furthermore, it is interesting to note that American clubs dominate the top 10 list of the most valuable clubs.

Therefore, we can conclude that globalization and sport are inseparably linked today and that they support each other. Thanks to the development of technology and the speed of information spread, sport is expanding globally, and due to its multiple functions, it also serves as a connector between all nations directly or indirectly involved in it. Following global sports events has become an integral part of modern life. It can be assumed that in the future, we will continue to see how sport and globalization strengthen their bond, from individual players to clubs and other organizations that are part of the sports world.

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PREVENTIVE AND RESTORATIVE APPROACHES IN EARLY CHILDHOOD CARIES

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ABSTRACT

Early childhood caries (ECC) is a bacterial infectious disease affecting children under the age of three, caused by early colonization of the oral cavity by *Streptococcus mutans*. The transmission of this bacterium often occurs from mother to child through saliva, via shared utensils, pacifiers, or droplets. The development of ECC involves multiple factors, including the host (teeth), the presence of cariogenic bacteria, a sugary diet, and sufficient time for these conditions to act synergistically. Poor oral hygiene, frequent nighttime breastfeeding, and high consumption of sweetened beverages significantly accelerate the onset and progression of ECC.

KEYWORDS: early childhood caries, preventive strategies, restorative procedures

ABSTRAKT

Frühkindliche Karies (ECC) ist eine bakterielle Infektionskrankheit, die Kinder unter drei Jahren betrifft und durch eine frühe Besiedlung der Mundhöhle durch *Streptococcus mutans* verursacht wird. Die Übertragung dieses Bakteriums erfolgt häufig von der Mutter auf das Kind über den Speichel, über gemeinsam benutztes Geschirr, Schnuller oder Tröpfchen. Bei der Entwicklung von ECC spielen mehrere Faktoren eine Rolle, darunter der Wirt (die Zähne), das Vorhandensein von kariogenen Bakterien, eine zuckerhaltige Ernährung und genügend Zeit, damit diese Bedingungen synergetisch wirken können. Schlechte Mundhygiene, häufiges nächtliches Stillen und ein hoher Konsum von gesüßten Getränken beschleunigen den Beginn und das Fortschreiten der frühkindlichen Karies erheblich.

STICHWORTE: Frühkindliche Karies, Präventionsstrategien, restaurative Verfahren

RÉSUMÉ

La carie de la petite enfance (CPE) est une maladie infectieuse bactérienne touchant les enfants de moins de trois ans, causée par la colonisation précoce de la cavité buccale par *Streptococcus mutans*. La transmission de cette bactérie se fait souvent de la mère à l'enfant par la salive, via le partage d'ustensiles, de sucettes ou de gouttelettes. Le développement de l'ECC implique de multiples facteurs, dont l'hôte (les dents), la présence de bactéries cariogènes, une alimentation sucrée et un temps suffisant pour que ces conditions agissent en synergie. Une mauvaise hygiène bucco-dentaire, un allaitement nocturne fréquent et une consommation élevée de boissons sucrées accélèrent considérablement l'apparition et la progression des caries de la petite enfance.

MOTS-CLÉS: caries de la petite enfance, stratégies préventives, procédures de restauration

INTRODUCTION

Early childhood caries (ECC), as defined by the American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry, refers to the presence of one or more decayed teeth, missing teeth due to caries, or filled tooth surfaces in any

child up to the age of three (Karaca et al.,2013). The term "early childhood caries" was adopted in 1994 and describes the occurrence of dental caries in infants and preschool-aged children (Ivančić et al.,2006). This condition is a complex disease that can appear on maxillary primary teeth as early as one month after eruption and is one of the most prevalent childhood diseases. ECC is a global issue, affecting children across all socioeconomic classes, but it disproportionately impacts those from lower-income backgrounds. The disease progresses rapidly, often starting on smooth surfaces and spreading to other teeth, causing severe social, psychological, and dental problems in young children. The maxillary primary teeth are particularly significant for physical appearance, and their loss impacts not only aesthetics but also functionality, such as chewing and speech, and can lead to the development of poor habits (Berkowitz, 2003)

Clinical examinations commonly reveal characteristic patterns, with central maxillary incisors, lateral incisors, and the first maxillary and mandibular molars being most affected. Maxillary primary incisors are particularly vulnerable, often experiencing carious lesions that extend to the pulp (Ivančić et al.,2006). In extreme cases, ECC can lead to the complete destruction of the tooth crown. In the past, due to the complexity of restoring severely damaged primary teeth, extraction was often the most common treatment (Karaca et al.,2013).

However, ECC remains a significant public health issue as it predisposes children to caries in permanent teeth, disrupts normal feeding, affects growth, causes pain and discomfort, and can lead to communication difficulties and psychological problems that impact a child's quality of life (Nissan and Khoury-Absawi,2009).

ECC is also known by various synonyms, including bottle caries, infant caries, circular caries, rampant caries, early childhood caries, labial caries, upper maxillary caries, and pediatric caries (Ivančić et al.,2006).

The purpose of this study is to consolidate knowledge gained through academic education in pediatric and preventive dentistry, under the guidance of mentors, to provide a comprehensive overview of early childhood caries.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Treatment of Early Childhood Caries. Managing early childhood caries involves a combination of preventive and restorative approaches, tailored to the severity and extent of the disease. Early intervention is critical to mitigate the progression of decay and minimize its impact on a child's oral health and overall well-being.

In cases of mild decay, conservative treatments such as topical fluoride application can be employed to promote remineralization of the enamel. Sealants may also be used to protect vulnerable surfaces from further damage. For moderate caries, restorative fillings are commonly used to repair the affected areas, restoring the tooth's function and structure.

When the decay has progressed significantly, leading to substantial loss of hard tooth tissue or pulp involvement, more advanced restorative techniques are necessary. Crowns are often recommended in such cases to preserve the tooth and maintain its function. If the pulp is infected, endodontic treatment may be required before placing a crown.

In severe cases where the tooth structure is extensively damaged or an abscess has developed, extraction might be unavoidable. Post-extraction, space maintainers may be utilized to ensure proper alignment of the remaining teeth and to prevent complications during the eruption of permanent teeth.

Education and behavioral modifications play a vital role in the treatment process. Parents and caregivers are advised on proper oral hygiene practices, dietary changes, and regular dental check-ups to prevent recurrence. Establishing good oral hygiene habits and addressing dietary factors, such as reducing the consumption of sugary foods and beverages, are essential for long-term success.

Ultimately, the goal of treating early childhood caries is not only to restore dental health but also to improve the child's quality of life by alleviating pain, enabling normal feeding, and supporting healthy growth and development.

In modern dental medicine, minimally invasive techniques are the method of choice in rehabilitation of RDK (5). When choosing the appropriate technique for each patient, the dentist must know their indications and contraindications (Nissan and Khoury-Absawi,2009).

Traditional Restorative Procedures. The primary objective of traditional restorative techniques is to preserve as much of the healthy dental tissue as possible while removing carious tissue (Jurić et al., 2015). The carious lesion is removed using a round carbide or ceramic bur. Only the demineralized tissue is excised, resulting in a cavity shape dictated by the caries process. Enamel edges are beveled, and the preventive opening of fissures to physiologically clean areas is avoided (Goršeta et al.,2009).

When treating primary teeth, factors such as patient cooperation, child's age, caries risk, and caries incidence are crucial for material selection. Given the specific anatomy of primary teeth, including thinner enamel, larger pulp chambers, smaller tooth size, and faster progression of carious lesions, timely intervention with appropriate materials is vital (Corrêa-Faria, 2020).

Materials used in pediatric dentistry should have preventive effects, good adhesion to dental tissue, effective marginal sealing, and ease of use (Goršeta et al.,2009).

Glass-Ionomer Cements (GICs). GICs consist of liquid (polyacrylic acid or copolymers of acrylic, maleic, or itaconic acid) and powder (calcium-aluminum-fluorosilicate glass particles). Based on composition, they are classified as (Goršeta et al.,2009):

- Conventional GICs;
- High-viscosity GICs;
- Metal-reinforced GICs (cermets);
- Resin-modified GICs (57).

Conventional GICs bond through an acid-base reaction. Their applications include Type I (cementation), Type II (restorations), and Type III (liners and fissure sealants) (Jurić et al., 2015). These materials offer advantages such as chemical bonding to enamel and dentin, biocompatibility, fluoride release, aesthetic properties, ease of use, and good retention. Indications include Class I, III, and V restorations, cavity linings, fissure sealing, and tunnel preparation restorations.

High-viscosity GICs, formulated with added polyacrylic acid and finely distributed smaller particles, are used in ART (Atraumatic Restorative Treatment) and for primary teeth restorations due to their enhanced abrasion resistance and mechanical properties.

Metal-reinforced GICs, containing metal particles (e.g., silver, palladium, gold, platinum), improve mechanical strength and wear resistance. These materials are suitable for primary molar restorations or rebuilding severely damaged teeth.

Resin-modified GICs contain hydrophilic organic matrices (e.g., HEMA) and photoinitiators for light curing alongside chemical curing. Their dual-bonding mechanism creates a hybrid layer on dentin, improving retention and reducing marginal leakage. They offer advantages such as higher fluoride ion concentration, ease of application, better adhesion, and reduced solubility, but drawbacks include color instability, monomer toxicity, and polymerization shrinkage (Goršeta et al., 2009).

Nano-ionomers, the latest generation of resin-modified GICs, exhibit improved properties such as higher fluoride release, enhanced polishability, and better aesthetics (Jurić et al., 2015).

GICs are often chosen for children with high caries risk, special needs, or when achieving a dry working field is challenging. Their primary drawback compared to composite materials is weaker mechanical properties. Failure rates for GICs are 33% over five years, with an average restoration lifespan of 33 months, making them suitable for primary dentition (Mahoney et al., 2008).

Compomers. Compomers are quick and easy to apply, making them ideal for pediatric dentistry. They are used for Class II restorations in primary teeth, cervical restorations, fissure sealing, temporary fillings, and cementing orthodontic brackets (Nicholson, 2008). Designed to combine the best properties of composites and GICs, compomers consist of calcium-aluminum-zinc-fluoride glass, methacrylates, inorganic fillers, ytterbium trifluoride, pigments, initiators, and stabilizers (Nicholson, 2008).

These materials provide chemical and micromechanical bonding, enhanced hardness, wear resistance, fluoride release, polishability, and aesthetic appeal. The polymerization process includes three stages: acid-base reaction (like GICs), light polymerization of the composite component, and self-initiated free radical polymerization. However, they are hydrophobic like composites and require an adhesive system for bonding to dental tissue (Nicholson, 2008).

Composites. Composite materials were introduced in dental practice in the 1960s, becoming the material of choice for restorations over amalgam by the 1990s (Tarle and Klarić, 2017). Composites consist of three main components: an organic resin matrix, inorganic filler particles, and a coupling agent, along with color stabilizers, polymerization inhibitors, pigments, and an activator system.

Based on filler particle size, composites are classified as:

- Macrofiller composites (particle size 20–50 μm , 77–80% filler content);
- Microfiller composites (particle size 0.04–0.2 μm , 38% filler content);
- Hybrid composites (particle size 0.04–5 μm , 70–80% filler content).

Modern indications depend on polymer matrix composition, polymerization modulator types, filler size, and proportion. Macrofiller composites are no longer used due to poor polishability, instability, and discoloration. Microfiller composites are indicated for Class III, IV, and V restorations and minor tooth corrections, while hybrid composites are used for Class I and II restorations, dentin core build-ups for Class IV cavities, and composite inlays (Jurić et al., 2015).

Although composite materials offer excellent aesthetics and mechanical properties, they are less widely used for primary teeth restorations due to time-intensive procedures like etching and applying adhesive systems, hydrophobic properties, and moisture sensitivity during application.

Atraumatic Restorative Treatment (ART). The Atraumatic Restorative Treatment (ART) is a minimally invasive approach aimed at removing softened carious dentin while halting the progression of dental caries. Originally developed as a restorative and preventive technique for underprivileged areas with limited access to electricity and water, ART has since gained acceptance in more developed countries. This technique involves the gentle removal of infected dentin using only hand instruments, without the need for anesthesia, and the application of a high-viscosity glass ionomer cement. The cement chemically bonds to dental tissues and contributes to remineralization (Frencken,2010). Studies by Lo et al. have shown that ART reduces anxiety, with 93% of children reporting no pain during the procedure and 86% willing to undergo it again (62). The absence of the noise from dental turbines, often distressing for children, adds to ART's appeal, as manual excavators suffice for removing softened dentin (Holmgren,2013).

When rotary instruments are used to access the carious lesion, the method is referred to as the modified ART technique. Although rotary tools can streamline and speed up the procedure, they carry risks such as excessive cavity widening, unnecessary removal of potentially remineralizable dentin, and pulp exposure (Holmgren,2013).

Research by Fusayama and Massler identified two layers in dentin: the outer infected layer, which is soft, non-vital, bacteria-rich, and non-remineralizable, and the inner affected layer, which is harder, vital, and capable of remineralization. The complete removal of the infected dentin is essential, while the affected dentin can remain to support the restoration process. Studies have demonstrated that sealed carious lesions lack the nutrients needed for further progression, especially with the remineralizing effect of glass ionomer cement (Mickenautsch and Grossman, 2006).

Successful ART implementation requires accurate diagnosis and skilled clinical execution. The procedure includes the following steps:

- Isolation of the working field;
- Removal of infected dentin using an excavator;
- Conditioning of dentin to eliminate residual layers;
- Placement of high-viscosity glass ionomer cement;
- Occlusal adjustment and verification (Holmgren,2013).

Research evaluating ART's efficacy found an 86% success rate for single-surface restorations, with a 5% annual failure rate, while multi-surface restorations had a higher annual failure rate of 17% (Duangthip et al., 2017). The most common issues include complete or partial material loss, marginal caries, and material wear exceeding 0.5 mm (Mickenautsch and Grossman, 2006).

Hall Technique. The Hall technique is a minimally invasive method used to halt the progression of carious lesions by cementing a crown onto primary molars without the need for rotating instruments, anesthesia, or tooth preparation (Welbury,2017). Dr. Norna Hall observed a high prevalence of dental caries in Scotland and developed a simple technique for treating caries in children, which can be used by all dentists, not just pediatric specialists (Hussein,2015).

This technique involves the straightforward cementing of a stainless steel crown that prevents the flow of oxygen and nutrients, while glass-ionomer cements facilitate the remineralization of the captured carious lesion. Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of glass-ionomer cements in halting caries progression (Evans,2015).

The Hall technique is not suitable for all patients with carious lesions, and certain criteria must be assessed before beginning the procedure.

Indications for the Hall technique include:

- Class I and II lesions, with or without cavitation
- Enamel hypoplasia
- High caries risk
- Following successful endodontic treatment

Contraindications include:

- Non-cooperative patients;
- Teeth with symptoms of irreversible pulpitis or sepsis;
- Teeth with clinical or radiographic signs of affected pulp or periradicular area;
- Fractured teeth with insufficient sound tooth structure;
- Patients at risk for infectious endocarditis.

After taking the medical history and performing a clinical examination, the procedure for placing the metal crown consists of seven steps:

1. Determining occlusion and expanding the interdental space by placing an orthodontic separator for 3–5 days.
2. Securing the airway.
3. Selecting the appropriate size metal crown.
4. Filling the crown with glass-ionomer cement.
5. Cementing the crown onto the tooth and applying pressure to ensure a proper fit.
6. Removing excess cement and checking the crown's fit.
7. Cleaning the interdental space, checking occlusion, and the relationship with adjacent teeth.

It is crucial to explain to both the child and parents that initially, the crown may feel higher than the other teeth, and that this is not the final step. Regular follow-up visits are necessary (Evans,2015). After 30 days, the vertical dimension is adjusted using dentoalveolar compensation (Welbury,2017).

A 2007 study comparing the effectiveness of the Hall technique and restorative procedures showed that the success rate for the Hall technique was 98%, compared to 85% for restorative procedures (Evans,2015). The advantages of the Hall technique, compared to restorative procedures, are most evident in a graph from a study where children, parents, and dentists were surveyed about the techniques (Evans,2015). A 2013 study on the acceptance of the Hall technique also showed that children and parents had a positive opinion of the metal crowns, with most children experiencing no issues following the procedure. Most children accept metal crowns and describe them as "transformer teeth," "tiara teeth," or "Viking teeth," and dentists describe the Hall technique as less traumatic for children, reducing anxiety during dental treatment (Page at al.,2014).

CONCLUSION

Early diagnosis and the implementation of preventive measures are crucial in preventing early childhood caries. It is important to educate parents about the significance of oral health and their vital role in prevention—adopting healthy eating habits and maintaining good oral hygiene. Additionally, parents should prevent the vertical transmission of *Streptococcus mutans* (SM) to their child by treating

all carious lesions in their own mouths and using xylitol-containing chewing gums. Pediatricians also play an essential role in prevention, as they come into contact with children before dentists and can advise parents about the importance of the first dental check-up by the age of one.

Depending on the clinical situation, appropriate therapy is implemented. If a non-cavitated lesion is present, fluoride varnish application is recommended along with other preventive measures. In cases of enamel cavitation, silver diamine fluoride is applied. If the carious lesion is progressive and has affected most of the crown and cannot be stopped with preventive methods, restorative therapy is carried out with maximum preservation of hard dental tissues.

The ART (Atraumatic Restorative Treatment) method and Hall technique have proven to be the preferred methods in restorative therapy, especially for children who have a fear of dental procedures. These techniques are well accepted by children due to their minimally invasive approach, restoration of teeth without the use of rotating instruments and anesthesia. Glass-ionomer cement is a material commonly used in pediatric dentistry because it is easy to apply, has beneficial properties, and can remineralize hard dental tissues.

The goal of preventive or restorative therapy is to retain primary teeth until their natural exfoliation, as they are crucial for preserving space for permanent teeth, chewing, clear speech, and the growth and development of the jaw.

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TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS IN SPORTS: ADVANCING PERFORMANCE, ACCURACY, AND GLOBAL IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

Sport and technology have become inseparably intertwined in the modern world, shaping how sports are followed and understood. Technology in sports encompasses a wide range of innovations, from basic tools like video analysis and heart rate monitors to advanced solutions such as VAR (Video Assistant Referee) and artificial intelligence. Each of these technologies has brought significant changes to the way sports are played, observed, and analyzed.

This paper provides a detailed overview of key technological innovations that have transformed sports in recent years, along with an analysis of emerging technologies shaping the sports landscape today. Particular focus is placed on technologies such as Instant Replay, Hawk-Eye, and Goal-Line Technology, which have improved accuracy and fairness in sports competitions. Modern advancements like AI, VR (Virtual Reality), and nanotechnology are also explored for their contributions to performance analysis and athlete training.

KEYWORDS: Technology, Sport, Innovation, Hawk-Eye, Goal-Line Technology, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Nanotechnology

ABSTRAKT

Sport und Technologie sind in der modernen Welt untrennbar miteinander verwoben und prägen die Art und Weise, wie Sport verfolgt und verstanden wird. Die Technologie im Sport umfasst ein breites Spektrum an Innovationen, von einfachen Hilfsmitteln wie Videoanalyse und Herzfrequenzmessgeräten bis hin zu fortschrittlichen Lösungen wie VAR (Video Assistant Referee) und künstlicher Intelligenz. Jede dieser Technologien hat die Art und Weise, wie Sport gespielt, beobachtet und analysiert wird, erheblich verändert.

Dieses Papier bietet einen detaillierten Überblick über die wichtigsten technologischen Innovationen, die den Sport in den letzten Jahren verändert haben, sowie eine Analyse der neuen Technologien, die die Sportlandschaft heute prägen. Besonderes Augenmerk wird auf Technologien wie Instant Replay, Hawk-Eye und Torlinientechnologie gelegt, die die Genauigkeit und Fairness von Sportwettbewerben verbessert haben. Moderne Fortschritte wie KI, VR (Virtual Reality) und Nanotechnologie werden ebenfalls auf ihren Beitrag zur Leistungsanalyse und zum Training von Sportlern untersucht.

STICHWORTE: Technologie, Sport, Innovation, Hawk-Eye, Torlinientechnologie, Künstliche Intelligenz (KI), Nanotechnologie

RÉSUMÉ

Le sport et la technologie sont devenus indissociables dans le monde moderne, façonnant la manière dont les sports sont suivis et compris. La technologie dans le sport englobe un large éventail d'innovations, des outils de base tels que l'analyse vidéo et les moniteurs de fréquence cardiaque aux solutions avancées telles que le VAR (Video Assistant Referee) et l'intelligence artificielle. Chacune de ces technologies a apporté des changements significatifs à la manière dont les sports sont pratiqués, observés et analysés.

Ce document donne un aperçu détaillé des principales innovations technologiques qui ont transformé le sport ces dernières années, ainsi qu'une analyse des technologies émergentes qui façonnent le paysage sportif aujourd'hui. L'accent est mis sur des technologies telles que la relecture instantanée, l'œil de faucon et la technologie de la ligne de but, qui ont amélioré la précision et l'équité des compétitions sportives. Les avancées modernes telles que l'IA, la RV (réalité virtuelle) et la nanotechnologie sont également explorées pour leurs contributions à l'analyse des performances et à l'entraînement des athlètes.

MOTS-CLÉS: Technologie, sport, innovation, Hawk-Eye, technologie de la ligne de but, intelligence artificielle (IA), nanotechnologie.

INTRODUCTION

From the running track to the football field, technology has become an indispensable player in the world of sports. It has transformed nearly every aspect of modern sports, from how games are played and analyzed to how they are experienced by fans. This paper will explore how technology has revolutionized sports throughout history, focusing on pivotal milestones such as the introduction of Instant Replay, Hawk-Eye technology, and wearable sensors. Furthermore, it will examine emerging technologies like artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and nanotechnology, highlighting their potential impact on the future of sports. This study argues that technology has not only revolutionized the way sports are played and monitored but has also profoundly changed how they are perceived and experienced.

Over the decades, technology has progressively integrated into sports, bringing unprecedented levels of precision, fairness, and excitement. From tracking athletes' performance with wearable devices to providing fans with immersive experiences through virtual reality, technology continues to blur the lines between reality and innovation. The adoption of Hawk-Eye technology in tennis and cricket, for instance, has eliminated human errors in decision-making, enhancing fairness and transparency in these sports.

Additionally, the widespread implementation of goal-line technology in football ensures that every crucial moment is accurately captured, preventing controversies that previously plagued the sport. Wearable sensors have also enabled athletes to monitor their health and performance metrics in real time, allowing for tailored training programs that maximize their potential while minimizing injury risks.

Emerging technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) and virtual reality (VR) are shaping the future of sports in fascinating ways. AI is now used to analyze vast amounts of data, helping coaches devise winning strategies and enabling broadcasters to offer fans insightful commentary and predictions. VR has

introduced immersive training environments where athletes can simulate real-world scenarios, improving their decision-making and performance under pressure.

Nanotechnology is another groundbreaking advancement, contributing to the development of lighter, stronger, and more durable sports equipment. From high-performance running shoes to advanced racing bicycles, nanotechnology is pushing the boundaries of what athletes can achieve.

The commercialization of sports has also been significantly influenced by technological advancements. Broadcast innovations, such as 4K and 8K resolution, combined with the accessibility of streaming platforms, have made sports more appealing and accessible to global audiences. This has driven substantial revenue growth for sports organizations and increased opportunities for sponsorships and partnerships.

Moreover, technology has fostered inclusivity in sports. Adaptive equipment and assistive technologies have empowered athletes with disabilities to compete at the highest levels, exemplified by the advancements seen in the Paralympic Games. These innovations not only enhance performance but also inspire a broader audience, showcasing the universal appeal of sports.

As technology continues to evolve, ethical and regulatory challenges arise, such as concerns about data privacy and the potential misuse of performance-enhancing technologies. Addressing these issues will be crucial to ensuring that technological advancements benefit all stakeholders in the sports ecosystem.

This paper seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of the transformative role of technology in sports, emphasizing both its achievements and challenges. By examining past innovations and exploring emerging trends, the study aims to shed light on the dynamic interplay between technology and sports, offering insights into what lies ahead for this ever-evolving partnership.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Historical Development of Technology in Sports. The heritage of sports traces its origins to events like horse racing and fox hunting during the colonial era. However, the defining characteristics of modern sports began to emerge only in the mid-19th century. By the early 20th century, football matches regularly attracted crowds exceeding 40,000 spectators, and the stadium built for the 1908 London Olympics had a capacity of over 68,000—an early example of modern, seated stadiums. After 1850, advancements in organization, media coverage, commercialization, community competition, and other developmental processes rapidly accelerated. The agrarian nature of sports gradually gave way to the influences of urbanization and industrialization. As Betts (1953) noted, "Just as the industrial revolution changed the interests, habits, and activities of all social classes, it left a clear mark on the development of sports."

The integration of new information technologies with the sports industry has ushered in profound changes, enabling a new era of development. According to Zhaoxi (2015, cited in Deng and Tang, 2020), "The integration of information technology, internet platforms, and the traditional sports industry has facilitated the entry of sports into a new phase of growth." This transformation has attracted significant investment from major internet companies, capitalizing on the vast potential for growth in the sports industry. Liping (2008, cited in Deng and Tang, 2020) emphasized, "In the era of new information technology, emerging business models are shaping the trajectory of the sports industry, with the integration of these technologies being a key trend for the future."

The application of new information technologies in the sports industry is essential for fostering economic growth. Examining this integration not only broadens the scope of sports industry research and informs policy planning but also provides an intellectual foundation for bolstering regional economic development through sports. Furthermore, it facilitates the expanded application of information sciences in sports industry research.

"The integration of electronics into sports began modestly. In the early 20th century, stopwatches and basic timekeeping devices were among the first electronic tools used in professional sports" (Corporate – Community Member, 2024). These early instruments played a crucial role in ensuring precise time measurement during races and competitions.

During the 1960s, the introduction of electronic scoreboards marked a revolutionary advancement in how games were followed. For the first time, fans could track the progress of a match in real time, significantly enhancing the spectator experience.

This era also witnessed the early adoption of video analysis for performance review. Coaches and athletes began to rely on video recordings to identify strengths and weaknesses, leading to more strategic preparation. The technological shift did not stop there. Advancements in broadcasting technology made it possible for sports to reach audiences worldwide, turning local competitions into global events.

As sports evolved, so did the tools that supported them. Early examples of wearable technology, such as heart rate monitors, became popular in the 1980s, providing athletes and trainers with invaluable data to optimize performance and recovery. These advancements laid the groundwork for today's sophisticated wearable devices that track everything from hydration levels to biomechanical movements.

Technological progress in sports has continued to expand its influence beyond performance enhancement. It has become a cornerstone of sports marketing and fan engagement, with interactive applications and live streaming platforms transforming the way audiences connect with their favorite teams and athletes.

The early technological milestones in sports not only revolutionized gameplay but also set the stage for more advanced innovations. These developments highlight the significant role technology plays in making sports more accurate, engaging, and inclusive, paving the way for a future where its impact will only grow.

Modern Technologies in Sports. Modern technologies are revolutionizing how we play, watch, and analyze sports. Today, advanced tools significantly enhance every aspect of the sports experience, from smartwatches and sensors that track every step and heartbeat to sophisticated data analysis systems that help coaches understand games and strategies better.

Technology not only improves gameplay and training but also elevates the viewer's experience, making sports events more engaging and informative than ever. With technological advancements, sports continue to evolve, opening new opportunities for everyone involved.

VAR Technology. VAR (Video Assistant Referee) is a technology introduced in football to assist referees in making critical decisions during matches. The system is used to review and confirm key situations, such as:

- **Goal validation:** Checking if a goal was legitimately scored, including potential fouls, handball incidents, offsides, or whether the ball had exited the field before the goal.

- **Penalty decisions:** Determining if a foul occurred inside or outside the penalty area, whether a penalty was correctly awarded, or if there were infringements during the penalty kick.
- **Red card incidents:** Reviewing direct red card scenarios, such as denying a goal-scoring opportunity, violent conduct, serious foul play, or abusive behavior.
- **Mistaken identity:** Correcting cases where the referee penalizes the wrong player with a card.

The VAR process is managed by a dedicated team located in the Video Operations Room (VOR). This team includes a chief VAR referee, at least one assistant VAR referee, and technical operators handling the equipment. Communication between the VAR team and on-field referees occurs via radio, with conversations recorded and stored. An additional screen near the field allows the main referee to review contentious situations if necessary.

VAR automatically reviews all situations and missed incidents, alerting the referee if a potential error requires stopping the game for a review. If the VAR team identifies a clear and obvious error or a significant missed incident, they recommend that the referee review the footage. The main referee can then change their initial decision after watching the replay.

In some cases, referees may rely solely on the VAR team's description of the situation, particularly for offside calls or determining the location of fouls, without needing to review the footage themselves.

The development of VAR began in the Netherlands in 2010, with initial tests conducted during the 2013/2014 season. After these early trials, VAR was used in various countries, including Australia and in tournaments like the FIFA Club World Cup. It was also implemented in select matches in Germany's Bundesliga and Italy's Serie A.

VAR gained global recognition during the 2018 FIFA World Cup in Russia, where it was used on a global stage for the first time. Since then, VAR has become a standard tool in football worldwide. In Croatia, VAR was introduced in early 2020 in the highest domestic football league.

The use of VAR during the 2018 World Cup led to the highest number of penalties in tournament history—28, compared to 13 in the 2014 Brazil World Cup and 18 in the 2002 World Cup in Japan and South Korea. Interestingly, only four red cards were issued in 2018, compared to 28 during the 2006 World Cup in Germany.

Analytics; Data Collection and Informatics. Sports analytics represents one of the most significant advancements in the field in recent years. By utilizing mathematical models and analyzing large volumes of data, experts can better understand abilities, trends, and patterns to enhance performance and predict outcomes of sports events. Tools like EPTS (Electronic Performance Tracking Systems), video analysis, and other analytical instruments enable coaches and analysts to develop better strategies, evaluate player performance, and analyze opponents. These tools provide critical insights to improve training and tactics.

"Today, every major professional sports club either has an analytics department or an analytics expert. Teams of people need to scan scout notes, convert these PDF files into Excel, and then forward them to top analysts." (Perinović and Kumiša, 2020.) Based on these analyses, mathematicians generate important statistical information that scouts and managers use to evaluate which player is most suitable for the team and the best timing to engage certain players. This process helps create a comprehensive player profile to assess their value to the team, whether for signing contracts or purchasing from another club.

Analytics has become crucial for professional sports and a significant competitive advantage. Teams that disregard analytical methods risk losing their competitiveness. The growing interest in analytical data is also evident among fans, who increasingly follow analytical content and statistics. An example of such content is the website "FiveThirtyEight.com," launched by Nate Silver in 2008. This site, part of the Entertainment and Sports Programming Network (ESPN), employs over 20 journalists specializing in data analysis and providing insights into upcoming sports seasons. Silver's methods were so successful in sports that they expanded into politics, where his analytics system correctly predicted the outcomes of 49 out of 50 U.S. states in the 2008 presidential elections.

Websites like "FiveThirtyEight.com" use sophisticated systems to analyze past results, win-loss ratios, and opponents' histories to predict the outcomes of future sports events. In basketball, for instance, "Player Tracking" technology analyzes court movements using six cameras installed on arena ceilings, tracking player and ball movements 25 times per second. This data provides detailed insights into player performance through statistics on speed, distance, ball interaction, and other factors. While these technologies produce vast amounts of data, the challenge lies in determining which data is essential for team improvement and athlete selection decisions. Excessive information can cause confusion, and a team's success depends on how experts interpret and apply this data. Analytics will continue to evolve and become even more critical, but achieving maximum results requires expertise from coaches and tacticians to optimize the use of this information.

Advancements in technology have enabled the collection of large amounts of data during games, but there is often a gap between the volume of collected information and its processing into truly useful insights. Studies, such as those conducted by Joachim Gudmundsson and Michael Horton from the University of Sydney, explore the challenges within the analytics process.

This approach to data collection can be applied to sports where two teams compete for ball control in an enclosed field. Each team's goal is to score as many points as possible while simultaneously preventing the opponent from scoring. "Sports sharing this structure include soccer, basketball, ice hockey, field hockey, rugby, handball, Australian football, American football, lacrosse, etc. However, most data comes from games like professional soccer and basketball, which have the resources for data collection." (Perinović and Kumiša, 2020.)

These records include player and ball trajectories and logs of key events such as passes and shots. Advanced technologies enable these trajectories to be recorded at high frequency, facilitating detailed analysis. A significant area in sports analytics is network science, which treats players as nodes connected by lines when the ball travels between them. This method allows for a detailed analysis of teamwork and efficiency, and mathematical tools for network analysis significantly enhance this type of research.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Sports. Artificial intelligence (AI) is a scientific discipline focused on developing computer systems capable of performing tasks that would require intelligence if done by humans (Ivašić-Kos, 2021). For example, AI can process raw sensory data, like images or sounds, into useful information. Computer vision, a branch of AI, enables systems to analyze multimedia data, allowing machines to "see" and interpret their environment.

AI has transformed sports by enhancing audience engagement, game strategies, and training programs. Advanced algorithms analyze vast data sets, improving athlete performance and decision-

making. Recent advancements in semiconductor technology, faster processors, and enhanced data analysis have further integrated AI into sports, now a global industry valued at over \$500 billion in 2023.

AI applications in sports include:

1. **Performance Analysis and Injury Prevention:** AI tracks physical metrics such as heart rate and biomechanics, enabling personalized training and injury risk assessment through predictive analytics.
2. **Talent Scouting:** Algorithms analyze performance data and videos to identify potential talents globally, reducing subjectivity in recruitment.
3. **Strategic Enhancements:** AI evaluates opponents' strategies and predicts game outcomes, providing coaches with data-driven tactical recommendations.
4. **Personalized Training and Nutrition:** AI creates tailored plans by analyzing biometrics and performance, optimizing athletes' physical and dietary regimens.
5. **Game Outcome Predictions:** AI identifies patterns in opponent behavior, enabling proactive strategy development and offering insights for sports betting.
6. AI's ability to quickly analyze large datasets provides real-time insights for players, coaches, and fans, revolutionizing decision-making and advancing sports innovation.

Nanotechnology in Sports. One of the critical aspects of technological application in sports is the use of nanotechnology. Nanotechnology enables precise control of molecular structures and atoms on the nanometer scale. This technology allows the development of special materials with unique properties, making nanotechnology a revolutionary force in the creation of sports equipment. Today, manufacturers of sports gear utilize advanced materials and production techniques that enhance flexibility, durability, resilience, strength, and thermoregulation of products. It is believed that nanotechnology offers significant opportunities for sports and that its application will become increasingly widespread in the future.

Currently, the most prominent materials include carbon nanotubes, which are six times lighter than steel and more than a hundred times stronger, with a strength comparable to diamonds. These materials have ushered in a new era in the design of sports equipment. The interdisciplinary nature of nanotechnology enables numerous innovations, resulting in products specifically designed for sports activities. Equipment made using nanotechnology significantly differs from conventional sports gear and holds vast potential for further application in sports. By utilizing crystal-clear carbon molecules, various forms of clothing, footwear, and equipment are created, reducing risks, increasing durability, and simultaneously employing lighter materials.

Nanotechnology represents the latest technological advancement in manipulating matter at the atomic and molecular levels, improving the performance of various materials. This technology is most commonly used in sports like swimming, cycling, skiing, and running, which are primarily aerobic physical activities. In swimming, in particular, nanotechnology materials have provided athletes with advantages, prompting additional research and regulations.

The goal of nanotechnology is to maximize material efficiency while minimizing weight, all to preserve athletic performance. Nanomaterials have improved the effectiveness of training and athlete performance.

Nanotechnology is used in creating sports shoes, a crucial component of sports equipment. This technology enables the integration of microchips into shoes, significantly increasing the number of

operations that can be performed in a second. These shoes help better absorb impacts, reduce stress on joints, and enhance athlete performance. Nanotechnology is not only used in manufacturing sportswear and footwear but also in developing sports accessories and equipment. Notable examples include the production of golf clubs and tennis rackets.

"The importance of nanotechnology has been recognized by many major companies investing in the development of technologically advanced accessories for athletes. The development of this technology is very costly and not accessible to all athletes, but as a result of business operations by companies utilizing nanotechnology, various products are created that can be used by both professional athletes and amateurs." (Hercigonja, 2022)

Biometric Monitoring. Biometrics is used in sports for talent identification, injury risk assessment, and evaluating athlete readiness. It involves data analysis in complex conditions to identify key factors such as optimal performance, injury risks, or athlete potential.

The need for more advanced tools for biometric analysis and better talent identification is evident. In the NFL, for example, only about 53% of first-round draft picks achieve long-term success. "Biometrics can help identify injury risks, determine when it is safe for athletes to return to the field, and assess athlete readiness to determine when they will achieve optimal performance. Wearable devices have been particularly useful for this during the COVID-19 pandemic." (Booton, 2020)

With technological advancements, biometrics allows increasingly precise injury and recovery analyses. For example, recovery from concussions may take longer than previously thought, and advanced technology helps better understand these processes.

Movement is a crucial factor in sports performance. By analyzing functional movement patterns, experts can determine how an athlete performs specific motions and adjust training to improve efficiency or reduce injury risks. Advanced motion analysis systems, such as cameras and sensors, help understand the full range of athlete movements and tailor training to their needs.

Hydration also has a significant impact on performance. Dehydration can considerably slow athletes down, and traditional methods of assessing hydration are not always accurate. New technologies that measure changes in sweat allow more precise hydration monitoring and prevent serious issues like heat illnesses.

In the future, technology will continue to evolve toward smart cameras capable of automatically tracking and analyzing athlete movements. These cameras are expected to be unobtrusive and easy to use, providing athletes with clear and useful information about their performance without adding extra burdens.

Blockchain Technology. "Blockchain technology has emerged as a major change across various industries, and the world of sports is no exception. From enhancing fan engagement to ensuring transparency in ticket and merchandise sales, blockchain has the potential to revolutionize how we experience and manage sports." (Yellowbrick, 2023)

Enhancing Fan Engagement. Blockchain technology significantly impacts the way fans connect with their favorite teams and athletes. Through blockchain platforms, fans can experience unique opportunities, such as owning digital collectibles, accessing exclusive content, or even owning virtual shares in sports teams. This technology not only strengthens the connection between fans and teams but also creates new revenue sources for sports organizations.

Transparency in Ticket and Merchandise Sales. Issues like ticket fraud and counterfeit merchandise have long been present in sports. Blockchain can resolve these problems by providing a secure and transparent platform for ticket and merchandise sales. By using blockchain technology, sports organizations can guarantee the authenticity of their products and tickets, reducing the risk of fraud and preserving brand reputation.

Smart Contracts and Player Management. Blockchain can simplify the creation and management of player contracts. Smart contracts enable automatic management of various aspects of contracts, such as payment terms, performance incentives, and royalty distribution. These contracts are transparent, secure, and enforceable, reducing the need for intermediaries and minimizing the risk of disputes, benefiting both players and sports organizations.

Tracking Athlete Performance. Blockchain technology can enhance the tracking and analysis of athlete performance. By integrating wearable devices and IoT sensors with blockchain, sports organizations can securely collect and store performance data. This data can help optimize training, identify injury risks, and improve overall performance. Blockchain also ensures athlete data privacy, giving them control over their own information.

Secure and Transparent Betting. The multi-billion-dollar sports betting industry often faces problems like fraud and lack of transparency. Blockchain can introduce trust and integrity into betting. By recording all transactions on a distributed ledger, blockchain ensures transparency and prevents manipulation. Smart contracts can automate payouts, ensuring timely winnings without disputes.

Anti-Doping Measures. Preserving clean and fair sports is crucial. Blockchain technology can help combat doping by creating a transparent and immutable record of athlete test results. Storing these results on the blockchain prevents manipulation and ensures the integrity of testing, protecting athletes' reputations and maintaining fair competition.

In conclusion, blockchain technology has the potential to significantly transform the sports industry by enhancing fan engagement, ensuring transparency in ticket and merchandise sales, simplifying contract management, improving athlete performance tracking, securing betting, and supporting anti-doping measures.

The Future of Technology in Sports. As sports evolve and become increasingly dynamic, technological innovations play a key role in its transformation. From smart devices that enable precise performance tracking to advanced analytical tools that guide strategies, to new digital experiences that engage fans in unprecedented ways, technology in sports promises exciting changes. In this context, the future of technology in sports holds the promise of further evolution and improvements that will not only enhance athletes' performance and team efficiency but also redefine how all participants in sports, from players to spectators, experience the game. Below are some potential future applications.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning. The development of artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms and machine learning is focused on analyzing large amounts of data, which improves training programs and strategies. Advancements in semiconductor technology contribute to the development of sensors, data analysis, and connectivity. To achieve efficient data processing, fast and robust AI chips are required. Electronic design automation (EDA) tools enhanced with AI technologies, such as Cadence SPICE simulation software, facilitate faster circuit design. Cadence supports rapid design creation and

verification, critical emulation, and prototyping, and offers Cadence Tensilica HiFi DSP for efficient AI processing in compact electronics.

Virtual and Augmented Reality. Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies have the potential to significantly change athlete training and fan engagement. VR could allow athletes to simulate various match scenarios, enabling them to practice strategies and improve decision-making in a simulated environment. On the other hand, AR could enrich the fan experience by displaying real-time statistics and interactive elements during live matches, enhancing their understanding and enjoyment of the sport. These technologies promise a significant transformation in the way athletes train and in the way sports events are viewed.

Smart Fabrics. Advanced fabrics containing sensors to track various physiological parameters, such as heart rate, body temperature, and muscle activity, are being developed. These smart fabrics can provide real-time feedback on athletes' performance, helping to prevent injuries and optimize training routines. By continuously monitoring and analyzing data, these fabrics have the potential to significantly improve the way athletes train, providing personalized insights and enabling better decisions for performance enhancement and health management.

CONCLUSION

Technology has become a key factor in modern sports, significantly influencing the way sports are followed, analyzed, and understood. This paper explored how technological innovations have shaped sports, starting from early achievements such as video analysis and heart rate monitors to contemporary solutions like VAR (Video Assistant Referee), artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR), and nanotechnology.

Previous technological advancements, such as Instant Replay and Hawk-Eye technology, laid the foundation for more advanced systems. Instant Replay allowed for the re-examination of controversial moments in real time, improving the accuracy of decisions, while Hawk-Eye revolutionized ball tracking in sports like tennis and cricket, enabling precise analysis of ball movement. Goal-Line Technology (GLT) further enhanced fairness in football by accurately detecting goals.

The paper also discussed the application of contemporary technologies in detail. For instance, VAR has significantly reduced the number of controversial decisions in football by analyzing key moments from different angles. Semi-automated offside technology (SAOT) uses cameras and sensors to precisely determine the position of players in relation to the defensive line, further increasing decision accuracy.

Artificial intelligence and data analytics enable detailed monitoring and analysis of athletes' performances. AI can predict injuries by analyzing patterns in athletes' physical data, while data analytics help coaches adjust training and strategies. Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) provide innovative methods for training simulation and rehabilitation, while nanotechnology offers new materials and technologies for improving equipment and apparel.

In conclusion, the paper highlights that technology not only improves sports practices and fan experience but also opens new possibilities for the future of sports. The integration of these technological innovations enables continuous progress in the sports sector, providing better performance analysis, enhanced training, and more accurate decision-making. Understanding and applying these technologies

is key to the further development of sports, laying the groundwork for innovations and commercialization in this dynamic field.

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FARMERS' PREFERENCES FOR DIFFERENT FINANCIAL PRODUCT VALUES OFFERED BY COMMERCIAL BANKS IN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

This study applies the Fishbein Model to analyze farmers' preferences for financial products offered by commercial banks. The research identifies key attributes influencing farmers' attitudes, including loan repayment period, collateral flexibility, interest rates, initial disbursement, and business consulting services. A survey was conducted among 33 farmers, utilizing a Likert scale to quantify preferences. Based on these findings, recommendations are provided for banks to improve their financial product offerings, such as extending repayment periods, increasing loan disbursement amounts, offering flexible collateral options, and enhancing advisory services. These insights help commercial banks optimize financial products tailored to agricultural sector needs.

KEYWORDS: preferences, financial product, commercial banks

ABSTRAKT

Diese Studie wendet das Fishbein-Modell an, um die Präferenzen der Landwirte für die von Geschäftsbanken angebotenen Finanzprodukte zu analysieren. Die Studie identifiziert Schlüsselattribute, die die Einstellung der Landwirte beeinflussen, darunter die Kreditrückzahlungsdauer, die Flexibilität der Sicherheiten, die Zinssätze, die anfängliche Auszahlung und die Unternehmensberatung. Es wurde eine Umfrage unter 33 Landwirten durchgeführt, wobei eine Likert-Skala zur Quantifizierung der Präferenzen verwendet wurde. Auf der Grundlage dieser Ergebnisse werden den Banken Empfehlungen zur Verbesserung ihres Finanzproduktangebots gegeben, wie z. B. die Verlängerung der Rückzahlungsfristen, die Erhöhung der Kreditauszahlungsbeträge, das Angebot flexibler Sicherheiten und die Verbesserung der Beratungsdienste. Diese Erkenntnisse helfen den Geschäftsbanken, Finanzprodukte zu optimieren, die auf die Bedürfnisse des Agrarsektors zugeschnitten sind.

STICHWORTE: Präferenzen, Finanzprodukte, Geschäftsbanken

RÉSUMÉ

Cette étude applique le modèle de Fishbein pour analyser les préférences des agriculteurs en matière de produits financiers offerts par les banques commerciales. La recherche identifie les attributs clés qui influencent les attitudes des agriculteurs, y compris la période de remboursement du prêt, la flexibilité des garanties, les taux d'intérêt, le décaissement initial et les services de conseil aux entreprises. Une enquête a été menée auprès de 33 agriculteurs, utilisant une échelle de Likert pour quantifier les préférences. Sur la base de ces résultats, des recommandations sont formulées pour que les banques améliorent leur offre de produits financiers, notamment en allongeant les périodes de remboursement,

en augmentant les montants des prêts, en offrant des options de garantie flexibles et en améliorant les services de conseil. Ces informations aident les banques commerciales à optimiser les produits financiers adaptés aux besoins du secteur agricole.

MOTS-CLÉS: préférences, produits financiers, banques commerciales

INTRODUCTION

The financial sector plays a crucial role in supporting agricultural activities by providing farmers with essential financial products such as loans, credit lines, savings accounts, and insurance. Understanding farmers' preferences towards these financial products is vital for commercial banks to design tailored offerings that meet their specific needs. This literature review examines key factors influencing farmers' financial preferences, including accessibility, interest rates, loan conditions, and risk management features. It also explores the role of financial literacy, government interventions, and technological advancements in shaping farmers' choices.

1. Factors Influencing Farmers' Financial Product Preferences. Accessibility is a major determinant in farmers' preference for financial products. Research indicates that rural farmers often face challenges in accessing formal banking services due to inadequate banking infrastructure, lengthy application processes, and stringent collateral requirements (Kumar & Singh, 2019). Mobile banking and digital financial services have emerged as effective solutions to bridge this gap, enabling farmers to conduct transactions remotely and access financial services more conveniently (Munyegera & Matsumoto, 2016).

2. Interest Rates and Loan Conditions. The cost of credit, particularly interest rates and repayment terms, significantly influences farmers' borrowing decisions. Studies show that farmers prefer loan products with lower interest rates, flexible repayment schedules, and longer loan tenures to accommodate seasonal income fluctuations (Carter et al., 2021). Additionally, microfinance institutions and agricultural cooperatives often provide more favorable terms compared to commercial banks, making them a preferred alternative for small-scale farmers (Adebayo & Anyanwu, 2018).

3. Risk Management and Insurance. Agricultural production is inherently risky due to unpredictable weather conditions, market volatility, and pest infestations. As a result, financial products that include risk-mitigation components, such as crop insurance and weather-indexed loans, tend to be more attractive to farmers (Dercon & Christiaensen, 2019). Research also suggests that farmers who have experienced financial losses in the past are more likely to prioritize risk protection when selecting financial products (Giné & Yang, 2020).

4. Financial Literacy and Awareness. Farmers' understanding of financial products and their benefits influences their adoption rates. Several studies highlight the importance of financial education programs in increasing farmers' confidence in utilizing banking services (Cole et al., 2017). Farmers with higher financial literacy levels are more likely to diversify their financial portfolios, invest in savings schemes, and opt for insurance products (Zeller & Sharma, 2019).

5. Government Policies and Subsidies. Government policies and support programs play a crucial role in shaping farmers' preferences for financial products. Subsidized credit schemes, interest rate waivers, and loan guarantee programs encourage farmers to engage with commercial banks (Binswanger & Khandker, 2018). However, concerns about bureaucratic inefficiencies and delays in subsidy disbursements often deter farmers from fully utilizing such schemes (Meyer et al., 2020).

6. Technological Advancements and Digital Banking. The rise of fintech solutions and digital banking platforms has revolutionized the financial landscape for farmers. Studies show that mobile money services, blockchain-based financial products, and artificial intelligence-driven credit scoring systems enhance farmers' access to credit and banking facilities (Jack & Suri, 2016). Farmers in developing countries are increasingly adopting digital payment systems, reducing their dependence on cash transactions and improving financial inclusion (Beck et al., 2019).

Methodology of research

The Fishbein model is used at the survey. The model is one of the most popular for studying consumer needs. The so-called multi-attribute need models assume that a consumer's attitude toward an object depends on the beliefs they hold about several or many attributes of the examined object. The use of a multi-attribute model means that attitudes toward a company, product, or brand can be predicted by identifying these competitive beliefs and combining them to derive data on the overall consumer need for the objects.

Step 1. Purpose of the model. The first step is to establish the goal of using the Fishbein Model. In this case, the objective is to evaluate **farmers' preferences** towards different financial products offered by commercial banks based on various attributes.

Step 2. Identifying the Key Attributes of Financial Products. Since the Fishbein Model is a **multi-attribute model**, it requires identifying the relevant **attributes** that influence farmers' attitudes toward financial products. Common attributes might include. The attributes were selected based on expert opinions and literature review.

Step 3. Survey to Collect Farmers' Preferences. We design a survey where farmers evaluate each financial product based on the identified attributes. A Likert scale (e.g., 1 to 6) is used for rating satisfaction levels: 1 – Completely dissatisfied: 2 – Slightly dissatisfied: 3 – Neutral: 4 – Slightly satisfied: 5 – Mostly satisfied: 6 – Completely satisfied. Each farmer rates each attribute for each bank's financial product using this scale.

Step 4. Assigning Importance Weights (Ik) to Each Attribute. Not all attributes have the same level of importance to farmers. The survey ask farmers to rate the **importance (Ik)** of each attribute on a scale (e.g., 1 to 6). This ensures that more important attributes have a greater impact on the final attitude score.

Step 5. Compute the Belief Score (βijk) for Each Attribute. Each farmer assigns a **belief score (βijk)**, which represents how well they think a **specific financial product from a bank satisfies a given attribute**. For example, if a farmer believes that **Bank X offers a very attractive interest rate**, they might assign it **βijk = 5**, while **Bank Y's interest rate** might be considered **less attractive**, resulting in **βijk = 3**.

Step 6: Apply the Fishbein Model Formula. The overall **attitude score (Aijk)** for each **financial product** is calculated using the formula:

$$A_{ijk} = \sum (\beta_{ijk} \times I_k) A_{ijk}$$

where:

i = Attribute (e.g., loan amount, repayment period, etc.)

j = Financial product (e.g., Bank X's loan)

k = Farmer/respondent

Ik = Importance weight of attribute **i** assigned by farmer **k**

βijk = Belief score assigned by farmer **k** for how well financial product **j** meets attribute **i**

Aijk = Total attitude score for financial product j

This formula is **calculated for each financial product from each bank.**

By filling out the supercard, two useful results are achieved. First, the card identifies the most significant attitudes from farmers' perspectives when deciding on a financial product offered by a commercial bank. Second, it defines the key benchmarks for designing financial products in the future and the positioning strategy to be used.

Sample Selection. The sample was derived from the registry of farmers, where all agricultural producers voluntarily register. As of December 31, 2023, the total number of registered farmers was 99,441. A random sampling method was applied, resulting in a sample of 33 farmers engaged primarily in agricultural production.

Farmers' Financial Needs as Business Entities Beyond their household roles, farmers also have financial needs as business entities involved in agricultural production. This section of the dissertation analyzes the financial products offered by commercial banks to farmers and assesses how well these products align with farmers' preferences. Additionally, the level of differentiation in financial products and how well this differentiation reflects farmers' financial needs is examined.

Table 1. Survey Card for Assessing Farmers' Attitudes Towards Financial Products. Own interpretation.

Attribute	Importance	Commercial Bank "X"	Commercial Bank "Y"	Commercial Bank "Z"
Proposed loan amount				
Initial disbursed amount				
Loan purpose				
Currency in which the loan is granted				
Loan repayment period				
Loan repayment interest rate				
Availability of a grace period				
Processing fee for loan applications				
Loan management commission				
Early repayment commission				
Loan repayment method (number of installments and options for repayment via subsidies or other loans)				
Type of collateral (type of pledge)				
Requirement for a guarantor				
Requirement for insurance				
Availability of business consulting services from the bank				
Overall Attitude Score (Aijk)				

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The primary financial products offered by commercial banks for agricultural needs are presented in Table 1. Farmers assessed the financial products available on the market according to predefined attributes, defined and justified in the methodological section of the dissertation. The survey, completed by 33 farmers, determined the overall scores for each attribute. The assessment results are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Importance Ratings of Financial Product Attributes. Source: Survey of 33 farmers, 2024

Farmers ranked the following six attributes as the most important:

Loan repayment period – Rated highest with 84 points. Farmers prioritize the repayment period when seeking a loan. The longer the repayment period, the more attractive the financial product.

Possibility of loan guarantee – Rated 83 points. Farmers prefer loans secured by subsidies or other grant instruments provided by the Agricultural Fund.

Type of collateral – Rated 79 points. Many commercial banks require collateral, such as pledging future subsidies or agricultural land.

Initial disbursed amount – Rated 77 points. Farmers prefer receiving 100% of the loan amount in the first disbursement to ensure liquidity.

Business consulting services – Rated 76 points. Only five out of 23 commercial banks offer free business consulting.

The least important attributes were:

Currency of the loan – Rated 33 points, as long as the interest rate and repayment terms are acceptable.

Requirement for a guarantor – Rated 38 points, considered less significant.

Findings and Conclusions The market for financial products for farmers has been steadily growing in recent years, both in the number and value of loans issued.

Large commercial banks with substantial assets generate the most profit from agricultural financial services, leading to market monopolization.

Commercial banks that segment farmers as a distinct market and offer tailored financial products achieve better profitability.

A well-defined positioning strategy significantly impacts sales effectiveness and profitability.

The most important financial product attributes for farmers are loan repayment period, loan guarantee, type of collateral, initial loan disbursement, and business consulting services.

The four most reputable banks offering financial products that best meet farmers' needs are DSK Bank, Eurobank, UniCredit Bulbank, and Investbank.

CONCLUSION

This analysis confirms that commercial banks with well-developed strategies for financial products tailored to farmers achieve higher market success. The ability to use agricultural subsidies as collateral remains a key factor for success in the financial services market for agriculture.

The Fishbein Model results indicate the following recommendations for commercial banks:

- Focus on Loan Repayment Period and Collateral Flexibility: Given that these are the most valued attributes, banks should offer longer repayment periods and flexible collateral options, such as allowing farmers to pledge agricultural subsidies as security.
- Enhance Loan Disbursement Policies: Farmers prefer receiving the entire loan amount upfront to improve liquidity. Banks should consider providing higher initial disbursements rather than staggered payouts.
- Increase Availability of Business Consulting Services: Only a few banks offer free business consulting, yet farmers find this valuable. Banks should invest in financial advisory services tailored to agricultural needs.

- Improve Competitive Positioning on Interest Rates and Fees: While farmers prioritize loan terms over currency type, banks should remain competitive in interest rates and processing fees to attract more clients.
- Strengthen Market Segmentation Strategies: Banks that target farmers as a distinct market segment and design customized financial products perform better. Expanding personalized financial solutions will enhance customer loyalty and satisfaction.

These strategies will help banks improve their offerings and increase their market share in agricultural financing while better addressing farmers' financial needs.

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MARKETING MANAGEMENT OF PRODUCTION. THEORITICAL ASPECTS AND DETERMINANTS

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ABSTRACT

The modern business environment is characterized by a high degree of uncertainty and turbulence. In order for the business organization to cope in the conditions of such a dynamic environment, higher requirements are placed on its management, such as - the business is considered as an "open" system, where the main factors for its success are sought outside it and its success is associated with how well it adapts to the business environment. To achieve the set goals, the business must direct its activity to the consumer, to his needs and desires, adopting the marketing concept of management. Putting the marketing management concept into practice begins with formulating a company's marketing strategy.

KEYWORDS: marketing, management, business, business model

ABSTRAKT

Das moderne Unternehmensumfeld ist durch ein hohes Maß an Unsicherheit und Turbulenz gekennzeichnet. Damit ein Unternehmen unter den Bedingungen eines solchen dynamischen Umfelds bestehen kann, werden höhere Anforderungen an sein Management gestellt, wie z.B. - das Unternehmen wird als „offenes“ System betrachtet, bei dem die Hauptfaktoren für seinen Erfolg außerhalb des Unternehmens gesucht werden und sein Erfolg davon abhängt, wie gut es sich an das Unternehmensumfeld anpasst. Um die gesetzten Ziele zu erreichen, muss das Unternehmen seine Tätigkeit auf den Verbraucher, seine Bedürfnisse und Wünsche ausrichten und das Marketingkonzept des Managements übernehmen. Die Umsetzung des Marketing-Management-Konzepts in die Praxis beginnt mit der Formulierung der Marketingstrategie eines Unternehmens.

STICHWORTE: Marketing, Management, Unternehmen, Geschäftsmodell

RÉSUMÉ

L'environnement commercial moderne se caractérise par un degré élevé d'incertitude et de turbulence. Pour que l'organisation commerciale puisse faire face aux conditions d'un environnement aussi dynamique, des exigences plus élevées sont imposées à sa gestion, telles que - l'entreprise est considérée comme un système « ouvert », où les principaux facteurs de son succès sont recherchés en dehors d'elle et où son succès est associé à la manière dont elle s'adapte à l'environnement commercial. Pour atteindre les objectifs fixés, l'entreprise doit orienter son activité vers le consommateur, ses besoins et ses désirs, en adoptant le concept de gestion marketing. La mise en pratique du concept de gestion marketing commence par la formulation de la stratégie marketing de l'entreprise.

MOTS-CLÉS: marketing, gestion, entreprise, modèle d'entreprise

INTRODUCTION

The modern market is saturated with supply and competition between manufacturers is fierce. Under these conditions, the improvement of production management is a continuous activity. P. Penchev defines the following interrelated directions in which the improvement of management takes place:

- 1) improvement of the production and organizational-management structure;
- 2) improvement of management approaches and methods;
- 3) improvement of the information technology base for management;
- 4) improving leadership style, social climate, etc.

These guidelines help to increase the quality of management, which results in the efficient functioning of the business. In the current development, emphasis is placed on improving the management approaches used in the wine industry. "Management can be defined as a purposeful way of influencing the behavior of a certain business to reach pre-formulated goals"(Angelov, 1998). This impact is realized through the management decisions taken, in the formulation of which modern organizations focus not on the internal environment, but on its interactions with the external environment. A significant change in management thought and practice occurred in business management with the emergence of the marketing concept of management.

"The marketing concept of management is expressed in the constant search for the best ratio between the demands of consumers, on the one hand, and the company's desire to obtain a higher profit, on the other" (Trendafilov, R., A. Simova. Agromarketing. Bolid, 2000). "The marketing concept is not a second definition of marketing. It is a way of thinking - a managerial philosophy for the overall activity of the business. This philosophy affects the entire operation of the business, not just marketing activities" (Pride, W. Marketing: Concepts and Strategies. Farcom, 1994).

The main advantage of marketing management is to focus attention on the processes from the positions of the market in order to comply with its requirements as much as possible (Borisov and Radev, 2020). Such conscious coordination and coordination of economic activity with the activity of surrounding economic entities can increase its efficiency. For a business to succeed, its managers must recognize these external forces, understand the interrelationships between them, and understand what their actual and potential impact is on the business. First of all, managers must manage the business so as to minimize the negative effect of the impact of external environmental factors and maximize their positive effect on the business. In order to achieve this, it is necessary to adopt a systematic approach. It "is a working concept by which we can understand how something works. This approach moves us away from thinking that the things in our lives are separate, isolated entities and directs us to see them as a set of interconnected components working together to support each other and achieve different goals. The closest example of a system is the human body, which is made up of various interacting organs. When all the organs work together, we are healthy. But if the interaction between them breaks down, we get sick." (Bound, 1995). Adopting this approach, Dimitrov considers business as a system composed of smaller elements and at the same time as part of a larger system with the following common points:

- the production system consists of material and personal elements that are interconnected and arranged (in time and space) in a strictly defined way
- the system is an element of a larger, more complex system, and each of its elements is lower rank system

- the system is in continuous, dynamic interaction with the external (surrounding) environment
- in the system, interaction between the elements is ensured and implemented, aimed at achieving certain goals.

This approach is also used by Penchev, who considers business as an "open" system that is constantly in interaction with other economic and socio-political organizations and private individuals from the external environment. "The open system concept means that organizations and individuals can interact with an unlimited number of other organizations and individuals. These interactions can reveal opportunities, threats, or both. If these interactions are not controlled, or worse, if the key actors are not identified early enough, then there may not be time for the business to respond through its strengths and/or change its weaknesses." (Ward, 1995). Examining business as a system Savov singles out the following three concrete levels of system hierarchization. Physical (machines) and biological (living organisms) systems belong to the lowest level, and their combination gives a system of a higher level - the production system, and the result of the combination of production systems is the macroeconomic system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Every business exists in a certain external environment. Also called business environment, environment, surrounding environment, it is the one that predetermines business opportunities. It contains many entities - consumers, competitors, suppliers, intermediaries, government institutions, etc., with which the business is in continuous contact, and there is a two-way interaction between the business and the business environment. The business environment affects the business through its input, and through its output it affects the business environment. Many signals (variables) arrive at the input - information, production resources, legal restrictions, etc., which, by means of a production process, are transformed into some product, which is realized in the business environment through the output.

Here the question arises as to what variables, in what quantitative and qualitative ratio, should enter through the input of the production system. This choice can be determined by various factors, but in all cases the result of it (the company product) is the one that will give the most accurate and true answer for its correctness. The product is the one that combines all incoming input signals that become elements of the internal environment.

"The internal environment of the business is a set of all the components, integrated and interconnected within it, which function together to achieve its goals. These components are called "internal variables", "controllable variables", etc." (Ivanov, 1999). Individual authors define the content of the internal environment differently. Iv. Ivanov defines the main internal variables as goals, collaborators, structure, technology and tasks. According to P. Penchev enterprise unites material, human and financial resources in order to produce certain goods. The consulting company McKinsey presents the 7 S's of a successful business (strategy, structure, system, style, staff, skills and shared values) as its internal environment. Another author V. Savov defines business as a set of workers united by a common goal and using relevant technical means, raw materials, materials, technologies and information and a certain organization of labor to create finished products or services under the guidance of management bodies. Giving this broader definition, the author also shares a second one, according to which business is the unity and integration of object and subject of management, where both object and

subject are people. Thus, the various internal elements are separated into two large systems (governing and managed), making up the internal environment of the business, again emphasizing the human resource.

"Or, as the famous American researcher Chester Bernard, one of the classics in the field of management, claims, "business" - it is a group of people whose activities are consciously coordinated to achieve a common goal or goals." (Angelov, 1998).

Other authors Ir. Slavova and V. Blagoev use the functional approach in determining the internal environment. In it, internal factors are qualified by functional areas: marketing, finance, production, personnel, organization and management. Such an approach is also used by M. Porter in his proposed "value chain", according to which every economic business performs multiple activities. These activities express its internal environment and are divided into two groups - core activities (inbound logistics, production, outbound logistics, marketing and sales, after-sales service) and supporting activities (company infrastructure, human resource management, technological development, supplies).

Regardless of how internal elements are defined, all authors agree that they need to be managed. Since there is no control at all, it is always associated with specific objects, all internal elements can be defined as control elements. In each economic unit, a management process takes place, i.e. "a series of continuous and interconnected actions. We call these actions management functions. These are planning, organizing, leading and controlling" (Angelov, 1998). These functions are implemented in every single element of the internal environment of the business, which we define using the functional approach. The main advantage of this approach is expressed in the fact that each functional area has its own specific characteristics and peculiarities, which is why knowledge and competences from the relevant area are needed in the implementation of management functions. The control elements and functions are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Elements and functions of control. Source: own interpretation.

According to Pride and Ferrell, managerial functions in marketing management have the following content.

"Planning is a systematic process that focuses on evaluating opportunities and resources, defining marketing objectives, developing marketing strategy, and developing implementation and control plans. Planning determines when and how the marketing activity will be carried out and who will carry it out.

The organization of marketing activities includes development and internal marketing unit structure. A marketing unit can be organized by product function, region, or consumer type (Borisov and Radev, 2020).

Proper execution of marketing plans depends on coordination of marketing activities, motivation of marketing personnel and effective communication within the unit.

The marketing control process consists of establishing standards and evaluating the actual condition by comparing it with the established standards and by reducing the differences between desired and actual performance."

When managing the elements of management, all authors agree that, according to the content, management is: strategic, current and operational. "Strategic management defines the main goal, the development strategy of the business. Current management focuses on managing current tasks related to business tactics and policy. Operational management is a concretization of management in space and time." Based on these definitions, we can summarize that strategic management has a long-term nature and covers the largest period of time compared to current and operational management, which in turn must ensure its implementation through a series of short-term actions. Strategic management is "management of improvement in a long-term perspective", which is carried out through the development and implementation of strategies. Strategic management of a company's marketing activities requires a marketing strategy.

It has already been mentioned that the business (considered as a system) is in continuous, dynamic interaction with the external (environment) environment and that there is an interaction between its elements aimed at achieving certain goals. But we are looking for an answer to the question of how these interactions are carried out, on what principles their management is based.

Setting a goal (goals) is a starting point not only for economic activity, but also for any other activity in human society. "A goal can be defined as a desired result or some specific state to which a group strives as the people in it work together." We share the view of Drucker that there is only one true definition of the purpose of business, namely to create a customer. "The customer is the basis of the business, supporting its existence. He alone creates work. And it is to satisfy the customer that society entrusts wealth-reproducing resources to the business enterprise."

What must be penetrated into the mind of the entrepreneur is that his work, initiative and risk are meaningful only in the presence of market recognition?

It is important for all businessmen to understand that the purpose of industry is not the production of goods, but the satisfaction of consumer needs. The starting point for business is the buyer and their needs and wants, not technology or sales experience.

Although we completely agree with the cited authors, we cannot fail to take into account the opinion of another group of authors that business is designed to bring profit and who support the theory of "maximizing profit". Although the theory itself is losing more and more of its supporters, the need to make a profit is indisputable. But profit is seen as a reward, a reward for the actions of business in

satisfying consumer needs. Profit is also a necessary prerequisite for the further development of the business. Between these two seemingly divergent goals, a balance needs to be established, which can be achieved by adopting the marketing concept of management. With it, the consumer is placed at the center of the business, every economic activity begins and ends with him, and marketing is that element of the internal environment that establishes the relationship with the consumer (the consumer's place in the business is presented in Figure 2). The relationship between the company and the consumer is two-way - from the consumer to the company and from the company to the consumer. In the first case (user → company) there are two flows - informational and monetary. The information flow provides the company with information about the wishes of the user, about what he values when making a decision for purchase, who makes the purchase decision itself, where the product is consumed, etc. The second flow (cash) is not only a source of income (income) of the company, but also shows how the consumer has valued the company's product, through his willingness to pay a certain price for it. The other relationship (firm→consumer) is expressed through the firm's product. The product moves from the company to the consumer, characterized by its qualities, appearance, price, promotion, place of supply, etc., which attract the consumer and associate him with the company.

Figure 2. Place of the users in the business. Source: own interpretation.

Accepting the consumer as the center of any economic system, we consider him as the most obvious exponent of the company's product market. In fact, in the center is precisely the market, which, in addition to the characteristics of the consumer, is identified with many other elements - competitors, suppliers, intermediaries, substitute goods, technological, economic, social and other environments. Each of these elements has an impact on the company, which finds expression in the characteristics of the

company product. The transformation of input variables into outputs according to market requirements means that the firm has adopted the marketing concept of management as its business philosophy. The implementation of this concept in practice takes place through the development and implementation of the company's marketing strategy. It accumulates in itself all the characteristics of the market, and more precisely how they are evaluated by the managers of the company. The marketing strategy shows how the company will work in a given market (it is the link between the company and the consumer), but at the same time it sets the requirements that must be covered by the internal company environment (here it appears as a coordinating element) in order to realize the desired interaction company- user ie to achieve company goals.

In the economic literature, there are many classifications of marketing strategies, the most famous of which are: the strategies determined by the product-market relationship (the so-called Ansoff matrix); the competitive strategies of M. Porter; military strategies in marketing introduced by F. Kotler on describing conflict situations; strategies based on market segmentation; marketing strategies according to the type of firm that implements them.

The Ansoff matrix represents the "market-product" relationship as follows (Figure 3). Based on it, the company can choose among the following four strategies:

-market penetration strategy - involves increasing the volume of sales of existing goods, in the current market, by encouraging current customers to buy more, by attracting customers from competitors, or by persuading non-users to start buying it. This strategy can be used in view of the low consumption of honey per head of population for Bulgaria, the existing reserves in terms of increasing efficiency when applying international marketing in their activity.

	current product	new product
current market	strategy penetration market	strategy product development
new market	strategy development market	strategy diversification

Figure 3. Ansoff matrix. Source: own interpretation.

- market development strategy - in this strategy, the existing products are offered in new markets, and new markets do not mean only their geographical dimension, but this can be the satisfaction of new needs with the same products. This strategy is revalidated by entering new geographic markets, developing new market segments.

- product development strategy - in this strategy, the company offers to the existing markets new products that belong to the same product group, most often different modifications to satisfy the needs of a larger number of users from different market segments. It is suitable for productive enterprises, by offering new products that have not been produced until now.

-diversification strategy - it implies simultaneous entry into new markets and new industries. There are the following four types of diversification strategies: 1) concentric diversification – the company offers new products that have technological or marketing similarity with its existing product lines, but the products themselves attract the attention of a different group of customers. It is applicable in winemaking through the production of other alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages; 2) vertical diversification - suppliers often do not meet the quality requirements of raw materials, materials and equipment. In this case, the company can absorb their production. Another way by which winemakers can secure the quality raw material they need, and also to overcome the negative trend in the age structure of the vineyards; 3) horizontal diversification - the company can focus on the production of goods that are not related to the currently used technologies, but are bought by the same consumers; 4) conglomerate (corporate) diversification - the company can look for new businesses that have no connection with the company's current technologies, products or markets. Its practical importance is expressed in reducing the risk of narrowly specialized production, which makes it applicable in every single industry.

Strategies developed on the basis of the Ansoff matrix have two main advantages. First, they are easy to use, as no further explanation of their nature is needed, and second, they represent how the two main variables will develop - the markets that will be worked on and what products will be offered. Therefore, these strategies can be defined as baselines, creating an opportunity to subsequently develop strategies that emphasize other important market factors.

Such an opportunity is provided by the competitive strategies of M. Porter, which are developed based on the company's competitive advantages. According to M. Porter competitive advantage can be marketing (external) advantage and cost advantage (internal). "Competitive advantage is marketing when it is based on distinctive qualities of the product that constitute value for the buyer either by reducing his costs of using it or by increasing the results of using it. Competitive advantage is cost (internal) when it is based on a firm's superiority in the level of costs of manufacturing and marketing the product." (Stoyanov, 1999)

Based on these two competitive advantages M. Porter formulated the following strategies: leadership (of the company) in terms of total costs, differentiation (individuation) and focus. Cost leadership - here the business works to achieve the lowest production and distribution costs so that it can offer lower prices than the competition and capture a larger market share. Firms implementing this strategy must be good at engineering, procurement, manufacturing and physical distribution. The problem is that competitors with even lower costs can emerge and hurt a company that has staked its entire future on cost leadership. Differentiation - here the business focuses on achieving superior results in some important area of customer benefit, such as being a leader in service, quality, design or technology - but not a leader in all of these areas. In winemaking, the strategy finds expression in the production of wine with guaranteed origin. Focusing - here the business focuses on one or several narrow market segments, gets to know these segments well and seeks either cost leadership or differentiation within the target segment. It is also suitable for wineries, by serving a certain segment of the market.

Formulated in this way, these strategies require that the market in which the company will operate, as well as the product that will be offered, be determined in advance, since the emphasis in them is on the competition, i.e. on what basis bidders will compete. That's why we believe that the strategies presented by Ansoff and M. Porter complement each other and it is appropriate to use them together.

Another attempt to present the ways in which it is possible to conduct a competitive struggle was made by F. Kotler, through his proposed two types of military strategies – offensive and defensive. Attackers attack: Frontal attack - it attacks the strengths of the competitor. Such a strategy requires significant resources for its implementation. Flank attack – the competitor company is attacked in some of its weak areas, for example a market segment in which the competitor works poorly. Roundabout attack - is a combination of frontal and flanking attack. Attack on other segments – in practice, this is the introduction of new products and/or entry into new markets. Guerrilla tactics - includes a set of actions related to temporary difficulties for the competitor, which in their entirety lead to negatives for him. Defensive strategies: Positional warfare - the same means used by the attacking firm are used. Counterattack - two types: the preliminary strike, when we nullify the attacker's actions before they have had an effect, and the counterattack, when the competitor has started some action and we respond with a nullifying move. Flank defense - this strategy is based on complementing our offer with new capabilities that neutralize potential attacks from competitors. Multi-level defense - implies the development of the company in other market segments and with other products and brands, so that it is not completely dependent on one product or market. Attack in another direction (strategic retreat) - when the company does not have an advantage to defend and/or cannot maintain the occupied market positions.

Although these strategies present in an interesting way the approaches to conducting a competitive struggle, they lack specification of the means through which it will be conducted. The author has presented rather broad limits in which company capabilities move, which can create difficulties in their construction and use.

The next approach to the classification of marketing strategies is based on market segmentation and defines the following three possible strategies: 1) Undifferentiated (mass) marketing – entering the target market with a single strategy aimed at the mass consumer; targets a large, extensive market. 2) Differentiated marketing - the company seeks to present itself to two or more defined segments of the market with a marketing strategy developed for each of them. 3) Concentrated marketing - the company seeks to present itself to a well-defined market segment with a specific marketing strategy. Although this approach is based on one of the main variables (the market), it does not create prerequisites for projecting the company's growth and is suitable for generally determining the directions of the company's activities. Another approach is widely advocated in the economic literature, according to which marketing strategies are classified based on the market position of companies. These strategies can be: market leaders' strategy; contenders' strategy for better market positions; next market strategy; niche market strategy. "Strategy of market leaders. It is applied when a large market share (40%) has been achieved, when sales are growing rapidly and the desire of the company is to preserve the achieved positions. This strategy allows for various means to achieve the goal - product innovations, distribution channels, use of prices that upset the competitor and are unbearable for him, etc. Contenders strategy for better market positions. It is preferred by companies that are not among the leaders, but have ambitions and opportunities to gain better positions in the market, and challenges of a different nature and against different competitors can be fruitful for them. This strategy includes such strategic moves as the low price strategy, introducing new products that would stimulate new needs, improving service, expanding and improving advertising, etc. Challenges can refer both to companies with great competitive power and occupying leadership positions, as vulnerabilities have been established in their positions, as well as to

weak competitors, from whose market "territories" can be taken away. Next Market Strategy. It is preferred by companies that do not have a large market share, but, although without pretensions to expand their presence, can improve their profitability. Their strategy in its general form can be characterized as protectionist, reduced to the defense of the occupied position, but it is not simply defensive in nature. By using different means of the marketing mix, both the expansion of existing markets and the conquest of new markets and new customers can be pursued. Niche strategy. It is applied by companies that have a small market share - for example up to 10%, and are interested in small market niches that large companies ignore. In many cases, these strategies rely on an orientation towards specialization as a means of increasing profits and stabilizing market positions" (Andreeva, 2001).

These strategies emphasize the company itself and its competitive position in the market, which is why we believe that they do not express a specific implementation strategy, but define the possible set from which to choose an appropriate strategy according to the company's market position. We also find a similarity with the military strategies of F. Kotler, since both approaches determine the possibilities of conducting a competitive struggle using other strategies (for example, those developed by Ansoff, M. Porter or strategies on individual elements of the marketing mix).

CONCLUSION

The main advantage of marketing management is to focus attention on the processes from the positions of the market in order to comply with its requirements as much as possible. Such conscious coordination and coordination of economic activity with the activity of surrounding economic entities can increase its efficiency. For a business to succeed, its managers must recognize these external forces, understand the interrelationships between them, and understand what their actual and potential impact is on the business. First of all, managers must manage the business so as to minimize the negative effect of the impact of external environmental factors and maximize their positive effect on the business. In order to achieve this, it is necessary to develop marketing strategies.

The marketing strategy shows how the company will work in a given market (it is the link between the company and the consumer), but at the same time it sets the requirements that must be covered by the internal company environment (here it appears as a coordinating element) in order to realize the desired interaction company- user ie to achieve company goals. Marketing strategies require that the market in which the company will operate, as well as the product that will be offered, be determined in advance, since the emphasis in them is on the competition, i.e. on what basis the bidders will compete. Therefore, we believe that the strategies presented by Ansoff and M. Porter complement each other and it is appropriate to use them together.

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MOTIVATIONAL APPROACHES IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

People's behavior is related to their motivational system. Depending on the economic situation, people choose one theory of motivation, changing it depending on the economic conditions. The purpose of the article is to review the basics of the most important theories that can be successfully applied to motivate people. People most often use a combination in their motivational requirements to solve the problems that arise in front of them, in order to provide for themselves and their family first of all good living conditions.

KEYWORDS: motivation theory, human resource management, needs

ABSTRAKT

Das Verhalten der Menschen hängt mit ihrem Motivationssystem zusammen. Je nach wirtschaftlicher Situation wählen die Menschen eine Motivationstheorie und ändern sie je nach den wirtschaftlichen Bedingungen. Ziel dieses Artikels ist es, einen Überblick über die Grundlagen der wichtigsten Theorien zu geben, die erfolgreich zur Motivation von Menschen eingesetzt werden können. Die Menschen verwenden meist eine Kombination von Motivationstheorien, um die Probleme zu lösen, die sich ihnen stellen, um für sich und ihre Familie vor allem gute Lebensbedingungen zu schaffen.

STICHWORTE: Motivationstheorie, Humanressourcenmanagement, Bedürfnisse

RÉSUMÉ

Le comportement des individus est lié à leur système de motivation. En fonction de la situation économique, les gens choisissent une théorie de la motivation et la modifient en fonction des conditions économiques. L'objectif de cet article est de passer en revue les bases des théories les plus importantes qui peuvent être appliquées avec succès pour motiver les gens. Le plus souvent, les gens utilisent une combinaison dans leurs exigences de motivation pour résoudre les problèmes qui se posent à eux, afin de s'assurer à eux-mêmes et à leur famille, avant tout, de bonnes conditions de vie.

MOTS-CLÉS: théorie de la motivation, gestion des ressources humaines, besoins

INTRODCUTION

People's behavior is related to their motivational system. Depending on the economic situation, people choose a certain theory of motivation, changing it depending on the economic conditions. People most often use a combination in their motivational requirements to solve the problems they face in order to achieve their goals. Motivation comes from the Latin "moveo" - "move", a reason to undertake or do something. It is the degree of willingness and choice that a person needs to commit to doing one behavior or another. A motive is something that initiates a movement; motivation is what makes people act or behave in a certain way. Motivating people is about guiding them in a certain direction and taking the

necessary steps to get them there. Being motivated means either wanting to go somewhere of your own accord, or being encouraged by any means available to set out purposefully and succeed upon your arrival. (Andreeva, 2001) Under motivation are understood those psychological processes that cause the emergence, direction and permanent reproduction of voluntary purposeful actions. Motivation is all those circumstances of inner pursuit, which are described as desires, aspirations, urges and others. It is an internal state that activates or drives motivation and relates to effort, persistence, and goals. Motivation is that network of relationships that predispose a person to act in a certain goal-directed way. Motivation is that internal state that activates, directs and sustains human behavior to achieve goals (Kamenov, 1999). The study of motivation is primarily concerned with why people act in certain ways. Motivation can be defined as the direction and duration of action. This definition is related to the question of why people choose a certain course of action and prefer it to another. A process or factors that cause people to act or behave in a certain way (Angelov, 1998). The evolution of views on motivation follows the main styles of interpreting organizational reality. The question of how to make people work well - productively, qualitatively, etc., is a major problem before the management of any business and is solved in accordance with specific organizational ideas.

The goals facing any business can only be achieved as a result of the joint work of all its personnel (Vladimirova etc, 2005). They are achieved the more effectively, the more adequately they are adapted to the external environment and the factors operating in it, the more correctly the staff is selected or their capabilities are more objectively taken into account, but also the better the personnel are motivated of the company. One of the important tasks of management is motivating people. Motivation, as a state of inner conviction to do something, is based on needs that are inside the individual and on incentives and goals that are outside of him (Ward, 1995). Needs are an intrinsic quality that engages human behavior to achieve given goals. A motive or inducement is something that initiates, causes a certain behavior in someone - behavior of action or behavior of purposeful inaction. A motivated person or a motivated person is one who voluntarily adopts and performs a certain behavior. Motivation is a desire to achieve high levels of effort in relation to organizational goals, which are conditioned by the ability of effort to satisfy some individual needs. There are two types of motivation: 1) internal motivation / "internal" is a conditional definition, since motivation is an incitement in a person's cerebral cortex and is therefore something only internal to him / - the one that arises spontaneously in people and influences their behavior; 2) external motivation / "external" is also a conditional definition / - the desire for a certain behavior, which is caused in the relevant individual under the influence or influence of other human individuals. External motivation - creating someone's desire for something, is a process in which a subject (individual or group) purposefully and successfully uses some means (stimulus) to influence a person or a group of people, i.e. upon a human object, causing it to desire to do that which is the object of the effect (Bound, 1995). Eliciting and/or maintaining extrinsic motivation is a complex process. In order for the successful manager to maintain this motivation in the people of the organization, he needs to: understand the model of the "motivation" process; to know in principle the factors determining motivation; to be aware that motivation is not just about giving someone more money to make them motivated; to understand that creating a feeling of over-satisfaction in someone can be tantamount to a state of demotivation (complacency and inertia), (Drucker, 2001). In reviews of motivation research, various

classifications of motivation theories are justified. They are divided into substantive and procedural - the former give an answer to the question of what motivates, and the latter - how to motivate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Substantive motivational theories address the fundamental question facing each individual: "What prompts, stimulates, or initiates a given behavior?". The answer to this question is related to the concept that needs drive individuals to act in a certain way. Need is considered to be an internal state of man. The need for food satisfaction (the food need), steady work (the security need), or career advancement (the promotion need) are seen as needs that prompt individuals to choose specific actions or lines of behavior. In the field of motivation, Abraham Maslow's theory, formulated by him in 1943, later gained wide fame as the "needs hierarchy theory", is the most widely recognized. The main idea in the author's theory is that a person experiences a need when he feels a lack physiologically and psychologically, and that human needs can be classified and hierarchically ordered by importance. Maslow himself divided the entire set of human needs into five large, hierarchically arranged groups: physiological needs; security needs; social needs; esteem and self-esteem needs; perfection needs. Physiological needs are the most important from a physiological point of view for the employee. It could be said that they are primary, because they are inherent not only to man, but also to every living being. If these kinds of needs (for example, those of health, sleep, water, food, etc.) are not satisfied, efforts to influence one's behavior by using means that can satisfy needs of a higher order are fruitless, because these funds will then not act as an incentive, i.e. will not cause motivation in the object of influence. The needs for security, economic stability, safety, psychological security occupy the next ascending level in the hierarchy of human needs, because they generally appear (feel or become aware) only after satisfying physiological needs. These kinds of needs are related to the future of the human individual. If a person's physiological needs are already satisfied, the problem of security that must be guaranteed to him "emerges". This is how specific needs arise, for example to preserve the state of work commitment (availability of a good job), formation of savings of money or other kind of funds in case of future needs of them, need for social insurance and others. At the third hierarchical level in the ascending gradation of human needs are social needs - the need for love, inclusion, acceptance by someone, belonging to a certain social group and others. When these needs are not met, the human individual adopts defensive behavior, withdrawing into himself and sharpening his attention to the external environment. The next group, fourth in order in the ascending gradation of human needs, consists of two internal levels: at the first level is the need for respect from others for the human individual; at the second level is an individual's need for self-respect. The need for self-respect is completely different from the need for respect from others. Highest in the hierarchy of human needs is the need for self-realization, for continuous development of abilities, for creative activity. So, in order to achieve his perfection, each person must "climb" the "ladder" of satisfying his own needs. Maslow's theory is a very successful attempt, although not final, to systematize the content and mutual conditioning of the variety of human needs. Its author gave impetus to a number of subsequent studies on motivation. He directs his attention to the higher needs, until then relatively less explored. His idea of hierarchy is very strong, though not undisputed, and reveals the dynamics and consistency in human motivation.

The idea of the "pyramid of human needs" contains the following important ideas: People act to satisfy certain needs of their own. The engine of human activity is unsatisfied human needs; Individual groups of human needs are hierarchically interconnected. People direct their efforts first to satisfy their priority needs (bottom - up the steps of the pyramid). Only when they have satisfied them at a certain level do they direct their activity towards satisfying the next set of needs. These ideas have important implications for management practice. In order to effectively influence the behavior of employees in the organization, one must know the level and manner of satisfying their needs. This would give guidelines for the current direction of the individual employee, for the things that are important/unimportant for him, for the distribution of his personal resources, etc. n., accordingly, it can help to direct this employee to appropriate organizational roles, tasks, in order to form an appropriate organizational environment.

If Maslow's ideas about human needs are interpreted literally, managers can be "suggested" the following connections between groups of needs and areas of managerial influence: physiological needs (fair salary, comfortable working conditions); need for security (safe working conditions, workplace security); social needs (opportunities for social interaction, group stability, stimulation of cooperation) and others.

Another theory, the two-factor theory of motivation by F. Herzberg focuses on two groups of factors - supporting and motivating. Supporting factors are related to the avoidance of dissatisfaction (dissatisfaction) - company policy and administration, technical supervision, interpersonal relations with the immediate supervisor, equals and subordinates, salary, job security, personal life, working conditions, organizational status. These factors do not create strong motivation. The following factors are considered motivating: achievement, recognition, promotion, work itself, opportunity for personal development, responsibility. These factors cause strong motivation, but their absence does not lead to strong dissatisfaction. The supporting factors can be interpreted primarily as external, related to the conditions of the environment, and the motivating factors - as internal, related to the nature of the work performed and the satisfaction from its performance. The supporting factors are: the policy and management of the economic institution; the discipline in the economic institution; working conditions and workplace security; the payment of labor; the connections with the members of the group to which the respective person belongs; personal life; relationships with his subordinates (if any); social status; social security and service. If any of these factors is at a lower level than the level in the branch or region, improving its level causes a decrease in staff dissatisfaction, i.e. an increase in staff satisfaction in the relevant business unit is determined. However, when hygiene factors cause complete satisfaction, continuing their positive development, an increase in the degree of satisfaction cannot be achieved. Then the motivational factors should be used, namely: personal progress through a corresponding change in the type of official work; recognition to the person for the result of work; satisfaction of personal interest by assigning work corresponding to it; increasing the responsibility of the employee in the overall work of the organization; growth in professional career. In summary, Herzberg's theory states that an individual's satisfaction is the result of the job itself, and his dissatisfaction—from working conditions. Interesting work satisfies him, but routine repels him. In turn, bad working conditions repel him, but suitable ones satisfy him.

In his theory of needs, McClelland identified three important higher needs: 1) Achievement; 2) Affiliation; 3) Authority. People's motivation at work is built on the basis of these three needs. People learn them if they see in their surroundings opportunities to satisfy them. The need for achievement is an

individual's need to bring the things he has undertaken to a successful conclusion. The need for belonging and affiliation is a need to establish and maintain favorable relationships and to provide assistance and empathy to a particular group of people. The need for power is the need to influence other people in order to achieve a certain result. McClelland's theory is known to be as attractive as it is practical. It is easy to remember - there are only three needs and these are the main parameters of motivation. At the same time, managers discover simple but effective ways to apply theory to their practice. It is enough to analyze the positions in the company to understand whether the jobs orient people towards achievements. Or to assess the extent to which the reward system orients people's behavior towards achievement. McClelland's most important conclusions and recommendations for motivation are: People with a highly developed need for achievement: a/ Prefer to avoid very easy and overly difficult goals (tasks); b/ They prefer to have immediate and reliable feedback on how they work; c/ They should not be directed to management positions, because they will be extremely demanding of their subordinates, which is not always useful for calm work. People with a strong need for power: They perform best in leadership positions when their need for achievement harmonizes with the need for achievement of subordinates; People who are suitable for leadership positions should have a moderately developed need for power and a low degree of need for affiliation. David McClelland was convinced that people were able to change their needs by being taught the three needs.

Clayton Alderfer's theory is another modern human resource management development theory known by the acronym ERG. In it, he modifies Maslow's hierarchy of needs into three levels: 1) Existence—these are physiological needs and Maslow's need for security; 2) Relatedness – includes needs for relationships: social and external respect (relationships in family, friends, colleagues and employers). Third and fourth levels of Maslow's hierarchy. 3) Growth—this refers to the self-actualization needs that unite Maslow's fourth and fifth levels. The ERG-theory (abbreviation made up of the first letters of the indicated three levels of needs) is a more concentrated variant compared to Maslow's theory. In an applied aspect, the ERG-theory diagnoses motivational problems in the company by seeking answers to the following questions related to its functioning: what needs does the specific employee have now; which of his needs are met and how; which of his unsatisfied needs is lower in the hierarchy; are higher level needs unmet and why; has he redirected himself to some lower-level need; how the "unmet" need can be satisfied. Employees may have many and varied needs that must be met simultaneously. According to this theory, focusing on one idea is an ineffective method of motivation.

Need theories do not adequately explain why people choose a behavior to satisfy their specific needs. This choice factor in motivation is at the center of process motivation theories. This group of theories is usually defined as more useful for the practical management of human resources because it is the basis of the applied motivational techniques (Ivanov, 1999). The theory of justice or the theory of social comparison of D. Stacey Adams argues that people want others to treat them with dignity. A sense of justice and a sense of injustice motivate them differently. In other words, people are sensitive to the relationships they have with other people. When they give something of themselves, they ask others to value it, and if they reciprocate, they maintain their relationships without changing them. Adams emphasizes the balance between what people give to their workplace and what they get out of it. Maintaining a balance is one of the important conditions to have motivation in the workplace. There are several basic concepts in Adams' theory of motivation through justice. Here they are: Inputs - this is the

individual's contribution to the organization. For example, time, effort, ability (qualification, skills, knowledge), loyalty, empathy, soul and heart, personal commitment and others; Output – what the individual receives in return for his input. For example salary, bonus, responsibility, security, development, reputation, pride, pleasure. Bilateral perception is the perception and comparison of an individual's contribution and output with the input and output of other colleagues. Equity is the feeling, the feeling, in which the perception and comparison of an individual's contribution and outcome is equal to the contribution and outcome of others. Negative inequity - this is the feeling, the feeling that the contribution of the individual and the contribution of his colleagues are the same, but the result of others is greater than his result. Positive Inequity – The feeling, the sense that the individual's contributions and the contributions of others are the same, but the individual's outcome is greater than the other's outcome. It is necessary to note that the theory of justice gives the company leadership and its managers an orientation and direction where and how to direct their efforts to neutralize the injustice in the actions of their companies. A good knowledge of company personnel from different levels about fairness and unfairness, and on this basis, is essential—the motivation to ensure fair remuneration and recognition of the personality of each of the employees or a group of employees.

The motivational theory of expectation, which was developed by V. Vroom, is one of the leaders in the theory of the motivation process. The degree of motivation of the employees of the organization for work (or other activity) depends on their perception and their ability to perform a certain work and the reality of reaching the set goals. According to the expectancy theory, not only people's needs have a motivational effect, but also their thought process, in which employees evaluate the real possibilities of achieving a given goal and receiving the corresponding reward. Expectancy theory is based on the following logic: people perform their work tasks in such a way as to receive the desired compensation. At the core of their activity is the possibility of choosing their desired behavior. Specific behavior is justified by the interplay of choices, expectations, and preferences. While choice is related to the possibility of realizing an alternative behavior, expectations are an expression of the relationship between the type of behavior and its associated consequences (eg, reward). Preferences reflect the meaning, meaning, value of the possible consequences of a given behavior. It affirms the dependence of the efforts made by the employee on his creation of real results from the set goal and the desire to reach it. An example can be the student's preparation for an exam. Let's assume that the student is preparing for the last exam, and he took the previous ones with very good and excellent grades. He knows he needs to get a grade of very good or excellent to get a bigger scholarship. His motivation will be influenced by: Belief in his abilities, i.e. that it can get an excellent grade; The desire to receive an increased scholarship. If the student was not confident that he could get an A, or that this grade would increase his scholarship, then he would not have the motivation to conscientiously prepare for the upcoming exam. The theory of expectation examines two types of expectations affecting the employee's efficiency in his work: 1) Do the efforts put in ensure a high degree of the assigned work; 2) Will the effective activity lead to the expected results. The degree of motivation is influenced by the value or attractiveness of the results obtained for the employee. If the results obtained with good work and considerable effort are not of interest to him, then his motivation will be at a low level. Conversely, results that are valuable to the employee generate strong motivation. Modern approaches to motivation are based on attempts to build integrative models that consider human behavior in its real context. The model of L. Porter and E. Lawler attempts to clarify the

relationship between performance, satisfaction and reward, but also includes the matching of tasks to the employee's skills, abilities and character traits. The main thesis of Porter and Lawler's theory of motivation is: "A man's desire to do his job well cannot sufficiently explain the strength, character, and content of his motivation. It is also necessary to take into account how he himself perceives his real possibilities in order to cope successfully". Thus, for example, an employee with greater abilities and skills, who is aware of his role and contributions to the company, undoubtedly achieves more results, at the cost of less effort. He is definitely a motivated employee, but in this case it is not about his desire that will motivate him, but about the awareness and appreciation of his own abilities, skills and contributions. Porter and Lawler's theory of motivation, also known as "expectancy theory", explains the results that an employee achieves using three variable factors: Effort; Human abilities and characteristics; Realization of the role by the employee himself. The level of effort, in turn, depends on the value of the reward and the extent to which the employee expects and believes in the existence of a strong relationship between effort and possible reward. According to Porter and Lawler, the performance of a task, with the expected final results, leads to two types of rewards: 1) Internal reward from the completed task - feeling of competence and self-respect; 2) External reward - praise from the manager, bonus, promotion, etc. When the internal and external rewards that the employee receives for the work performed are perceived by him as fair, he receives satisfaction from the work done. It can be seen that satisfaction is a measure of how valuable the reward is. And this assessment affects the person in future situations. This conclusion of Porter and Lawler, that productive work brings satisfaction, will probably come as a surprise to those managers who believe exactly the opposite, namely that happy (satisfied) employees have "by themselves" high performance in their work. It can be seen that one can also think in another way that Porter and Lawler suggest - a successful outcome is a cause of full satisfaction, not a consequence of it. However, this requires not only effort, but also capable people, appropriate rewards, adequate perceptions of rewards and values. which the employee achieves using three variables: Effort; Human abilities and characteristics; Realization of the role by the employee himself. The level of effort, in turn, depends on the value of the reward and the extent to which the employee expects and believes in the existence of a strong relationship between effort and possible reward. According to Porter and Lawler, the performance of a task, with the expected final results, leads to two types of rewards: 1) Internal reward from the completed task - feeling of competence and self-respect; 2) External reward - praise from the manager, bonus, promotion, etc. When the internal and external rewards that the employee receives for the work performed are perceived by him as fair, he receives satisfaction from the work done. It can be seen that satisfaction is a measure of how valuable the reward is. And this assessment affects the person in future situations. This conclusion of Porter and Lawler, that productive work brings satisfaction, will probably come as a surprise to those managers who believe exactly the opposite, namely that happy (satisfied) employees have "by themselves" high performance in their work. It can be seen that one can also think in another way that Porter and Lawler suggest - a successful outcome is a cause of full satisfaction, not a consequence of it. However, this requires not only effort, but also capable people, appropriate rewards, adequate perceptions of rewards and values. which the employee achieves using three variables: Effort; Human abilities and characteristics; Realization of the role by the employee himself. The level of effort, in turn, depends on the value of the reward and the extent to which the employee expects and believes in the existence of a strong relationship between effort and possible reward. According to Porter and Lawler,

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CONCLUSION

Motivation refers to those psychological processes that cause the emergence, direction and lasting reproduction of voluntary purposeful actions. Motivation is all those circumstances of inner drive that are described as desires, aspirations, urges, and others. It is an internal state that activates or drives motivation and relates to effort, persistence, and goals. Motivation is that network of relationships that predispose a person to act in a certain goal-directed way. Motivation is that internal state that activates, directs and sustains human behavior to achieve goals. The study of motivation is primarily concerned with why people act in certain ways. Motivation can be defined as the direction and duration of action.

Substantive motivational theories address the fundamental question facing each individual: "What prompts, stimulates, or initiates a given behavior?". The answer to this question is related to the concept that needs drive individuals to act in a certain way. Need theories do not adequately explain why people choose a behavior to satisfy their particular needs. This choice factor in motivation is at the center of process motivation theories. This group of theories is usually defined as more useful for the practical management of human resources because it is the basis of the applied motivational techniques.

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